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ABOUT THE JOURNAL

The *Global Research Journal of Business Management (GRJBM)* is a publication of the Association of Management and Social Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN). It is a peer-reviewed journal published both offline and in hardcopy, focusing on cutting-edge research and practical solutions in business management and related disciplines.

Scope

GRJBM invites research articles from a broad spectrum of topics, including but not limited to organizational behavior, strategic management, financial management, human resource management, entrepreneurship, and the impact of technology on business processes.

Vision

To be a global leader in fostering scholarly debates and disseminating high-quality, timely, and impactful research on contemporary business management issues.

Mission

To continuously provide an intellectually stimulating platform for academics, practitioners, and policymakers to share insights, drive innovation, and contribute to the advancement of business management practices worldwide.

EDITORIAL PREFACE

We are pleased to present Volume 3, Issue 2 of the *Global Research Journal of Business Management (GRJBM)*, a publication of the Association of Management and Social Sciences Researchers of Nigeria (AMSSRN). As a trusted platform for the dissemination of impactful research, GRJBM continues to deliver high-quality, peer-reviewed articles that address contemporary challenges and opportunities in the realm of business management.

This issue features an engaging collection of articles that examine critical themes such as economic development through entrepreneurship, the impact of COVID-19 on entrepreneurship, corporate workplace management and non-life insurance claims. Together, these studies reflect the journal's commitment to advancing knowledge and informing practice within Nigeria and beyond.

We are deeply grateful to our contributors for their insightful work and to our reviewers and editorial team for their dedication to maintaining the high standards of GRJBM. The unwavering support of AMSSRN has also been instrumental in the continued success of this journal.

We trust that the articles in this issue will stimulate meaningful discussions and provide actionable insights for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers.

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INNOVATION IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Innovation in Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Economic Development

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ABSTRACT

Research Purpose: The study examined the link between innovation in entrepreneurship and sustainable economic development.

Methodology: The indicators of entrepreneurship innovation, such as product innovation and process innovation, were compared to the indicators of economic development, such as wealth generation and employment creation. The questionnaire was the major method used to collect data from the primary source to achieve this. The Spearman rank correlation statistic was used to provide answers to the research questions to establish the relationship between the dependent and independent variables in the study. The hypotheses were tested with the Theil-Sen regression technique with the aid of the *Eview* statistical package.

Findings: The findings of the first hypothesis show a significant relationship between product innovation in entrepreneurship and wealth generation. This is achieved as the mean squares of 738.31 were gotten for product innovation and 11.09 for residuals, an F-calculation value of 66.603, and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. The second hypothesis was tested to determine the degree of relationship between process innovation in entrepreneurship and employment creation. The findings show mean squares of 547.47 for process innovation in entrepreneurship and 7.30 for residuals, an F-calculation value of 75.036, and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, concluding that there is a significant relationship between process innovation in entrepreneurship and employment creation.

Recommendations: Based on the findings, the study recommends, among others, that small and medium enterprises should intensify their efforts towards innovating their products. This can be achieved by injecting funds into their research and development (R&D) department to find new ways of enhancing their product quality, packaging, and standards.

Keywords: Innovation, Entrepreneurship, Economic development, Product, Process, Wealth generation and employment creation.

Introduction

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Organizations are designed to satisfy the needs of their consumers while also turning a profit. The right kind of human resource—the entrepreneur—is what businesses need to transform their products, operations, and marketing because they are constantly looking for new ways to do so. To grow the economy, create jobs, raise living standards, and meet modern social expectations, entrepreneurship is essential. Innovative entrepreneurship can produce ideas for growing both new and existing businesses, producing goods to boost local economies, and fostering change for improved customer experiences. Because innovation is a key component of successful businesses, it is beneficial to understand what it entails.

Innovation research has advanced significantly in recent years. Innovation can take one of five various forms, including new goods, processes, markets, sources of supply, and industrial organizations, according to Ukpog, Kingsley, and Uforo (2022). Innovation, according to Schumpeter (1934), is the creative fusion of pre-existing elements. According to Van Kleef and Roome (2017), innovation is "the process of discovery and development that results in new goods, manufacturing processes, organizations, technology, and institutional and systemic structures."

The process of starting a business is referred to as entrepreneurship. One of the four resources that economists classify as essential to production, together with land/natural resources, labor, and capital, is entrepreneurship. The first three of these are combined by an entrepreneur to create products or render services. They usually write a business plan, hire staff, gather materials and funding, and provide the company direction and management.

The act of establishing and developing new business ideas with the intention of making a profit, assisting their community, and achieving organizational objectives is known as innovation in entrepreneurship. To suit an organization's needs and increase their marketability, creative entrepreneurs create business models. Most business owners use cutting-edge concepts to develop new versions of these models or improve the ones they already have. This inspiration can be used to create creative company success plans.

Innovation in entrepreneurship is crucial for spotting emerging trends and consumer demands. This makes it easier for a business to create new products or services that appeal to its target market. A company may continue to develop innovative products, services, or updated brand development to stay relevant in order to respond to current trends in its industry.

Innovation is the application of a new or considerably enhanced product, good or service, process, a new marketing approach, or a new organizational system in business or workplace organizations, according to Szabo, K. Z. and Emilia H. (2012) in OSLO Manual OECD, (2005). On the other hand, entrepreneurs are firm owners who aim to create or increase economic activity by discovering and utilizing new items in order to generate value, according to OECD, 2007b. Innovative entrepreneurship, or new businesses built on fresh innovative ideas, is what happens when entrepreneurship and innovation are combined.

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But innovation varies according on the topics the study wants to look at. Innovation in both products and processes falls under this category. Product innovation is the creation of items or services that differ considerably from the company's earlier offerings in terms of their attributes or intended uses (Olaru, 2016). Process innovation, according to Maier D. (2015), is the significant alteration of particular methods, tools, and/or software with the goal of lowering production and distribution costs, enhancing the production or distribution of new or improved goods, boosting productivity or supply activity flexibility, and lowering environmental risks.

The four pillars of sustainability are human, social, economic, and environmental. According to Futurelean.com, the conference's focus is only on economic sustainability. Economic growth that also results in higher living standards that everyone may experience is referred to as being economically sustainable. Sustainable economic growth is inclusive economic growth that can be felt throughout the entire country. However, the study uses a few South South SMEs in Nigeria to investigate the connection between entrepreneurship innovation and sustainable economic development.

Statement of the problem

Numerous studies have shown that entrepreneurship innovation has a favorable effect on economic growth. After researching the American pharmaceutical industry, Roberts (2019) discovered that innovation activities have a beneficial impact on organizations' ROI over the long term. Based on an empirical analysis of Fortune 1000 businesses, Cho and Pucik (2005) came to the conclusion that an organization's ability to innovate was positively correlated with its ability to grow and be profitable.

If we look more closely at the opinions of the experts mentioned above, we see that the majority of their study is conducted outside without taking into account the business environment in Africa, particularly Nigeria. By using a few selected Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Imo state, Nigeria, the researcher is attempting to close a geographic, unit, and content gap while taking into account the differing perspectives of various researchers in the field.

Objective of the study

The major goal is to evaluate entrepreneurial innovation for sustainable economic growth. The specific objectives include to;

- (a) examine the relationship between product innovation in entrepreneurship and wealth generation.
- (b) ascertain the relationship between process innovation in entrepreneurship and employment creation.

Research Questions

- (a) What is the relationship between product innovation in entrepreneurship and wealth generation?
- (b) To what extent is the relationship between process innovation in entrepreneurship and employment creation?

Hypotheses formulation

- (a) There is no significant relationship between product innovation in entrepreneurship and wealth generation.
- (b) Process innovation in entrepreneurship does not significantly relate to employment creation.

Scope of the study

The scope of this study is examined based on three categories; the content scope, geographic scope and unit scope.

The relationship between the independent and dependent variables is examined via the content scope. Innovation in entrepreneurship serves as the study's independent variable, with the measurement criteria being product and process innovation, and sustainable economic development serves as the study's dependent variable, with the measurement criteria being wealth creation and employment creation.

The Aluminum and Paint Industries in Imo State, Nigeria, that are included in the study's geographic scope are Vina Aluminium Industries at Okigwe Road, Max Aluminium at Portharcourt Road, Gmicord Aluminium and Pritec Supergel Factory at Onitsha Road Industrial Layout, Dulux Owerri at Ikenegbu Layout by Maris Junction, Silvercad Ventures Limited at Emekuku Road, and Megalux Paint at Ikenegbu Owerri. The selection was motivated by Imo State's high concentration of small and medium-sized businesses.

The unit scope is the management and staff of the selected enterprises.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The study examines related literature in the area of conceptual, theoretical and empirical review.

Independent variable

Dependent variable

Fig. 1: Operational Conceptual Framework

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The relationship between the Independent variable and Dependent variable was diagrammatically explained by the operational conceptual framework. The independent variable in this graphic is innovation, with indicators like "product and process innovation," and the dependent variable is economic development, with metrics like "wealth creation and employment creation."

Conceptual Review

The Concept of Innovation

The word innovation comes from the Latin innovare, which means "into new." Innovations can be summed up in the simplest terms as doing something new. Fundamentally, innovation may be defined as the act of coming up with and fusing ideas in order to connect recent successes with earlier learnings in order to address problems in the future. This is frequently connected to technical advances and is important to the global economy (Baskaran & Mehta, 2016).

Types of Innovation

Ukpong, Kingsley, & Uforo (2022) opined that types of innovation include but not limited to product (including goods and services), process and marketing.

Product Innovation

Product innovation, according to Atalay et al. (2013), is the introduction and creation of new types of goods or services that are distinct from those that have previously existed and fill in the gaps left by the previous results while placing a greater emphasis on quality. Companies that create new products must pay close attention to market orientation since understanding market orientation is essential to creating successful new products (Wiwoho, 2012).

Process innovation

According to Maier, Olaru, and Eidenmüller (2015), process innovation is a novel approach to creating or delivering a new good or service. Examples include innovations in production procedures, technical roadmaps, or manufacturing tools. In the manufacturing of washing machines, a process innovation could be the adoption of a new sheet material or the substitution of a conventional machine tool with a computerized numerical control (CNC) machine tool, both of which result in cost savings of up to 50% or productivity increases of three times or more (Demircioglu, 2016).

The meaning of an Entrepreneurship

In the business realm, entrepreneurship refers to the idea of creating and running an enterprise in order to make money by taking various risks. Entrepreneurship is simply the desire to launch a new enterprise. The expansion of the world market's economy has been greatly aided by entrepreneurship. The majority of individuals could believe that there is only one definition for the word "entrepreneurship."

Sustainable Economic Development

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The fundamental tenet of sustainable economic development is that the majority of environmental issues result from a lack of growth. Because they frequently have few options, groups in poverty opt for short-term financial gains over long-term sustainable solutions. This study focused on two aspects of economic development: wealth creation and job creation.

Wealth generation

Wealth creation is the process of investing your saved funds to increase your wealth by selecting investments that line up with your financial objectives. In addition to making the appropriate investment, you must give your investments enough time to grow if you want to generate enough wealth.

Employment creation

In Nigeria, one of the most significant social and economic challenges is employment. It is viewed as a partnership between two persons, typically established through an employment contract. In other terms, employment is defined as the total population of workers in a community, state, or nation. Entrepreneurial innovation has a method of giving young people who are unemployed jobs. This is due to the fact that new employees will be hired to manage the organization's operations, which brings fresh blood into the organizational system. A natural process of social and economic development is the creation of jobs.

Theoretical Review

Entrepreneurship Innovation Theory

Alois Joseph Schumpeter Known as one of the greatest economists of the 20th century, he gave the ideas of entrepreneurship and innovation life. His hypothesis in Natasha (2017) states that innovation may be used to:

1. The introduction of a new product or an improved version of an existing product;
2. the use of novel sales or production techniques;
3. the opening of a new market;
4. the purchase of novel raw material sources; and
5. the exploitation of novel industrial structures, such as the dissolution of monopolies.

Thankfully, you don't need to have the genes of Mark Zuckerberg or Elon Musk to exemplify entrepreneurship and innovation. It is a spirit that resides and comes from within, accessible to one and all as long as there is a burning desire to *find* it.

According to Natasha (2017), Milton Hershey failed terribly more than once before establishing the biggest chocolate manufacturing facility in the world. Or Theodore Geisel, an unsuccessful author whose work was rejected 27 times before it was published, better known as Dr. Seuss. Innovation is not a rare, expensive good that only a select few can afford, as Hershey, Geisel, and many other companies demonstrate. She suggests that one shouldn't anticipate a slowdown in entrepreneurial innovation any time soon. The way people interact with the world is changing thanks to entrepreneur-driven innovations, which range from cutting-edge devices like the iPhone to entertaining, basic toys like the Fidget Spinner. This trend is only expected to intensify.

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Empirical Review

Roberts (2019) used longitudinal research in the U.S. pharmaceutical business to analyze the effects of product innovativeness on the sustainable efficiency of organizations. The statistical tool employed was the correlation coefficient. He discovered evidence for the expected association between a strong propensity for product innovation and sustained higher efficiency based on the analysis.

Cho and Pucik (2015) used the structural equation modeling method to investigate the relationship between innovativeness, quality, growth, efficiency, and market value at the firm level in the U.S. financial industry. Their research showed that quality mediates the association between innovativeness and efficiency, whereas quality mediates the relationship between innovativeness and growth.

Gap in Literature

The motivation behind the authors' decision to conduct this study was never fully reflected by empirical work on innovation in entrepreneurship for sustainable economic growth. This is due to the fact that the majority of studies on innovation focused on how it affected organizations' productivity or performance, making them fall outside the current study's topic area. Additionally, the majority of studies used foreign nations like the USA, creating a geographic divide. By investigating the link between entrepreneurship innovation and economic development using Nigeria as a case study, the current study closes the knowledge gap.

METHODOLOGY

The methodologies and processes utilized to carry out the study are thoroughly described in this chapter.

Research Design

In order to obtain responses sufficient for evaluating the association between innovation in entrepreneurship and economic development in Imo State, Nigeria, this study used the survey research design approach. Because of its advantages, the survey research design was thought to be the most suitable for the study.

Population of the Study

195 employees from the 6 small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) operating in Imo State make up the study's population. 195 employees from the companies made up the study's total number of measuring units.

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

The total population of the study, which consists of the six (6) aluminum and paint enterprises in Imo State, Nigeria, is the sample size chosen for this study. The population is tiny and controllable, thus this was done. Here, the idea of census size is used.

The Taro Yamen formula is used to calculate the sample size of responders in the following paragraphs.

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$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = Sample size sought
 e = Level of significance
 N = Population size
 1 = the theoretical constant

$$n = \frac{195}{1 + 195(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{195}{1 + 195(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{195}{1 + 0.4875}$$

$$n = \frac{195}{1.4875}$$

$$n = 131 \text{ respondents}$$

Sources of Data

Data for the study were generated through the primary data sources with the use of questionnaire. In this study primary data was collected through the structured questionnaire.

Validity and Reliability

Validity

The content and face validity were used to determine the degree to which the instrument can be claimed to be accurate and exact in the measurement of the variables under inquiry. This was done to assure the validity of the instruments for this study. Before being given to the study's target participants, the study's instrument was reviewed by research professionals.

3.7.2 Reliability

When evaluating the validity of the study instrument, the Cronbach alpha was used; items with return alpha coefficients of 0.7 and above were deemed suitable and adequate for inclusion in the analysis, whereas items with return alpha coefficients of less than 0.7 were deemed unsuitable and unqualified for inclusion in the analysis (Nunally," 2008).

3.9 Method of Data Analysis

In order to determine the link between the dependent and independent variables in the study, the research questions were addressed using the Spearman rank correlation statistic. Theil-Sen regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses with the use of the Eview statistical program in order to quantify the "significance" of the degree of correlations between the dependent and independent variables. This suggested that it was useful in determining whether or not the relationship's coefficient was significant.

RESULT

The presentation of the result is according to the research questions and hypotheses.

Tests for Normality Assumption for the Bivariate Regression Model

The residuals from the model must be regularly distributed in order to satisfy this premise. We can test a specific hypothesis regarding a bivariate regression model when residuals are regularly distributed. Therefore, it becomes crucial from a statistical perspective to look at the normalcy assumption before moving on to the hypotheses. However, it should be emphasized that employing the regression model directly results in mistake in the interpretation of the results when the assumption fails. When the error term is not normally distributed, there are two things to do: (i) Detecting outliers and deleting them before testing the hypotheses and (ii) using its non-parametric equivalent, which is the Theil's regression model, since it is assumption free. Here we tested the normality assumption based on using each of the dependent variables with each of the independent variables via the Anderson-Darling Statistic.

Normality of Errors Assumption – wealth generation versus product innovation in entrepreneurship

To test for normal distributed errors, we employed the Jarque-Bera test for normality. The hypotheses of the Jarque-Bera test are as follows:

H_0 : Errors are normally distributed

H_1 : Errors are not normally distributed

Normal Probability Plot of Residual for wealth generation & product innovation

Source: Eviews software

Since the p-value (0.523) is greater than 0.05 from Fig.4.1, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that the assumption of normality distributed errors is satisfied.

Normality of Errors Assumption – Employment creation versus process innovation

To test for normal distributed errors, we employed the Jarque-Bera test for normality. The hypotheses of the Jarque-Bera test are as follows:

H_0 : Errors are normally distributed

H_1 : Errors are not normally distributed

Normal Probability Plot of Residual for Employment creation versus process innovation

Source: Eviews software

Since the p-value (0.163) is greater than 0.05 from Fig. 4.2, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that the assumption of normality distributed errors is satisfied.

Analysis and Results of Research Questions

Research Questions/Hypotheses One to Two

In this section, the Spearman rank correlation coefficient and the Theil regression techniques were employed to address research questions and hypotheses respectively since the normality assumption of the error term was not all satisfied.

Research Question One

1. What is the relationship between product innovation in entrepreneurship and wealth generation?

Table 4.1: Spearman’s Rank Correlation Summary for wealth generation and product innovation in entrepreneurship

Variables	n	Σ	\bar{X}	SD	r
Wealth creation	131	1268	9.679	4.052	0.584
Product innovation	131	1216	9.282	3.178	

Moderate Relationship

Source: Extracted from SPSS Output (See Appendix III)

Table 4.1 shows the result obtained in respect of research question one. The result reveals that the Spearman rank correlation coefficient is 0.584, which is moderate. This implies that there is a moderate relationship between product innovation and wealth generation.

Testing of Hypothesis One

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between product innovation in entrepreneurship and wealth generation

Table 4.2: ANOVA Summary for Theil-Sen Regression of product innovation in entrepreneurship and wealth generation

Response: wealth generation	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-value	p-value
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Product innovation	1	738.31	738.31		
				66.603	0.000
Residuals	129	1430.00	11.09		

Source: Extracted from R-Studio Output

Table 4.2's conclusion reveals mean squares for product innovation of 738.31 and residuals of 11.09, an F-calculation value of 66.603, and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This signifies a result that is statistically significant. The null hypothesis, according to which there is no meaningful connection between product innovation in entrepreneurship and wealth creation, is thus disproved. As a result, the research comes to the conclusion that entrepreneurship and wealth creation are significantly related.

Research Question Two

2. To what extent is the relationship between process innovation in entrepreneurship and employment creation?

Table 4.3: Spearman's Rank Correlation Summary for process innovation in entrepreneurship and employment creation

Variables	N	Σ	\bar{X}	SD	r
Employment creation	131	1985	15.153	3.336	
Process innovation	131	1216	9.282	3.178	0.585

Moderate Relationship

Source: Extracted from SPSS Output

Table 4.3 shows the result obtained in respect of research question two. The result reveals that the Spearman rank correlation coefficient is 0.585, which is moderate. This implies that there is a moderate relationship between process innovation in entrepreneurship and employment creation.

Testing of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Process innovation in entrepreneurship does not significantly relate to employment creation.

Table 4.4: ANOVA Summary for Theil-Sen Regression of process innovation in entrepreneurship and employment creation

Response: employment creation	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-value	p-value
Process innovation in entrepreneurship	1	547.47	547.47		

	75.036	0.000	
Residuals	129	941.19	7.30

Source: Extracted from R-Studio Output

The result in table 4.4 shows the mean squares of 547.47 for process innovation in entrepreneurship and 7.30 for residuals, F-calculation value of 75.036 and a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This indicates statistically significant result. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between process innovation in entrepreneurship and employment creation is rejected. Hence, the study concludes that there is significant relationship between process innovation in entrepreneurship and employment creation.

5.0 This section discussed the findings based on the analysis, made conclusion as well as recommendations.

Discussion of Findings

According to hypothesis one of the study, there is a strong correlation between wealth creation in entrepreneurship and product innovation. A p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, and mean squares of 738.31 for product innovation and 11.09 for residuals, with an F-calculation value of 66.603, were obtained. This signifies a result that is statistically significant.

Additionally, the study's second hypothesis claimed that process innovation in entrepreneurship greatly influences job creation. The results showed that the mean squares for process innovation in entrepreneurship were 547.47 and for residuals were 7.30, with an F-calculation value of 75.036 and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This signifies a result that is statistically significant. These results are consistent with research by Roberts (2019), who used longitudinal data from the American pharmaceutical industry to assess how product innovation affects a company's ability to operate sustainably. He discovered evidence to support the predicted association between a strong propensity for product innovation and sustained excellent efficiency. Additionally, the work of (Cho and Pucik 2015) used structural equation modeling to explore the relationship between innovativeness, quality, growth, efficiency, and market value at the business level in the US financial industry. Their research showed that quality mediates the association between innovativeness and efficiency, whereas quality mediates the relationship between innovativeness and growth.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurial growth and economic sustainability depend on innovation. Innovative businesses produce money and provide jobs for young people. The study draws the conclusion that entrepreneurship innovation and sustainable economic development are significantly related.

Recommendations

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Based on the findings, the study recommends among others that;

- (a) Small and Medium enterprises should intensity effort towards innovating their products, this can be achieved by injecting funds into their research and development department to find new ways of enhancing their product quality, packaging and standard.
- (b) Entrepreneurs of SMEs should update their equipments and machines that they use in their manufacturing activities, new employees who are computer literate should be employed to ensure that their organizations are innovative in their process line of business.

REFERENCES

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INNOVATION IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Baskaran, E., & Mehta, A. (2016). *Strategies for improving research utilization*. *Technology Review*, 80(5), 32-39.

Demircioglu, M. (2016). *Primer on open innovation: Principles and practice*. *PDMA Visions*. 30(2), 1317.

Maier D., Olaru M., Maier A., Eidenmüller T. (2016). Importance of innovation in the context of changes arising from economic globalization, *International Business Information Management Association (IBIMA) 27th IBIMA Conference 4 – 5 May 2016*.

Natasha Lorraine Menezes (2017). *Decoding Theories that Make an Entrepreneur*. India: entrepreneur Oct 19.

Szabo ,K. Z and Emilia H (2012). *Innovative Entrepreneurship for Economic Development in EU*. *Procedia Economics and Finance* 3 (2012) 268 – 275

Ukpong, A. M, Kingsley L. U, and Uforo A. E. (2022). *Business Innovation and Organizational Sustainability: A Cross Sectional Study of Entrepreneurial Business in Uyo Metropolis*, *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, Vol.10, No.4, pp. 74-93.

Ukpong, A. M, Kingsley L. U, and Uforo A. E. (2022). *Business Innovation and Organizational Sustainability: A Cross Sectional Study of Entrepreneurial Business in Uyo Metropolis*, *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, Vol.10, No.4, pp. 74-93.

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IMPACT OF DIGITALIZATION ON EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE

The Impact of Digitalization on Employees' Performance in the Service Industry

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ABSTRACT

Research Purpose: This project studied the impact of digitalization on workers' performance in the service sector. The study specifically examined the effects of email technology, internet, and e-commerce technology on employee job effectiveness, turnover and productivity in the Nigerian service sector.

Methodology: A sample size of 400 was derived from the total population of 874,560 in IT business and users of IT selected in Nsukka zone of Enugu State Nigeria. Questionnaires were distributed to the sampled respondents as indicated above. A total of 364 questionnaires distributed were returned and were used in the analysis. The collected data were analyzed using simple tables and percentages, the hypotheses raised were analyzed using 2-tailed Pearson correlation.

Findings: Result of the analysis shows that E-mail technology has significant effect on employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector. It was also observed that internet technology has significant effect on employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector. The study further shows that E-commerce has significant effect on employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector.

Recommendations: In line with the findings, the study recommends that in order to benefit from their investment strategic human resource management which considers improvement of workers skill through training, apprenticeship and development should be given to the employee before new technology is introduced. Workers, working conditions to be improved and their salary and allowance be made to move along with increasing productivity and profitability in the industry. Workers union should ensure that the effects of technological change on their member's jobs are considered.

Keyword: *Digitalization, Employee Performance and Service Industry.*

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Background of the Study

Digitalization has become crucial as businesses, institutions, and service providers look to implement more efficient methods to serve their customers and loyal client base. According to Abbasi and Weigand (2017), the financial sector has benefited from information and communication technologies, particularly in the areas of risk management, support for banking services, and productivity growth. As a result, financial institutions have increased their investments in the process of digitalization. Abbasi and Weigand (2017) cited a study by Gareth et al. (2006) that claims that banks in North America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, and Latin America spent a total of \$241 billion on information technologies in the year 2016, and this represents an overall increase of almost 4% when compared with the year 2015. They reiterated that the practice of digitalizing financial institution services provides a fresh twist on service delivery and boosts customer satisfaction because of the variety in service provision.

Through supply chains, independent structures, outsourced manufacturing, contract manufacturing, and warehousing and delivery, technology has enabled the reconfiguration of design, marketing, production, delivery, and services. Technology's advancement has sparked an advanced digital transformation, which is not just limited to tech-savvy businesses but also high-tech major established organizations (Agboola et al., 2017; Weill and Woerner, 2018; Idiegbeyan-Ose, Ilo, and Isiakpona, 2015).

Digitalization is a paradigm shift that unavoidably has an impact on even the most established organizations, as well as on society as a whole (Sambamurthy et al., 2003; Gimpel & Roglinger, 2015). It is imperative to recognize how important industries, such as those in retail, media, transportation, and large industries, have been disrupted by digitalization. The service industry in Nigeria is currently experiencing this. Although the trend of digitalization has been around for a while, it appears to have recently had a particularly large impact and accelerated change. Because of digitization, the financial industry's working conditions have changed. Even though it's important to note that financial services have been automated for a while, a more drastic change might have been put off because most financial institutions were attempting to maintain their traditional financial modes of services (IFC, 2017). Business success has been a product of chance and free will. There are some discussions about how IT is affected by technological and commercial advancements (Anigbogu, Edoko, and Okoli, 2014). One major technological development that has an impact on all facets of business is the Internet. Businesses achieve their objectives by going outside automating their current processes and expanding their customer base, partnering with more companies, and utilizing the internet and mobile technologies to communicate effectively with governing bodies like governments (Tesfaye, 2014). Organizations can establish ways to connect with clients in a variety of ways thanks to mobile technology. Mobile

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technology, which includes mobile devices, networks, applications, and content management systems, has sparked significant organizational changes within the company as well as changes in customer relationships, the creation of customer groups, and inventory management practices. Customers can be reached using mobile technologies regardless of where they are in the world (Onu, et. al., 2015). The ability of mobile technology to personalize services has significantly raised customer expectations for the modern age of administration known as Mobile Customer Relationship Management (M-CRM).

One of the biggest barriers preventing business-to-consumer (B2C) business is customers' lack of trust. Due to the increased ability of businesses to connect, there are now international business opportunities and cross-border customer interactions that were not previously possible (Penalba, 2015). Because in the old-fashioned land-based internet, this phenomenon was nonexistent, businesses can use mobility in a way that is independent of place and time because users can access their applications at any time and from anywhere. The ideal outcome is the establishment of universal business and IT ethics. Now, companies would benefit from cutting-edge technologies, allowing them to intentionally obtain a small benefit through the proper provision of exceptional and improved customer services, thereby "locking them in" at any time to institute innovation, effective communication, and partnerships with other companies in the industry. Every organization needs information and communication technology, ICT (Al-Azzawi and Altmimi, 2015). ICT that is successful and of high quality can boost effectiveness and operational efficiency, strengthen organizational culture and potentially enhance business performance. Stair and Reynolds (2010) define information systems as including high-quality and reliable information and communication technology in addition to information capture, processing, and dissemination.

To streamline operations into a cohesive unit, provide management with critical data to support business decision-making, improve organizational communication, reduce the need for human labor, and increase employee productivity, a quality information system must contain pertinent, precise, thorough, adaptable, and timely information. Developing nations like Nigeria are still lagging in the use of ICT in production activities, despite the positive effects of ICT on economic productivity and development. Nigeria is dealing with serious ICT issues, which have contributed to the economy's continued decline due to difficulties in developing IT-related production functions.

Statement of Problems

The Nigerian economy lacks innovation, capacities, and ICT management capabilities. As a result, Nigeria's overall economic productivity and performance are low. The adoption of ICT in Nigerian organizations aims to increase the productivity and profitability of the company while achieving organizational efficiency and effectiveness. Additionally, it aids workers in acquiring particular

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abilities, and information, and retraining both on and off the job. Despite some attempts, ICT hasn't been able to eliminate the complexity of manual organization activities. This is due to the possibility of losing some system-stored data without manual documentation. The use of ICT has sped up and simplified business processes, but it hasn't been able to halt internal fraud or other irregularities. Information overload, increased work pressure, and worker equipment phobia are other effects of ICT use. For instance, businesses with cutting-edge technology perform specific tasks with robots rather than employees. By using ICT, employers can replace workers with incorrect qualifications and experience.

Information overload, which happens when a worker receives more information than he or she can process (for example, the more people use email, the more they feel like they can't handle it), is another significant issue brought on by ICT. As a result, this research tends to look at how digitalization has affected employee performance in the service sector.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the effect of email technology on employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector.
2. To ascertain the effect of internet technology on employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector.
3. To evaluate the effect of e-commerce on employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector.

Research Questions

1. What are the effects of email technology on employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector?
2. How does Internet technology affect employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector?
3. To what extent does e-commerce affect employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector?

Hypotheses Formulation

H₀₁: Email technology does not have any significant effect on employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector.

H₀₂: Internet technology does not have a significant effect on employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector.

H₀₃: E-commerce does not have a significant effect on employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

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Concept of Digitalization

According to Abdullahi, Shehu, and Usman (2019), the process of transitioning to a digital business is known as digitalization. It entails the use of digital technologies to alter a business model and offer new opportunities for generating revenue and value. Information is transformed into a digital (i.e., computer-readable) format during the digitization process. The result is the representation of a physical entity, such as an object, image, sound, document, or signal (typically an analog signal), which is created by generating a string of numbers that each describe a discrete collection of points or samples. This result is known as digital representation, or more specifically, a digital image, and for the signal, it is known as digital form. However, digitizing simply refers to "the conversion of analog source material into a numerical format"; the decimal or any other number system may be used instead (Abdullahi, Shehu, and Usman, 2019).

Tesfaye (2014) argued that digitization is crucial to data processing, storage, and transmission because it "allows information of all kinds in all formats to be carried with the same efficiency and also intermingled." Digital data has the potential to be easier to share and access over analog data and, in theory, can be propagated indefinitely without generation loss, provided it is converted to new, stable formats as necessary. Due to this potential, institutions have begun digitization initiatives to increase access, and the field of digital preservation has expanded quickly.

Stair and Reynolds, (2010) are of the view that digitization and digital preservation are sometimes confused with one another. Although they are distinct from one another, digitization is frequently an essential first step in digital preservation. To preserve fragile materials and increase customer access points, archives, libraries, and other memory institutions digitize their collections. Information professionals face difficulties as a result of this, and there is a wide range of potential solutions. As some analog materials, like audio and video tapes, approach the end of their useful lives, it is critical to digitize them before media degradation and equipment obsolescence render the data unrecoverable. The challenges and consequences of digitization include issues with time, and money, and providing a good place for historically underrepresented voices. Many organizations that digitize create their solutions to these problems. Over the years, mass digitization initiatives have had varying degrees of success; however, several institutions found success despite not using the conventional platform called Google Books (Penalba, 2015).

Oni and Koko, (2020) are of the view that digitizing is the primary method of storing images in a format suitable for transmission and computer processing despite the source of the image. Producing a digital map with a geographic information system is also essential. To create electronic maps, one can either digitize conventional paper maps or graphs (vector) or use satellite imaging (raster).

The process of transferring files or data into databases is also known as "digitization." Although technically incorrect, this usage derives from the term's earlier correct use to describe the step of

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the process that involves digitizing analog sources, like printed pictures, before uploading them to the target databases. The apparel industry can also benefit from digitizing, as an image can be recreated using technological tools.

Email Technology

Electronic mail, also known as email or e-mail, is a way for people to communicate with one another through electronic devices. The email was created as the digital equivalent of mail in the period when "mail" just refers to the physical type (combination of the letters e + mail). Later, email developed into an extremely popular communication tool, and in most countries today, an email address is frequently regarded as a fundamental and essential component of many processes in business, commerce, government, education, entertainment, and other areas of daily life (Olaoye, Olaofe-Obasesin and Akanni, 2019). Email is accessible over both local area networks and computer networks, primarily the Internet. The store-and-forward model is the foundation of present-day email systems. Email servers receive, deliver, forward, and store emails. Users and their computers do not need to be online at the same time to send or receive messages; instead, they simply need to establish a connection to a mail server or webmail interface.

Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions (MIME) have allowed Internet email, which was initially an ASCII text-only communication tool, to carry attachments with multimedia content and text in other character sets. While international email is standardized and uses UTF-8 for internationalized email addresses, it is not yet widely used. The term "electronic mail" and the shorter form "e-mail" have been in use since 1979. According to Olanrewaju (2016), the name "email" is now the most popular format and is advised by style manuals. It is the format required by working groups and IETF Requests for Comments (RFC). The majority of dictionaries use this spelling as well. The phrase, e-mail, was first used in the Journal of Electronics concerning the E-COM program of the United States Postal Service in June 1979. One piece of email is known as a message, and the service is frequently just referred to as mail. With the release of RFC-680 in 1975, the conventions for email fields such as "To," "From," "CC," and "BCC" were established. After the introduction of time-sharing in the early 1960s, computer-based messaging between users of the same system became feasible. MIT's CTSS project made this possible in 1965. Early mainframe and minicomputer programmers primarily created similar but typically incompatible mail applications. The initial ARPANET network mail, which introduced the now-common address syntax with the '@' symbol designating the user's system address, was sent in 1971. Conventions for sending mail messages over the File Transfer Protocol were honed over several RFCs.

Internet Technology

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Internet is a technical field that covers the skills required to create applications for the Internet or Internet-based systems, with the help of e-commerce, cloud, mobile, and web technologies. It should be possible for students who studied computer technology to develop applications using internet-based tools and software. This will help them pursue their desire to learn more about the Internet or broaden their employment options in positions such as Internet technology specialists, architects, systems analysts, infrastructure support, and other related positions respectively. The internet is a group of computers that are located all over the world and are linked to one another by a high-speed network. The primary means of transferring knowledge and exchanging cultures are now the internet. All networks and computers that are connected exchange information and make use of different services. Although it is the most widely used service, the World Wide Web (or Web3) is only one of the services that the Internet provides to its users (Okey-Colbert, and Ukandu, 2019).

The world's interconnected computer networks make up the internet. The Internet offers an infinite number of informational resources and services, including file sharing, email, telephony, and the Web's interconnected hypertext documents and applications. As a repository for human culture and knowledge, the Web was created to enable remote team members to communicate and share ideas on all facets of a single project. It is made up of a huge variety of files and documents that are kept on these computers and written in a type of Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML) that instructs browsers how to display the data. Because they can handle requests from numerous users concurrently, the computers that house the files are referred to as servers. Through programs known as browsers, users can access these HTML files and documents (Dampana and Agbeyegbe, 2017).

E-commerce(electronic commerce)

E-commerce is the electronic purchasing or selling of goods through online marketplaces or the Internet. A few of the technologies used in e-commerce include electronic data interchange (EDI), supply chain management, electronic funds transfers, inventory management, internet marketing, online transactions, and automated data collection systems. The largest sector of the electronics industry, e-commerce is in turn driven by technological advancements in the semiconductor sector (Al-Azzawi and Altmimi, 2015). The California Electronic Commerce Act, sponsored by the late Committee Chairwoman Gwen Moore (D-L.A.), and passed in 1984, was the first law to use the term, which was created by a state assembly consultant in California, Robert Jacobson. Although other technologies, like e-mail, may also be used, e-commerce typically uses the web for at least some of the life cycle of a transaction. E-commerce transactions are typically made to buy goods (like books from Amazon) or services (like music downloads from digital music stores like the iTunes Store). Online retail, electronic markets, and online auctions are the three subfields of e-

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commerce. The electronic business provides a foundation for e-commerce. The purpose of e-commerce is to enable consumers to shop online and make payments online via the Internet, saving both customers' and businesses' time and space while also significantly improving transaction efficiency, especially for time-constrained office workers (Akwu, Duke, and Inuaesiet, 2021).

There are two groups of contemporary electronic commerce. The first category is based on the products that are sold and includes everything from ordering "digital" content for immediate online consumption to ordering regular goods and services to ordering "meta" services to support other forms of electronic commerce. Based on the type of participant (B2B, B2C, C2B, and C2C), the second category is created. Large corporations and financial institutions use the Internet to exchange financial data to support domestic and international trade on an institutional level. For electronic commerce, data security, and integrity are critical concerns.

Employee Performance

Performance is the accomplishment of a specific task as measured against established or predetermined accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed standards. Performance in an employment contract is defined as the accomplishment of a commitment in a way that releases the performer from all obligations outlined in the contract. According to Kenney (1992), an organization's performance standards are used to gauge an employee's performance. The quality of an employee's performance on a task is referred to as their performance. There are certain performance standards that employees must meet in every organization and they are regarded as good performers when they perform under the established standards and organizational expectations. Performance can also be defined as the effective management and presentation of employees' tasks that reflect the quality the organization wants.

Strategic planners, operations managers, finance directors, legal counsel, and business owners (the company's owners) are just a few of the experts who are concerned with the employee's performance and job effectiveness in an organization. Many organizations have tried using the balanced scorecard methodology to manage organizational performance in recent years, where performance is tracked and measured in multiple dimensions like financial results, customer support; social accountability, such as corporate citizenship and community involvement; and staff stewardship. To increase organizational effectiveness in the pursuit of their missions and objectives, organizations use performance management, a systematic process that involves both individuals and groups of employees. Planning the work and establishing expectations, monitoring performance constantly, building performance capacity, periodically rating performance, and rewarding good performance are all part of employee performance management.

Salary has been identified as a key determinant of employee improvement in performance and has been demonstrated to have an impact on the employee turnover rate, which is the proportion of

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workers who leave an organization in a year. Performance improvements and performance-based compensation are positively correlated. Every employee works harder to produce more units because they all want to earn more money. Performance-based compensation encourages and motivates employees to use their creativity to produce more effort. Capable workers earn more than average workers as a result of these performance-based payments. In case studies of various businesses, it was discovered that when the system switched from monthly salaries to daily wages, production increased. This implies that higher salaries have a direct impact on workers' performance. When the pay system was changed from incentive pay to salary, the progress of the workers increased significantly in the case of fruit pickers. Managerial performance bonuses have the power to increase worker productivity. When it comes to higher management positions, managers frequently emphasize attracting and keeping qualified workers by switching from piece rate to salary. By offering more incentives, the main goal of this activity is to retain skilled labor (Evans and Lindsay, 1999).

Theoretical Framework

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is the foundation of this research project. Two constructs in Fred Davis' Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) are comparable to the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) constructs (Davis, 1989). It exemplifies how users adopt and work with technology. TAM constructs are perceived usefulness (PU), or how much a person thinks using a certain system would improve their job performance, and perceived ease-of-use (EOU), or how much a person thinks using a certain system would be effortless. While perceived ease of use is equivalent to complexity in TAM, perceived usefulness is equivalent to Rogers' relative advantage in DOI (EOU suggests that using the innovation requires little cognitive effort, whereas complexity implies the opposite).

According to research, the adoption of electronic commerce is significantly influenced by perceptions of perceived usability, usefulness, and benefits, as well as relative advantages. According to the DOI theory, individuals' characteristics, internal organizational structure characteristics, and external organizational characteristics all play a significant role in predicting organizational innovativeness.

Empirical Review

The topic of ICT and sustainable development in Nigeria was covered by Okey-Colbert and Ukandu in 2019. It has been noted that, when used properly, technology brings significant improvement in ways that benefit all stakeholders, including eradicating poverty and enhancing human capacity. The purpose of this study is to ascertain how ICT contributes to sustainable development. The secondary method of data collection was employed in this paper. Numerous academic works were examined. It was determined that ICT can increase international cost

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competition. It takes technology to isolated locations where it would have been expensive to use it before. Therefore, it was suggested that for Nigeria to achieve sustainable development, the country should encourage its people to use ICT to advance innovation and environmentally friendly solutions to persistent problems.

The ICT concept and its favorable effects on Nigerian administration, education, security, and employment were explained by Akwu, Duke, and Victoria in 2021. With recommendations to address obvious challenges, national development is seen to be improved through ICT. The scientific framework for this paper was social change theory. The idea of social change promotes progress and change because no society is static. Technology is viewed as one of the prerequisites for social change to create the most modern forms of existence where excellence is unavoidable. The study inferred that the only way to improve the fortunes of Nigeria's administration, education, security, and employment is through ICT. It is advised that an institutional framework for ICT should exist, with representation in all spheres of the Nigerian economy.

The Nigerian banking sector, which has greatly benefited from international technology innovation, was the subject of Olanrewaju's (2016) investigation into how business performance reacted to the advent of technology. Organizational employee performance and customer responses have been impacted by the introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT). The thesis looked at how employees and customers reacted to technological innovation and how that affected the performance of Nigerian banks. For the study, fifteen (20) large banks were chosen. Two null hypotheses were developed based on sets of questionnaires distributed to selected banks' employees and customers to determine whether there is no noticeable correlation between technological innovation and customer satisfaction as well as between technological innovation and employee performance in Nigerian banks. The first hypothesis was tested with Chi-square, which was based on the 400 questionnaires that were collected, or 88.88% of the 450 questionnaires that were distributed to customers. Results showed that technological innovation had an impact on bank employees' productivity, client satisfaction, and increased profitability. The study makes recommendations for managing technological innovation effectively to improve employee productivity, customer satisfaction, sustainable profit, increased return on investment, increased returns on equity, and foster competition in the Nigerian banking sector.

The impact of information and communication technology on employee performance in an organization was thoroughly examined by Dampana and Agbeyegbe (2017). This essay reviewed some relevant literature and theoretical framework that are relevant to the topic. To accomplish the stated objective, this paper uses a descriptive survey design. The population of this study consists of 50 study organization employees, with a sample size of 34 selected using a straightforward random sampling technique. The data was gathered using the questionnaire

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method. Using descriptive statistical tools like tables and frequencies, the data were analyzed with particular reference to the research questions. The results demonstrate that ICT has improved bank employees' performance by enhancing their skills and that ICT has introduced new techniques across all areas of banks by enhancing banking operations. Based on the findings, the researcher suggested that banks should advance their information technology to increase productivity. They also suggested expanding the use of ICT in the banking industry beyond urban areas and toward rural areas.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study was 874,569 selected individuals in IT business and users in Nsukka zone of Enugu State Nigeria. A sample of 400 was derived from the population and questionnaires were issued to them. Out of the 400 respondents issued questionnaires, 364 respondents returned their questionnaires' and the returned questionnaires were used in the analysis.

Table 1: Email technology enhances employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector

	Frequency	Percent	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid SA	152	41.8	41.8	41.8
A	120	33.0	33.0	74.7
UD	26	7.1	7.1	81.9
D	43	11.8	11.8	93.7
SD	23	6.3	6.3	100.0
Total	364	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 show that 152 or 41.8% of the respondents strongly agree that email technology enhances employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector, 120, or 33.0% Agreed, while 26, or 7.1.3% were undecided, 43 or 11.8% disagreed while 23 or 6.3% respondents strongly agree. It shows that the number of respondents that strongly agreed and strongly agreed has the highest number i.e. 155 and 120 respectively indicating that email technology enhances employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector.

Table 2: Internet technology enhances employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector

	Frequency	Percent	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid SA	55	15.1	15.1	15.1
A	59	16.2	16.2	31.3
UD	68	18.7	18.7	50.0
D	86	23.6	23.6	73.6

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SD	96	26.4	26.4	100.0
Total	364	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 revealed that 55 or 15.1% of respondents were of the view that they strongly agree that Internet technology enhances employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector, 59 or 16.2% of respondents agreed, 68 or 18.7% were undecided 86 or 23.6% disagreed while 98 or 26.4% respondents strongly disagreed with the above assertion, this shows that disagreed and strongly disagreed has the highest number of response implying that Internet technology enhances employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector.

Table 3: E-commerce has a great impact on employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector

	Frequency	Percent	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid SA	147	40.4	40.4	40.4
A	119	32.7	32.7	73.1
UD	32	8.8	8.8	81.9
D	29	8.0	8.0	89.8
SD	37	10.2	10.2	100.0
Total	364	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 shows that 147 or 40.4% of the respondents were unanimous in their opinion that e-commerce has a significant impact on worker productivity in Nigeria's service sector., 119 or 32.7% respondents agreed, 32 or 8.8% of respondent were undecided, 29 or 8.0% disagreed while 37 or 10.2% strongly agreed, this shows that e-commerce has a significant effect on employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector.

Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses posed in this section were examined using Pearson correlations. The test's main goal was to determine the relationship between two variables.

Hypothesis One

Ho: Email technology does not have a great impact on employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector.

Correlations

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		Email technology greatly impacts employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector	Email technology does not have a great impact on employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector
Email technology has a significant effect on employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 364	.934 (**) .000 364
Email technology does not have any significant effect on employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.934 (**) .000 364	1 364

** The significance level for correlation is 0.01 (2-tailed).

In hypothesis one, the researcher sought to examine the effect of email technology on employee job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector. In evaluating this theory, the Pearson correlation tool was used. The outcome indicated that the relationship was at 0.934. This indicates that there is a very strong and positive correlation. Furthermore, the correlation is significant at 0.00, which is less than 0.05. Additionally, this implies that the correlation was significant.

The implication is that employee job effectiveness in Nigeria's service sector is greatly affected by email technology. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Internet technology does not greatly impact employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector.

Correlations

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		Internet technology greatly impacts employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector	Internet technology does not have a great impact on employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector
Internet technology has a significant effect on employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 364	.949(**) 364
Internet technology does not have a significant effect on employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.949(**) 364	1 364

** The significance level for correlation is 0.01 (2-tailed).

In hypothesis two, the researcher sought to find out the effect of Internet technology on employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector. In testing this hypothesis, the Pearson Correlation Tool was utilized. The result showed that the relationship occurred at 0.949. This means that the correlation is positive and very strong. Again, the correlation is significant at 0.00 which is less than 0.05. This also means that the correlation was significant.

It is inferred that Internet technology significantly affects employee turnover in Nigeria's service industry. The alternative hypothesis is therefore accepted.

Hypothesis Three

H₀: E-commerce does not have does not greatly impact employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector.

Correlations

	E-commerce greatly impacts employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector	E-commerce does not have a great impact on employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector

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E-commerce has a significant effect on employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector.	Pearson Correlation	1	.913(**)
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	364	364
E-commerce does not have a significant effect on employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector.	Pearson Correlation	.913(**)	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	364	364

** The significance level for correlation is 0.01 (2-tailed).

Hypothesis three sought to evaluate the effect of e-commerce on employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector. The Pearson correlation tool was used to test this theory. The outcome demonstrated that the relationship was at 0.913. This indicates a strong and positive correlation. Correlation is also significant at 0.00, which is less than 0.05 which also means the correlation was significant.

The outcome is that e-commerce greatly impacts employee job productivity in the Nigerian service sector. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The four research hypotheses used to generate the results here serves as the framework for the discussion of the findings of this study. The outcome of hypothesis one demonstrates that the use of email technology has a significant impact on how effectively employees perform their jobs in the Nigerian service sector. According to a study by Okey-Colbert and Ukandu in 2019, Information Communications Technology can increase the international cost competitiveness of a firm. ICT assists in bringing technology to isolated locations where conventional technology would have been expensive. Thus, it was advised that if Nigeria wants to advance innovation and environmentally friendly solutions to persistent problems, it must encourage its citizens to use ICT.

According to the findings of hypothesis number two, the Nigerian service sector's employee turnover is significantly impacted by Internet technology. This finding is consistent with those made by Akwu, Duke, and Victoria (2021) regarding ICT and its favorable effects on Nigerian education, business, and employment. The research demonstrates that the only way to transform Nigeria's businesses, employment, and education positively is through ICT. It is advised that the Nigerian economy's various sectors adopt an institutional framework for information and communications technology (ICT).

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The findings of hypothesis three show that e-commerce has an important impact on worker's job productivity in the Nigerian service industry, which supports Olanrewaju's (2016) study about how information technology impacts organizational performance in the Nigerian banking sector, which recorded big improvements in banking services due to the advent of technology. This demonstrated how technological innovation affected bank employee productivity, client satisfaction, and increased bank profitability. To improve employee productivity, customer satisfaction, sustainable profit, increased return on investment, increased returns on equity, and foster competition in the Nigerian banking sector, the study advises effective management of technological innovation.

Summary of Findings

The study's findings on how digitalization affects worker performance in the service sector include the following.

1. E-mail technology has an important impact on an employee's job effectiveness in the Nigerian service sector.
2. It was also observed that internet technology has a big impact on employee turnover in the Nigerian service sector.
3. The study further shows that E-commerce has a big impact on the job of the employee in the Nigerian service sector.

Conclusion

According to the study's findings, the performance of Nigerian financial service firms has been significantly impacted by digitalization. Even though the connection is small, it is very important and suggests that financial service providers in Nigeria should put more emphasis on digitizing banking services to meet consumer demands. If the procedures for digitizing banking services are perfected, the issue of customers still visiting banking halls and waiting in lengthy lines to resolve minor issues will be a thing of the past. Digitalizing banking services aims to shorten wait times, remove bottlenecks, and speed up transactions. Digitalization should have a larger, more meaningfully favorable relationship with the performance of financial service firms in Nigeria, *ceteris paribus*, if this is properly and correctly implemented.

Finally, the study's findings suggest that product innovation influences how well financial services companies perform in Nigeria. Even though the results showed a marginally positive relationship between product innovation and the performance of financial service firms, the management of Nigerian financial service firms can spend more time improving their various products and services. This is not to say that there aren't enough banking products and services; rather, the ones that are currently available should be improved to meet customer needs and demands and prevent customers from having to frequently visit financial service providers and wait in line for assistance.

Recommendations

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1. Organizations should ensure that employees receive strategic human resource management before new technology is introduced to maximize the return on their investment, which considers improving workers' skills through training, apprenticeships, and development.
2. Workers should have better working conditions and productivity gains. Their pay benefits should increase in line with the industry's rising performance gains.
3. Labour unions need to make sure that the effects of technological change on their members' jobs are considered.
4. Technology in the service sector needs to be constantly evaluated, and instead of reacting to change, they should be anticipating it. For their members who will be impacted by technology change or who are likely to be impacted by it, they should arrange for training and retraining.

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REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, M.S. & Shehu, U.R. & Usman, M.B. (2019) "Impact of Information Communication Technology on Organizational Productivity in the Nigeria Banking Industry: Empirical Evidence," *Noble International Journal of Business and Management Research*, Noble Academic Publisher, vol. 3(1), 1-9,
- Abbasi T. & Weigand H. (2017) The Impact of Digital Financial Services on Firm's Performance: A Literature Review. Doi: Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1705.10294.pdf> on 18/02/2023
- Adenekan, T.E. & Jimoh, T.A. (2021) Technological Innovation, Digital Competence and Job Performance of Secretaries in Public Tertiary Institutions in Ogun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology* 5 (12) 5-12
- Agboola, M.G., et al (2019) Effect of Digitalization on the Performance of Commercial Banks in Nigeria. *IOP Conference. Series: Earth Environ. Sci.* 331 012014. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/331/1/012014>
- Akwu, A.U., Duke, A.E., & Inuaesiet, V.U. (2021) Impact of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on the Development of Nigeria: A Critical Overview. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research* 7, (1) 56-78
- Al-Azzawi, A.K.M. & Altmimi, L.A. (2015) Effect of Information and Communication Technology Investment on the Profitability of the Jordanian Commercial Banks. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(28): 166-73.
- Okey-Colbert, E.U. & Ukandu, C.N. (2019) ICT and Sustainable Development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Sustainable Development* 6, (1). 31-44.
- Oladejo M.O. & Y. Oluwaseun (2014) An Influential Analysis of the Impact of Information Technology (IT) on Co-operative Services in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*. 2, (3), 11-24,
- Olanrewaju, B.E. (2016) Effects of Information Technology on Organisational Performance in Nigerian Banking Industries. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7 (3) 52-64
- Olaoye, F.O., Olaofe-Obasesin, M.O. & Akanni, W. (2019) Impact of Information Technology on Corporate Organizations Performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Engineering Applied Sciences and Technology*, 4, (8), 84-88

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IMPACT OF DIGITALIZATION ON EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE

- Olise, M.C., Anigbogu, T.U., Edoko, T.D. & Okoli, M.I. (2014) Determinants of ICT adoption for Improved SME's performance in Anambra State, Nigeria. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 4(7): 163-76
- Oni, F.J. & Koko, M.N. (2020) Influence of Information and Communication Technology Skills on Office Managers' Performance in Private Industries in Port Harcourt Metropolis. *International Journal of Innovative Information Systems & Technology Research* 8(4):22-31
- Onu, C. A., Ibrahim, O.O. & Segun, F.K. (2015) Effect of Information Technology Investment on Organizational Productivity and Growth of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Developing Countries. *Business and Economics Journal*, 6(3): 1.
- Penalba, U. (2015) Promoting Learning Transfer Developing SME Marketing Knowledge in Dnipropetrovsk Oblast, Ukraine. *Journal of Quality Management and Business Excellence*, 20(4): 423-43.
- Stair, R.M. & Reynolds, G.W. (2010) *Principios de Sistemas de Información: Enfoque administrativo*. Cengage Learning Publishers
- Tesfaye H. (2014) The Impact of Information System (IS) on Organizational Performance: With Special Reference to Ethio-Telecom Southern Region, Hawassa. *European Journal of Business and Management* 6 (37) 331-338

COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND IT'S IMPACT ON ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Research Purpose: *This paper was to examine Covid-19 and it's impact on entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. The pandemic is more complex. It created immense social and economic problems at all levels, including social phobia, unemployment, supply chain disruption, stock market crashes, economic lockdown, and de-globalization. However, the major objectives among others were to evaluate the effects of entrepreneurship and innovation during COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria. The following review of literature was revealed; COVID-19 spill-over to the Nigerian economy, and impact on the world economy.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *Hence, the study was hinged on classical theory. The design of this research was survey. Both primary and secondary data were used in this study. The population of this study was 70 senior and management staff of the three event companies selected in Rivers State for this study and they were Vimos Events, SBE Events, and Sunshine Event Managers. The sample size from a population of 70 is 60 respondents at 95% confidence level. Chi-square statistic was used to analyse data in this study. The test of the first hypothesis on COVID-19 pandemic on entrepreneurship development in Nigeria offered a gainful insight on the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on entrepreneurship development.*

Findings: *Entrepreneurs should search with a purpose for the sources of innovation, the changes and their symptoms that point-out opportunities for successful innovation during the pandemic.*

Implication: *The study concluded that; the health pandemic caused by COVID-19 has dramatically changed society and altered current entrepreneurial practices.*

Originality/Value Added: *The recommendations among others were that; more loans should be given to entrepreneurs to help cushion the effects of COVID-19 on business organisations.*

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic, Small and medium enterprises, Entrepreneurship, development

Introduction

The coronavirus started spreading from Wuhan, Hubei Province, China. People living in Wuhan were having some contact with large seafood and in a live market where animals were sold, which implies that the mode of contracting coronavirus was from animal to human being. The virus named SARS-CoV-2 and the disease it causes has been named coronavirus disease 2019 (abbreviated COVID-19). The number one known patient of Coronavirus started experiencing symptoms in Wuhan, China on 1st December, 2019. From that time, there have been 800,000 reported cases around the world, that on 11th March 2020, World Health Organization -WHO (2020) declared COVID-19 pandemic. As a response to contain coronavirus spread and save lives, governments in affected countries imposed desperate measures of social distancing, restrictions on travelling, people gatherings and widespread lockdown. Many aspects of public and private life had to be moved to social media (Liguori & Winkler, 2020). However, entrepreneurs were no exception. They had to start moving their business activities to social media. Hence, not everything was solved conveniently on social media. Coronavirus has significantly influenced the entrepreneurial engagement of self-employed individuals. Some entrepreneurs had to windup their businesses for the main time because of governmental measures; others had to set up precautions and to run their activities in minimised extent. They also needed to find innovative solutions in all aspects of their entrepreneurial endeavour as the consequences of the pandemic prolong. It was after a long time before the entrepreneurs got oriented in the new situation, and governments started assisting them out with particular policy-actions targeting to pass information, advisory and financial assistance (Kuckertz et al., 2020; Turner & Akinremi, 2020). Therefore, this special issue captures the effects of COVID-19 on entrepreneurship development at different kinds of

levels in Nigeria, accumulating knowledge of best individual and policy-initiated practices helping entrepreneurs and self-employed persons to overcome the crisis.

COVID-19 is more complex. It created immense social and economic problems at all levels, including social phobia, unemployment, supply chain disruption, stock market crashes, economic lockdown, and de-globalization. Because of the uniqueness of the COVID-19 crisis, previous research was not sufficient to understand it.

Recent studies have shown that entrepreneurship is a critical component of local economic development with regard to the harmonization of standard of living in Nigeria (OECD, 2003). Hence, fostering entrepreneurship via promotional schemes for small-and medium-sized enterprises and start-ups is now an important objective for policy makers and governments around the world. A major impediment that affects the foundation, survival and growth of a business is the problem of acquiring sufficient financial resources, which arise due to supply-side and/or demand-side behaviour.

The existence of informational asymmetries, agency costs and associated risk between SMEs and providers of finance is a key issue for the occurrence of market imperfections and policy interventions during the COVID-19 era.

The availability of sufficient and appropriate financial resources is a major prerequisite for the foundation and long-term sustainability of new ventures (Brettel, 2003).

The specific objectives of this study are to evaluate the effects of entrepreneurship and innovation in times of COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria; examine the effects of government support targeting high-growth and start-ups in Nigeria and assess the effects of finding opportunities and COVID-19 pandemic crisis in Nigeria. The following research hypotheses were formulated in a null form;

H0₁ there is no entrepreneurship and innovation in times of COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria

H0₂ there is no government support targeting high-growth start-ups in Nigeria

H0₃ there are no opportunities during the crisis in Nigeria

Review of related Literature

COVID-19 Spillover to the Nigerian Economy

The direct effect: the COVID-19 pandemic spilt into Nigeria in different ways. One, the COVID-19 pandemic affected borrowers' capacity to service their loans, which produced non-performing loans (NPLs) that depressed banks' earnings and eventually impaired banks' soundness and stability. However, banks were unwilling to give additional loans to borrowers as much more borrowers struggled to repay the loans granted to them during the COVID-19 outbreak.

Impact on the Global Economy

The world economy was affected by the pandemic in two ways. firstly, the transmission of the virus enabled social distancing that led to the shutdown of markets, organisations' offices, businesses and events. Secondly, the rate at which the pandemic were transmitting and reached uncertainty about how porous the situation was, led to flight to safety in consumption and investment among consumers and investors (Ozili &

Arun, 2020). There was a consensus among top economists that the coronavirus would plunge the world into a recession.

Classical Theory

This paper was anchored on classical theory. The classical theory points out the virtues of free trade, specialisation because of Britain's industrial revolution that occurred in the mid 1700 and continued until the 1830s. The classical movement mark out the role of the entrepreneur in the context of production and distribution of goods in a competitive market environment (Say, 1803). Classical theorists emphasized on three modes of production which are land, capital, and labour. There have been various disagreements to the classical theory. These theorists were unable to examine the sudden changes prompted by entrepreneurs of the industrial age (Murphy, Liao, & Welsch, 2006).

Empirical Review

Adams-Prassl, Boneva, Golin, & Rauh, (2020) analyse the inequality in job/income losses based on the type of job and individual characteristic for the US and UK. The authors find that employees who can perform none of their tasks from home are more to lose their job. The study, however, found that younger individuals and people without a tertiary education were more importantly to experience drops in their income.

Yasenov (2020) finds that employees with lesser levels of education, younger adults, and immigrants are concerned in occupations that are less to be done from home. Similarly, Alstadsæter, Bratsberg, Eielsen, Kopczuk, Markussen, Raaum, & Røed, (2020) find that, in Norway, the pandemic shock has a heavy socio-economic gradient, as it has disproportionately affected the financially vulnerable population, including parents with younger children.

Methodology

Research Design

According to Nachmias and Nachmias (1995), a research design is the master plan that addresses the problems of scientific inquiry. A research design is the blue print, structure and strategy that is concentrated on the investigation to get answers to research problems and questions. It tries to ensure that the required data/information is collected economically and accurately. The research being a survey research design would allow for collecting data that will help to confirm the authenticity of the hypotheses in that the respondents can answer or respond to the questions at their desired time a two section questionnaire firstly, bio-data and secondly questions on the topic under investigation, respectively will be carefully designed.

Sources of Data

Primary and secondary data were used in this study. The main instruments used in the collection of the primary data were the questionnaire administered to the respondents. Secondary data were obtained from the works of other researchers on this study.

Population of Study

Research population is the aggregate number of persons, objective or phenomena from which relevant data of the study were collected. It refers to all conceivable elements subject or observation relating to the research work (Banji, 2007).

The population of this study is 70 senior and management staff of the three event companies selected in Rivers State for this study and they are Vimos Events, SBE Events, and Sunshine Event Managers. The three companies chosen and the respondents were through simple random sampling technique.

Determination of Sample Size

The sample size was determined using Yaro Yamane formula given as

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where, n = Sample size sought
 e = Level of significance = 0.05 or 5%

N = Population size = 70

$$n = \frac{70}{1 + 70(0.05)^2}$$

$$= \frac{70}{1.25}$$

$$= 56$$

= 60 respondents

Applying this formula, the sample size from a population of 70 is 60 respondents at 95% confidence level.

Validity of the Instrument

Validity is the extent to which an instrument measures what is meant to be measured. To ensure face validity of this instrument, copies of the instrument were given to experts and other colleagues for vetting before it was administered to the respondents. Contributions from these people were duly incorporated into the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

To get the reliability of the instrument, ten copies of the questionnaire were administered to employees of the companies under study, who completed the same and gave it back to the researcher. After one week interval, the same employees were presented with the same questionnaire for completion. The aim was to examine the consistency and trustworthiness of employees in completing the questionnaire.

When the two sets of responses were compared, it was evidenced that their responses were similar as the respondents, maintained similar stand points in both cases.

Data Analysis Techniques

Chi-square statistic was used to analyse data in this study. This statistical test is used to test how observed frequencies fit into the expected frequencies. It enables us to ascertain if there is a relationship between variables under investigation by assessing their marginal values depending on their level of dependence or independence. The formula for chi-square is as follows:

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(f_o - f_e)^2}{f_e}$$

f_e

Where, X^2 = Chi-square

f_o = Observed frequency

f_e = Expected frequency

Testing the Hypotheses

In testing the hypotheses, the following steps were adopted:

- i. The statement of the hypothesis in the null and alternative.
- ii. Identification of the test statistic.
- iii. The formulation of the decision rule.
- iv. Computation of the test statistic.
- v. Interpretation of the test result.

Table 1: Hypothesis One

H₀: there is no entrepreneurship and innovation in times of COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria

H₁: there is entrepreneurship and innovation in times of COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria

Table 1 Computation of chi-square (X^2) of response frequencies between entrepreneurship and innovation in times of COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria

Responses	Observed Frequency (f_o)	Expected Frequency (f_e)	$f_o - f_e$	$(f_o - f_e)^2$
Strongly agree	30	12	18	27
Agree	25	12	13	14.08
Undecided	2	12	-10	8.33
Strongly disagree	1	12	-11	10.08
Disagree	2	12	-10	8.33
Total	60	60	-	67.82

Computed $X^2 = 67.82$ **Source:** Research Data, 2021

Also, to determine the decision rule, the degree of freedom (df) is applied.

Also, to determine the decision rule, the degree of freedom (df) is applied.

$$df = (r - 1) (c - 1)$$

Where; df = degree of freedom

r = number of rows

c = number of columns

$$\text{Degree of freedom} = (r - 1) (c - 1)$$

$$= (2 - 1) (5 - 1) = 1 \times 4$$

$$df = 4$$

Significance level = 5%

The critical value of X_2 at $df = 4 = 9.49$

Computed $X_2 = 67.82$

Decision Rule

Since the computed value of $X_2 = 67.82$ is greater than the critical value of 9.49, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative accepted. Thus, there is entrepreneurship and innovation in times of COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria.

Table 2: Hypothesis Two

H₀: there is no government support targeting high-growth start-ups in Nigeria

H₁: there is government support targeting high-growth start-ups in Nigeria

Table 2 Computation of chi-square (X^2) of response frequencies between government support targeting high-growth and start-ups in Nigeria

Responses	Observed Frequency (fo)	Expected Frequency (fe)	fo - fe	(fo - fe) ² fe
Strongly agree	28	12	16	21.33
Agree	20	12	8	5.33
Undecided	6	12	-6	3
Strongly disagree	4	12	-8	5.33
Disagree	2	12	-10	8.33
Total	60	60	-	43.32

Computed $\chi^2 = 43.32$ Source: Research Data, 2021

Also, to determine the decision rule, the degree of freedom (df) is applied.

$$df = (r-1) (c-1)$$

Where; df = degree of freedom

r = number of rows

c = number of columns

$$\text{Degree of freedom} = (r-1) (c-1)$$

$$= (2 - 1) (5 - 1) = 1 \times 4$$

$$df = 4$$

Significance level = 5%

The critical value of X_2 at $df = 4 = 9.49$

Computed $\Sigma X_2 = 43.32$

Decision Rule

Since the computed values of $X_2 = 43.32$ is greater than the critical value of 9.49, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative accepted. Thus, there is government support targeting high-growth start-ups in Nigeria

Table 3: Hypothesis Three

H₀: there are no opportunities during the crisis in Nigeria

H₁: there are opportunities during the crisis in Nigeria

Table 3 Computation of chi-square (X^2) of response frequencies between opportunities and COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria

Responses	Observed Frequency (fo)	Expected Frequency (fe)	fo - fe	(fo - fe) ² fe
Strongly agree	32	12	20	33.33
Agree	23	12	11	10.08
Undecided	2	12	-10	8.33
Strongly disagree	1	12	-11	10.08
Disagree	2	12	-10	8.33
Total	60	60	-	70.15

Computed $\chi^2 = 70.15$ Source: Research Data, 2021

Also, to determine the decision rule, the degree of freedom (df) is applied.

$$df = (r-1) (c-1)$$

Where; df = degree of freedom

r = number of rows

c = number of columns

$$\text{Degree of freedom} = (r-1) (c-1)$$

$$= (2 - 1) (5 - 1) = 1 \times 4$$

$$df = 4$$

Significance level = 5%

The critical value of X_2 at df 4 = 9.49

Computed $\Sigma X_2 = 70.15$

Decision Rule

Since the computed values of $X_2 = 70.15$ is greater than the critical value of 9.49, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative accepted. Thus, there are opportunities during the crisis in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The test of the first hypothesis on COVID-19 pandemic on entrepreneurship development in Nigeria offers a gainful insight on the effects of COVID-19 on entrepreneurship development.

In table 1, there is entrepreneurship and innovation in times of COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria. Innovation is the major tool of entrepreneurs, the means by which they exploit change as an opportunity for a different business. Entrepreneurs should search with a purpose for the sources of innovation, the changes and their symptoms that point-out opportunities for successful innovation during the pandemic.

And in table 2, there is government support targeting high-growth and start-ups in Nigeria. However, entrepreneurship, the knowledge economy and high-growth start-ups have been seen as vehicles for a new and fundamentally different direction for the Nigerian economy.

Also, table 3, there are opportunities during COVID-19 crisis in Nigeria. Some new-born entrepreneurs and start-ups have been more opportunistic during the pandemic, leading their businesses with the help of repurposing and redirecting already knowledge, skills, people and networks to new needs that have come to stay.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The health pandemic caused by COVID-19 has dramatically changed society and altered current entrepreneurial practices. This means that new practices are needed reliant on entrepreneurial thinking to succeed in the global marketplace. It was recommended that more loans should be given to entrepreneurs to help cushion the effects of COVID-19 on business organizations; the partial lockdown of states should be reviewed from time to time, while markets and other SMEs should be allowed to open twice weekly at least with a controlled influx of consumers. All precautionary measures put in place by government and relevant health bodies aimed at tackling COVID-19 should be obeyed and sustained and the country should not be subjected to total lockdown for so long. A partial lockdown should be adopted in order not to worsen the entrepreneurship situation.

References

- Aldairany, S., Omar, R., & Quoquab, F. (2018), Systematic review: entrepreneurship in conflict and post conflict, *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 10, 2, 361-383.
- Alstadsæter, A., Bratsberg, B., Eielsen, G., Kopczuk, W., Markussen, S., Raaum, O., & Røed, K. (2020). The First Weeks of the COVID-19 Crisis: Who got hit? When and why? Evidence from Norway(Working, 27131; Working Paper Series). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w27131>.
- Adams-Prassl, A., Boneva, T., Golin, M., & Rauh, C. (2020). Inequality in the impact of the COVID-19 shock: Evidence From Real Time Surveys. <https://www.inet.econ.cam.ac.uk/working-paper-pdfs/wp2018.pdf>.
- ADB (2020). Asian development outlook: What drives innovation in Asia? Special topic: The impact of the COVID-19 outbreak-An update, Manila, Philippines. Asian Development Bank.

- Brettel, M. (2003). Business angels in Germany: a research note, *Venture Capital*, 5, 3, Taylor and Francis, 251-268.
- Chell, E. (2013). Review of skill and the entrepreneurial process. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 19, 1, 6-31.
- Liguori, E., & Winkler, C. (2020). From Offline to Online: Challenges and opportunities for entrepreneurship education following the COVID-19 Pandemic, *Entrepreneurship Education and Pedagogy*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515127420916738>.
- Murphy, J.P, Liao, J & Welsch, P.H. (2006). A Conceptual history of entrepreneurial thought. *Journal of Management History*. 12, 9-24.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2003), *Entrepreneurship and local economic development: Programme and policy recommendations*, Paris, OECD.
- Stephan, U. (2018). Entrepreneurs' mental health and well-being: A review and research agenda. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 32(3), 290-322.
- Say, J.B. (1803). *Traité D'économie Politique, ou simple exposition de la manière dont se forment, se distribuent, et se composent les richesses*, Paris. A.A. Renouard.
- Turner, J., & Akinremi, T. (2020), The business effects of pandemics – A rapid literature review, *enterprise research centre*, <https://www.enterpriseresearch.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/ERC-Insight-The-business-effects-of-pandemics-%E2%80%93-a-rapid-literature-review-Final.pdf>.
- UNDP, (2020a) COVID-19: Looming crisis in developing countries threatens to devastate economies and ramp up inequality, United Nations Development Programme, https://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/newscentre/news/2020/COVID19_Crisis_in_developing_countries_threatens_devastate_economies.html.
- Wach, D., Stephan, U., & Gorgievski, M. (2016). More than money: Developing an integrative multi-factorial measure of entrepreneurial success, *International Small Business Journal*, 34, 8, 1098-1121.
- World Health Organization - WHO (2020), WHO Timeline-COVID-19, <https://www.who.int/news-room/detail/27-04-2020-who-timeline---covid-19>.
- Yasenov, V. I. (2020). Who Can Work from Home?(SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 3590895). Social Science Research Network. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3590895>
- Word Economic, (2020) World economic prospects monthly. *Economic Outlook*, 44 (S2), 1-33.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT: A PANACEA TO JOB CREATION FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA (A STUDY OF SELECTED COMMUNITIES IN ANINRI L.G.A OF ENUGU STATE)

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Abstract

Research Purpose: Globally the concept of entrepreneurship has become so important because it accelerates economic growth and development in both developed and developing countries. The broad objective is to examine entrepreneurship development a panacea to job creation for sustainable economic development in Nigeria, while this specific objective was developed to: ascertain the extent to which skill acquisition can increase job generation in Aninri L.G.A.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Survey research design was used for the study. Population of the study was 135 entrepreneurs, and the entire population was used. Chi-square statistic was used to test the hypothesis. Researchers determined that skills acquisition had a significant and positive effect on the employment generation of Aninri L.G.A with the Cal value 17.001 > Cri value 15.51.

Findings: Researchers concluded that since skills acquisition helped to increase employment generation that it should be encouraged and technical education introduced in all levels of our educational system in Nigeria, as it will tailor the minds of young people to be entrepreneurial early in life.

Originality/Value Added: The researchers recommended that government at all levels in Nigeria should create an enabling environment in which entrepreneurship development should thrive and support all employable adults to acquire skills.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship Development, Job Creation, Sustainable Economic Development

Introduction

Ono, (2017), posits that globally that entrepreneurship development has become an important tool for accelerating economic growth and development. It has helped reduce unemployment and transform most economies in the world through employment creation. Ayozie and Farayola, (2005), opine that most Asian countries like China, India, Malaysia, Indonesia and many other countries had tremendous achievements in the 1990s through entrepreneurial activities. Ebiringa, (2012), opines that countries with a high level of entrepreneurial initiatives have greatly experienced reduction in unemployment rates as well as register sustainability in standard of living. He submitted that a considerable agreement, therefore, supports the need to promote entrepreneurship as a strategy for economic transformation. The level of economic development experienced by societies has significantly depended on the depth of entrepreneurship development that is present within that society. Williams and Michael, (2012), corroborated the views of Ebiriga, that entrepreneurs historically have altered the course of economic history in the world. Ebiringa, (2011), was of the same view that the focus of entrepreneurship is wealth creation and improved the welfare of the public. Ebiriga believed that it leads to an upward change whereby continuous economic growth affected the real per capita income of a country. He thus stressed that entrepreneurship development is an indispensable tool for economic transformation.

Ariyo, 2005; Oyelola et al, (2013), posit that entrepreneurship has been beneficial to Nigerians, because the private sector comprising entrepreneurship programmes has been providing different employment opportunities for greater than 50 percent of the country's population and providing greater than 50 percent of the industrial outputs. Onugu, (2005),

submits that many countries have strengthened and transformed their entrepreneurship sub-sector to such blossoming industry that has reduced significantly their unemployment and poverty level because of the enormous contributions of the sub-sector to the economic growth and development their country.

Nigeria has numerous untapped human and other natural resources, which if harnessed will boost economic development. Agbeze, (2012), argues that Nigerians have made their marks in different fields such as science, technology, academics, business and entertainment. Thus, that entrepreneurship activities and innovative ingenuity in Nigeria have developed enterprises in the areas of agricultural/agro-allied activities, restaurants, and fast food vending. He was of the view that in the area of solid minerals, there are quarrying, germs stone cutting/polishing and crushing engineering that Nigerians are doing exploits here too. He states that in power and transport, there are power generations, Haulage business (cargo and passengers). He was of the view that Nigerians are not excluded in the area of information and telecom business, which also connotes manufacturing and repairs of GSM accessories and the printing and selling of Recharge cards. Summarily,

Agbaeze, (2012), states that entrepreneurship involvement of Nigerians spans to the following areas hospitality and tourism business sector, oil and gas business, environmental and waste management business, financial bankingservices, insurance and stock trading, engineering and fabrication work, building and construction, and a lot of other sectors they explore.

Sagagi, (2010), opines that Nigerian youths are said to be poverty stricken and that there is a high rate of unemployment as a result of low entrepreneurial activities.

Statement of the Problem

Entrepreneurship development helps global economies grow and develop. It helps to reduce unemployment among the youths thereby reducing social vices in society. In Nigeria it helps to achieve the policy thrust of government on employment generation, hence the role of government in instituting programmes/policies to support entrepreneurship development.

Unemployment leads to crime/criminality that affects the security of the country. Nigeria lately has been experiencing a high rate of insecurity which ranges from boko haram activities, banditry, cultish, kidnapping, assassinations, herders and activities of unknown gunmen; these social vices emerged because of unemployment because our youths are not gainfully engaged in any entrepreneurial activities. The emergency of these social vice groups are indications that Nigerian youths are not gainfully engaged. It is imperative that when people are gainfully employment the issue of social vices is eroded and insecurity reduced. Employment is largely achievable through entrepreneurship development.

Attention is not given to entrepreneurship development even though it is a tool for reduction of unemployment and social vices. Government programmes and policies are not supporting entrepreneurship development through empowering our youths and providing financial support as a start off capital. These are premises on which this research work is anchored on.

Objective of the Study

The major objective of the study is to examine the role of Entrepreneurship Development as A Panacea to Job Creation for Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria. This specific objective includes to: ascertain the extent to which skills acquisition has increased employment generation in Aninri L. G. A.

Research Question:

To what extent does skills acquisition increase employment in Aninri L. G. A?

Research Hypothesis:

Skills acquisition have significant and effect on the employment generation of Aninri L. G. A

Review of related literature

Conceptual Review

Entrepreneurship

Igbo, (2006) posits that entrepreneurship has been defined by different authors to mean different things since the middle age. The entrepreneur is as an actor, innovator or a developer of technology. Inegbehebor (1987), in Akanwa and Akpanabia (2012), submitted that entrepreneurship is the willingness and ability of an individual to seek out investment opportunities, establish and run an enterprise successfully. Esomomu (1998), opines that entrepreneurship is the use of human intellect as shown in a creative and innovative performance. The National Directorate of Employment (NDE, 1989), in Onyebueke and Ochnongo (2002), believed that entrepreneurship is an art that involves recognising a business opportunity, mobilising resources and exploits that opportunity. Tijani-Alawiye, (2004), posits that entrepreneurship is a method for increasing the number of small and medium-sized enterprises in the country through creating and promoting many capable entrepreneurs that successfully achieve socio-economic development goals. He states that it is also the process of gathering creative and innovative ideas and applying managerial skills to achieve their set objective. Shepherd and Douglas, (1997) in Akanwa and Akpanabia, (2012), observed that entrepreneurship development is the ability to envision and chart a course for a new business venture by combining information from the functional disciplines and from the external environment that faces a new business venture. Adejumo, (2000), views entrepreneurship development as being capable of impacting positively on the economy of a nation and the quality of life of the people.

The researchers on other hand submitted that entrepreneurship development is the use of all factors of production to create business ventures that will satisfy the needs of the public at a profit to the owner. They stated that it helps to achieve the economic thrust of government in the area of employment generation and encourages the use of local raw materials.

Development: Development can simply be said to imply change or growth in a people's lifestyle. Itari, (1995), states that development means a change or an increase in the structural facilities of a people, community or society. However, some scholars believed that development is the ability of the people to solve their problems with their own wisdom, knowledge, experience and resources to have quality life. Onunwa, (2007), argues that development means the ability of society to achieve quick and steady rise in output of all gainful economic ventures. It was also seen as a means the capacity of a national economy generates and sustains an annual increase in its gross national production. The emphasis was on how society can increase the output in its tangible form, despite, the achievement at this level of growth as set by the United Nations, levels of living of the masses of people remained in the most cases unchanged. Soubbotina et al, (2014), was of the view that there were limitations in the earlier submissions of United Nations; there was a paradigm shift from "economic growth" to "human development" which is measured by life expectancy, adult literacy, access to all levels of education, as well as peoples' average income, which is a necessary condition of their freedom of choice. This idea of development was to encompass all aspects of individual's well-being from health life to their economic and political freedom. The Human Development Report of 1996, published by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) states that "human development is the end while economic growth is a means" to an end.

Sustainable Development:

The Brundtland Report defined sustainable Development as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generation to meet their own Needs". The organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2001) as quoted by Ahenkan and Osei-Kojo (2014), states that sustainable development is the

development path along which maximisation of human well-being for today's generation does not lead to the decline in the well-being of the future generation. Ahenkan and Oseikojo, (2014), posit that the definitions suggest that sustainable development considers the needs of the future and current generations, and it is rooted in the pursuit of the well-being and welfare of the people. They reiterated that sustainable development is concerned with the creation and sustenance of the conditions for current and future generations of humans to live well on this planet. Sims and Falkenberg, (2013), argued that right from the on start that a multi-prong approach to the idea of sustainable society went beyond concerns for only the destruction of the national environment to include the concern for meeting the essential needs of all people and those needs are met tenable within the consideration of the needs of future generations.

Entrepreneurship and Employment Creation

Basil, (2005), posits that entrepreneurship provides employment opportunities in a country by engaging the youths, and the vulnerable groups, thereby helping to reduce social vices. That entrepreneurship improves rural livelihoods not just by putting food on the table, but it also helps individuals and families to increase their income and improve their well-being.

Thomson, (2002), opines that entrepreneurship development helps youths; women and other vulnerable groups own businesses and generate more income to support their households and improve their standard of life. He emphasised that this income helps the entrepreneur start and grow his business, which will in turn help him to offer employment to others in their community.

Chu, Kara, Benzing (2010); Nwaka (2005); Oyelola Ajiboshin, Raimi, Raheem and Igwe (2013), submitted that between 45 and 60 percent of the urban labour force engage in small private enterprises that contributed greatly to the reduction of unemployment in Nigeria. Job creation/generation both for the entrepreneurs and employees can be a means for reducing unemployment in the country, as those with entrepreneurial abilities are afforded the opportunity to create their own businesses and make adequate use of their acquired skills and training.

Unemployment in Nigeria

Akwara et al, (2013), believed that unemployment and poverty remained key developmental challenges in Nigeria over a long time now. Udu and Agu (2005), posit that unemployment is "a situation in which persons capable and willing to work are unable to find suitable paid employment". The International Labour Organisation (ILO) (2007), submitted that unemployed workers are those who are currently not working, but are willing and able to work for pay, though currently available to work and have actively searched for work. Hornby, (2010) defines unemployment as "the facts of many people not having a job; the number of people without a job; the state of not having a job". Udu and Agu, (2005), opine that Nigeria does not have credible data on the rate of unemployment, because no institution has been able to produce accurate figures showing the current rate of unemployment in Nigeria. They reiterated that there is great need for entrepreneurship development in Nigeria today, more than ever before as the rate of unemployment and its effect on both the people and nation is worrisome, hence the need for small and medium scale enterprises. Chukwubuikem, (2008) and Salami, (2011) argue that, despite the abundant human and natural resources that Nigeria is still one of the poorest countries in the world and has one of the highest rates of youth unemployment in sub-Saharan Africa. Adebayo (1999), Alanana (2003), Echebiri (2005), Ayinde (2008), Morphy (2008 and Awogbenle and Iwuamadi (2010) in their study of unemployment in Nigeria, identified some leading causes of youth unemployment in Nigeria; to include the rapidly growing urban labour force arising from rural urban migration, lack of infrastructural facilities that makes the rural life unattractive as the youths move to the urban areas with the believe of getting lucrative and productive employment in the industries and to enjoy social amenities in the cities. This implies that the rural areas are neglected in the provision of social amenities thereby lack economic opportunities. Another factor is the rapid population growth. Nigeria National Bureau of

Statistics of 2012 states that the total population of Nigeria was around 166.2 million people, and projections for the future indicate that the population be greater than 180 million by 2020, given the annual growth rate of 3.2 percent (National Population Commission and ICF Macro, 2009). It shows that Nigeria is one of the most populous nations in Africa and high population growth has resulted in the rapid growth of the labour force, which has exceeded the supply of jobs.

Okafor, (2011), opines that corruption which has pervaded the entire social structure of Nigeria, has raided the country of developing economically, such that funds meant for projects had been misappropriated, diverted, or embezzled or stashed away in foreign banks. Adeniyi, (2013), states that statistics had shown that with the current drive, on the average that the labour force in Nigeria would be around 65.7 million a year between 2011 and 2020, and will be about 78.2 million a year between 2021 and 2030, all else being equal. He thought that this projection would be since it will take at least 20 years before any policy aimed at reducing population can be effective in Nigeria. Adeniyi, (2013), explains that in Nigeria with this trend that unemployment would be on the average, 55.8 million a year between 2011 and 2020 and 65.7 million a year between 2021 and 2030. He emphasised that this projection will cause unemployment in Nigeria to be around 9.9 million (15.07% rate) and 12.45 million (15.93% rate) on average between 2011 and 2020, and 2021 to 2030, respectively

Empirical Review

Previous studies on entrepreneurship development among scholars presented their varied views and findings.

Taiwo (2014) did a work on an empirical research on the impact of entrepreneurship development on job creation in Nigeria. He found that in any giving economy, entrepreneurship development has always given birth to job creation which enables people to do something that will better their lives and the country at large. He evaluated the relationship between job creation and entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. It was clear from his observation that job creation or employment opportunities in an economy can be traceable to entrepreneurship training and development.

Anyadike, Emeh and Ukah (2012), conducted a study on Nigeria's growing unemployment situation and how it increasingly dwindles the potentials of the country, especially following official figures from the Bureau of statistics that puts the figure at about 40 million Nigerian youths captured in World Bank statistics in 2009 are unemployed. Having utilised the secondary data. The authors concluded that government should make entrepreneurship sellable to the people by inputting it into the educational curriculum at all levels the educational sector and utilised a re-modelled NYSC scheme to educate the youths more on the importance and essence of entrepreneurship development.

Emeh, (2014), conducted a study on the unemployment rate in Nigeria: Agenda for Government. He discovered that statistically speaking in the last couple of years, Nigeria's economy is one of the fastest-growing in the world while its people are the most impoverished in real terms. Nigeria in the recent past experienced an event where millions of people scampered for about 4500 job vacancies advertised by the Nigeria Immigration Service leading to the death of about eighteen of them in an unwarranted stampede betray the idiosyncrasy of the Nation's nominal growth without corresponding development. With global unemployment projected to reach above 215 million by 2018, experts fear that Africa, particularly Nigeria's share of global scourge would increase disproportionately, with attendant unsavoury consequences unless the country immediately adopts pro-active and holistic approach to halt the rising youth unemployment.

Salami (2013), conducted a research on youth unemployment in Nigeria: A time for creative and innovative intervention. He said that unemployment in Nigeria is a time bomb waiting to explode if effective interventions are not put in place to mitigate the unsavoury impact of high youth unemployment. His work establishes a link between entrepreneurship and youth

unemployment if adequate attention focused on the creation of enabling the socio-economic and political environment that can galvanise a culture where the youths think job creation away from the mindset of job seekers.

Nwachukwu and Ogbo (2012) conducted empirical research on the role of entrepreneurship in economic development: The Nigerian perspective. The paper aims to develop and analyse the contributions of entrepreneurship in the economic development through SME development in Nigeria. A total of 1000 SMES were randomly selected from a cross-section of a population of all SMES spread around some states of Nigeria. The hypotheses of this research were tested at 0.05 level of significance using chi-square statistics hinged on identifying the greatest problem which SMES face in Nigeria. The researcher found that SMES have played and continue to play significant roles in the growth, development and industrialisation of many economics the world over. They concluded that promoters of SMES should thus ensure the availability or possessions of managerial capacity and acumen before pursuing financial resources for developing the respective enterprise.

Baba (2013) conducted research work on the challenges of entrepreneurship development in Nigeria and way forward. He is of the view that in this era of shrinking economic activities, government should endeavour to provide the necessary infrastructures required for skill acquisition among its citizenry because without technological skills, entrepreneurial spirit that drives economic development through job creation will lack. He concluded that entrepreneurship is essential for rapid and sustained economic growth but there is an urgent need to change the mind-set of the average Nigerian especially the youths towards embracing self-employment and de-emphasize the search for white-collar jobs that are non-existent.

Okoye, Iloanya and Udunze, (2014), conducted research on the extent to which entrepreneurship in Nigeria has helped reduce youth unemployment. The study revealed that government policies and initiative has affected the “transformation question”, resulting to the increase in corruption, inadequate and maladministration. They concluded that entrepreneurship country is an engine for job creation, innovation and diversity and that Nigeria’s entrepreneurs have a long way to go before they can effectively drive changes in the economy. They recommend that government should genuinely recognise the essence of entrepreneurship to economic development by providing the enabling environment for the youth to be gainfully employed for economic development.

Asad, Ali and Islam (2014) examined the need to reduce unemployment through entrepreneurship in Pakistan. The regression results indicate that 91 percent variations in entrepreneurship development have been explained by the explanatory variations in variables. The unemployment rate has been negatively related to entrepreneurial development. The high rate of unemployment has been associated with a low level of entrepreneurial development in the economy of Pakistan.

Methodology

The research design embodies the blue print for the collection, measurement and analysis of data related to the research questions. Survey research design was used in conducting the research.

The sources of data used were primary and secondary sources.

Population of the study

The population of the study was some chosen entrepreneurs from the five communities in Aninri L.G.A. of Enugu state.

Rice processors	Eateries	Tailors	Carpenter	Hair dressers	Total
28	24	26	27	30	135

The entire population of study was used because it was not countless.

Methods of data analysis

The responses to the questionnaire were first analysed using tables and simple percentages, while hypothesis was tested using Chi –square. The formula for Chi-square is

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$$

where: X^2 = Chi- square

O = Observed frequency

E = Expected frequency

Decision rule

Reject Ho and accept Hi if the calculated Chi-square is more than the critical value of Chi-square.

Data presentation and analysis

Table 4.1. Skill acquisition helped increase employment generation

Rating	Rice processors	Eateries	Tailors	Carpenter s	Hair dressers	Total	Percentage
SA	14	9	13	10	15	61	45.19
A	11	12	9	14	9	55	40.74
UD	3	3	4	3	6	19	14.07
SD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
D	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	28	24	26	27	30	135	100

Source: Field survey 2021

Table 4.1 above shows that 109 of t2q6he respondents representing 58.29 % strongly agree that skill acquisition enhances employment generation, while 78 respondents representing 41.71 percentage agree that skill acquisition enhances employment generation. Therefore, this shows that majority strongly agree that skill acquisition enhances employment generation.

Testing of hypothesis

Ho: skills acquisition does not have a positive and significant effect on the employment generation of Aninri L.G.A.

Hi: skill acquisition has positive and significant effect on employment generation.

Table 4.2: Calculated Chi-Square table

O	E	O – E	(O – E)2	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
11	11.1	-0.1	0.01	0.001
15	20.2	-5.2	27.04	1.33
15	11.1	3.9	15.21	1.37
13	8.6	4.4	19.36	2.25
14	17.1	3.1	9.61	0.56
2	2.9	-0.9	0.81	0.28
5	5.3	0.3	0.09	0.02
5	2.9	2.1	4.41	1.52
1	2.3	-1.3	1.69	0.73
5	4.5	0.5	0.25	0.06
9	7.9	1.1	1.21	0.15
20	14.5	5.5	30.25	2.09
2	7.9	-5.9	34.81	4.41
3	6.2	-3.2	10.24	1.65
15	12.3	2.7	7.29	0.59
				17.011

Source: Field survey 2021

Decision rule: If the calculated value table is greater than the critical value, reject null hypothesis (Ho) and accept the alternative hypothesis (Hi).

Decision

Since the calculated value (17.011) > 15.51 (critical value), reject the null hypothesis (Ho) and accept the alternative hypothesis which states that skill acquisition had helped to increase employment generation in Aninri L.G.A.

Summary of major findings

The researchers determined that skills acquisition had significant and positive effects on employment generation in Aninri L.G.A, with the cal value $17.011 > \text{Cri value } 15.51$.

Conclusion

Researchers concluded that since skill acquisition helped to increase employment generation that it should be encouraged and technical education should be introduced in all levels of educational systems in Nigeria as it will tailor the minds of the young people to be entrepreneurial early in life.

Recommendation

The researchers recommended that government at all levels in Nigeria should have policies that will support entrepreneurship development and enabling environment that will encourage employable adults to acquire skills.

References

- Alanana O. O. (2003). Youth unemployment in Nigeria: Some implications for the third millennium. *Global J. Soc. Sci.* 2(1):21-26.
- Adebayo A. (1999). Youth unemployment and national directorate of employment self employment programmes. *Niger. J. Econ. And Soc. Stud.* 41(1): 81-102.
- Adejumo, G. (2000). Indigenous entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. Characteristics, Problems and Prospects. *Journal of Department of Business Administration*, University of Illorin Nigeria.
- Adeniyi, J. A. (2013). Persistence of unemployment in Nigeria. The role of output growth and population. *The IUP Journal of Applied Economics*, (12), 4.
- Ahenkan, A. & Osei – Kojo A (2014). Achieving sustainable development in Africa: progress, challenges and prospects *International Journal of Development and Sustainability* 3 (1) 162 - 174.
- Asad A., Ali M. & Islam U. (2014). The relationship between entrepreneurship development and unemployment reduction in Pakistan. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*. Available in <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/3.01> retrieved on 10th March 2015.
- Anyadike N., Emeh I. E. J. and Ukah F. O. (2012). Entrepreneurship development and employment generation in Nigeria: Problems and prospects. *Universal Journal of Education and General Studies* 1(4) 88-102.
- Ariyo, D. (2005). Small firms are the backbone of the Nigerian economy. <http://www.africaeconomicanalysis.org>. Last Accessed 1 Nov. 2014
- Awogbenle AC, Iwuamadi KC(2010). Youth Unemployment: Entrepreneurship Development Programme as an Intervention Mechanism. *Afr. J. Bus. Manag.* 4(6):831-835.
- Ayinde O. E. (2008). Empirical analysis of agricultural growth and unemployment in Nigeria. *Afr. J. Agric. Res.* 3(7):465-468.
- Baba, G.K. (2013). The Challenges of Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria and way forward. *Journal of Business and Organizational development*. Available in www.cenresimpub.org retrieved on 10th March, 2015.

- Chu, H. M. Kara, O. and Benzing, C. (2008). An empirical study of Nigerian entrepreneurs: Success, motivations, problems, and stress. *International Journal of Business Research*, Find http://findarticles.com/p/articles/mi_6773/is_2_8/ai_n31121252/ Last Accessed 16 Aug, 2016.
- Eme, O.I. (2014). Unemployment Rate in Nigeria: Agenda for Government, *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*.
- Igbo, B.C. (2006). *Understanding Entrepreneurs Business*. Nsukka, Fulladu Publishers.
- International Labour Organization (2007). Enterprise based youths employment policies, strategies and programmes initiatives for the development of enterprise action and strategies, ILO Skills working paper No. 1.
- ILO – Report on Women Entrepreneurship – <http://www.wordquotient.com>. Business Articles-24/4/2014
- Morphy R.(2008). Nigeria: Youth unemployment, poverty – a time bomb for country. *Leadership*, Wednesday, 27 August
- National Population Commission and ICF Macro. (2009). Nigeria demographic and health survey 2008. Abuja, Nigeria: *National Population Commission* and ICF Macro.
- Nwachukwu, A. C. & Ogbo, A. (2012). The role of entrepreneurship in economic development: The Nigeria perspective. *European Journal of Business and Management*. Available in www.iiste.org retrieved on 16th March, 2015.
- Okafor E. E. (2011). Youth unemployment and implications for stability of democracy in Nigeria. http://www.jsdafrica.com/Jsda/V13No1_Spring_2011.
- Okafor E. E. (2008). Development crisis of power supply and implications for industrial sector in Nigeria. *Journal of Tribes and Tribals*, 6(2), 83-92.
- Okoye N. C., Iloanya, K. & Udunze, U. (2014). Youth unemployment and entrepreneurship development: Challenges & prospects in Nigeria. Kuwait Chapter of Arabian. *Journal of Business and Management Review*.
- Onoh, B. C. E., (2017). Introduction to entrepreneurship development. Cheston Agency Press Ltd. Cheston Plaza, Off Police Detective College, Ologo, New Site, Enugu. Nigeria
- OECD (2001), *Sustainable Development: Critical Issues*.
- Onyebueke & Ochnongo (2002). Entrepreneurship and economic development, Enugu: *Precision Printers and Publishers*.
- Oylola, O. T., Ajiboshin, I. O., Raimi, L., Raheem, S. & Igwe, .C. N. (2013). Entrepreneurship for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development Studies*, 2, (2), 197-215
- Salami CGE(2011). Entrepreneurial interventionism and challenges of youth unemployment in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research Volume 11 Issue7 Version 1.0 July 2011*. Global Journals Inc. (USA)
- Salami, C.G.E. (2013). Youth unemployment in Nigeria: A time for creative intervention. *International Journal of Business and Marketing management* www.regjournals.org/IJBMM.
- Sagagi, M.S. (2010). Enterprise development through value chain Analysis: A case of Kano State, Nigeria”. Readings in African Entrepreneurship, BUK – ESSEX, Kano: Adamu Joji Publishers. 48 – 50.
- Sims, L. & Falkenberg (2013). Developing competences for education for sustainable development: a case study of Canadian faculties of education. *International Journal of Higher Education* 2 (4). 1 – 14.
- Taiwo, O. E. (2014). Impact of entrepreneurship development on job creation in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Entrepreneurship*.
- Udu, E. &Agu, G.A. (2005). New system economics. Onitsha; Africana First Publishers Ltd.
- World Bank, (2004). Partnership in development: progress in the fight against poverty. Washington C: World Bank

ENTERPRENUERISM AS A PANACEA TO JOB CREATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF NIGERIA

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Abstract

Research Purpose: *The role of Entrepreneurs in economic growth and development of any nation cannot be underestimated. They serve as catalyst that drives the economy of nations especially in less developed countries to the next level. Previous literatures reviewed were unable to ascertain the categories of entrepreneurs that create new jobs in Nigeria and techniques they use. This study seeks to find out the categories of entrepreneurs that help to create jobs that are more new and ways they create them in Nigeria using survey research design and random sampling technique.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *A sample of 383 was drawn from a population of 10000 registered and unregistered entrepreneurs in Enugu Urban constituency, Enugu state Nigeria. The data for the study was collected using a well-structured questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Kuder Richardson 20, which was 0.86. The data was analyzed using mean score average.*

Findings: *The researcher discovered that the categories of entrepreneurs that create new jobs are the investors, intrapreneurs or innovator and online entrepreneurs. They do this by incorporating new technology into their businesses to promote efficiency, providing employment opportunities, addressing environmental and social - economic challenges and availing themselves to innovative competitions among other things.*

Implications: *The implication of these findings is that without these few groups of entrepreneurs in Nigeria, the economic growth and development of Nigeria will be a mirage. These entrepreneurs guarantee both short-term and long-term prospective unlike sole proprietorship which have only short term prospective and they are mostly predominant in Nigeria.*

Originality/Value Added: *The researcher therefore recommended among other things that Government should encourage Nigerian entrepreneurs to create more jobs that are new by venturing into incorporated businesses. Also educated and skilled youths should be encourage to find partners with quality skills that can complement their own by visiting conferences for entrepreneurship in other to form incorporated businesses ventures.*

Keywords: Entrepreneurism, Development, Job creation, Nigerian economy

Introduction

An entrepreneur is a person that starts a business, works for himself and taking on financial risks in the hope of profit. He is a job creators whose companies create every single product or service that is needed on a daily basis (Mitchell (2019). Entrepreneurs specialized in or combination of these four categories-product, service, information and attention (Gilbert, 2020).Some types of entrepreneurship need money or influence to be effective while other types of entrepreneurship need sweat, equity and hard work (Newman,2019). The need for entrepreneurism in the growth and development of Nigeria cannot be undermined due to current economic recession leading to geometric increase in unemployment rate and level of poverty in the country. Entrepreneurship businesses are still at a low level in Nigeria despite the fact that their activities fall within the essential goods and services needed on daily basis (Olakunle, 2020). Nigeria being a mono-economy driven by mostly oil industries with less attention to non-oil industries is naturally endowed with natural resources, diverse skilled labours and biggest domestic market in Africa. The productive labour force is currently on the increase as well as the unemployment rate, which is above 25% with millions of unemployed youths (Olayeide, 2020).

With these economic realities, there is need to create jobs and diversify the industrial and commercial sectors to utilize the abundant human and natural resources. Entrepreneurship businesses have been discovered to be an engine of economic growth in developed nations like U.S.A. and have the ability to provide quality life, employment opportunities and empowerments of the poor and downtrodden in the Country.

Small and Medium scale enterprises is seen as a pride of any nation because of its significant role as a catalyst for socio-economic transformation of any nation. Small and medium scale enterprises (SME'S) are real instrumentation for the achievement of national economic policy of employment generation and poverty reduction with small capital cost. SME's are also capable of attracting infrastural facilities, stimulation of economic activities in rural areas, reducing rural-urban migration and improvement in standard of living of people.

Many developing countries including Nigeria have started looking for solutions on how to integrate private sectors on their developmental policies and processes as one of the responses to the challenges of entrepreneurial development in these countries. Nigeria as a nation had already taken a bold step in this direction by including entrepreneurial studies in the educational curriculum and establishment of National directorate of employment scheme. The policy makers are of the opinion that such decision will inculcate the spirit of entrepreneurship in the mind of the public especially youths so as to get them ready for wealth creation by acquiring entrepreneurship skills. Entrepreneurship is sine qua non to national development, poverty reduction, employment generation and bedrock of industrialization in any economy.

The importance of entrepreneurship for productivity was first attributed to Alfred Marshal in 1990. In his book "Practice principle of Economics, marshal stated that there are four factors of production, they are land, labour, capital and organization. These factor are adequately use by an entrepreneur. Therefore, entrepreneur creates new commodities or improves on the old ones (Gilbert, 2020). Thus, early entrepreneurs were known for production and manufacturing with little capital. They began with trade by barter even before the origin of money, hence majority of the modern entrepreneurs engage in retail trade or sole proprietorship

Statement of Problem

Numerous researchers have written extensively on entrepreneurship and questioned its potency to generate employment, thus, underscoring the essence, importance and connectivity of this sub-sector in the development of any given economy. Knowledge gained by developed nations regarding the roles played by entrepreneurship support the fact that the importance of entrepreneurship cannot be overemphasized especially among the Developing Countries. Arguments have been ongoing lately about the future of work and entrepreneurial businesses in Nigeria especially in this period of economic recession This also coupled with fear of trying to understand the effects entrepreneurs will have on Nigerian industries and job creation. Available literatures reviewed showed the need and importance of entrepreneurship in job creation in Nigeria without specifying how these jobs and new ones can be created, and which categories of entrepreneurs create these jobs the most. This study seeks to find out the categories of entrepreneurs that can create new jobs the most and ways these entrepreneurs can create these new jobs and drive economic development of Nigeria to the next level

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out the categories of entrepreneurs that creates new jobs the most in Nigeria.
- 2) To find out ways entrepreneurs can create new jobs and drive economic development in Nigeria to the next level

Research Questions

- 1) What are the categories of entrepreneurs that create new jobs the most in Nigeria?
- 2) What are the ways entrepreneurs can create new jobs and drive economic development in Nigeria to the next level?

Statement of hypothesis

H0₁: there is no category of entrepreneurs that creates new jobs the most in Nigeria

H0₂: there is no way entrepreneurs can create new job and drive economic development in Nigeria

Significance of the Study

i). the findings from this study will be of immeasurable benefit to government and aspiring entrepreneurs in Nigeria.

ii). There is a record of serious economic depression caused by unemployment, hunger and poverty in Country. The study is very important this period as every economy is trying very hard to recover from the deadly effects of covid-19 virus. Nigerian businesses are already affected by this pandemic. Businesses are winding up and need reviving to boost economic growth and development.

iii). Many developing countries including Nigeria have started looking for solutions on how to integrate private sectors on their developmental policies and processes. The essence of this is to motivate people to become entrepreneurs, create new jobs that will help to drive the development of the country forward

Scope of the Study

This research work is de-limited to small and medium scale enterprises in Enugu Urban Constituency in Enugu state

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Various Scholars have define entrepreneurship to mean different thing, Mitchell (2019), stated that there are six most common types of entrepreneurs; they are Online Small Business, Investor, Lifestyle, Influencer and Internal entrepreneurs. An online entrepreneur is someone who makes his living selling a product, service or information online. Small business Entrepreneurs typically provide a service to a person or another small business. An investor is the Silicon Valley type of entrepreneur who takes massive risks and makes his money starting businesses with the intention of helping the next generation. A lifestyle entrepreneur is a type of entrepreneur that focuses on creating an environment where they can set their own schedule and live wherever they want. The goal is to be as flexible as possible and maximize enjoyment. Normally the people who are lifestyle entrepreneurs are called “digital nomads” or solopreneurs. A solopreneur is a person who operates entirely on their own, and without support from a team. An influencer is someone that built an audience around a topic and then sells exposure to that audience for instance the Hollywood celebrities. Finally, the intrapreneur can be every bit as valuable to the business as an entrepreneur because they can be irreplaceable to the decision makers. They embody the same business-mindedness, innovation and creativity that entrepreneurs do, often starting their own ideas and campaigns without handholding. All other entrepreneurs’ five entrepreneurs discussed in this work need intrapreneurs to work for them.

Stephenie (2020) view entrepreneurship as a deliberate and an orderly search for change conducted after a orderly analysis of different opportunities in a particular society. The author stated that entrepreneurship is a form of philosophy, because it portrays the way one thinks and acts and hence, it can exist in different forms, either in form of business, government or in the field of Knowledge, scientific, technology or poverty reduction. Historically, entrepreneurship has changed the bearing of different societies, industries or businesses. The author believed that an entrepreneur is a person who discovers a chance in a society, gather all the materials needed to

successfully use the resources, innovate, and render value to the society. These materials can be in form of technology, capital, organization natural and human resources.

Sylvia (2020) believed that entrepreneurship is the process of discovering an opportunity relevant to someone's needs and satisfaction and thus changing the opportunity into valuable product or services. The author also sees entrepreneurship as the activities or processes taking by entrepreneurs that are channeled towards attracting values associated with investment opportunities. Entrepreneurship can also be a process driven by the desire to innovate and produce new things or improving on existing ones and at the same time profiting from them.

According to George (2019), the reason for entrepreneurial development is to acquire an ability to look beyond and set a direction for fresh business opportunities by blending information from academic and market environment taking cognizance of the uncertainty and ambiguity facing fresh business set-ups. This entrepreneurial development requires courageous leadership, innovative tactics, creativity, sound strategies and good speculation of market trends.

Newman (2019) sees entrepreneurship as the process of making a different thing with so much value by dedicating enough energy and time knowing fully well the company's capacity in terms of capital, social and psychological risks and its sole motive of profit maximization.

Eric (2019) stated that entrepreneurship is the ability of a person to accept risks and make use of different factors of production to produce goods and services. The author also believed that entrepreneurship is the ability and willingness of a person to look for a business opportunities in a particular place and also capable and ready to start and manage the business successfully depending on the identified business discovery. This means that for entrepreneur to successful, he must acquire or possess the ability to look into his domain for business opportunities that will enhance his potentials in business and contribute to economic growth and development of his country.

Theoretical Literature

Entrepreneurship as a concept was believed to have originated in the early eighteenth century by a French economist known as Cantallion, who first described the word entrepreneurship as a "go-between", a "between-taker" or "risk-bearer". In the late eighteenth century, due to industrial revolution, the scope of entrepreneurship widened to include risk-bearer planning, organising, supervising and ownership of factors of production. Toward the nineteenth century, entrepreneurship took a new dimension following the advancement of new technologies adopted during the period of industrial revolution. Entrepreneurship therefore includes the suppliers of money with those who gain from entrepreneurial skills. By the late nineteenth century, the industrial revolution witnessed in the 18th century ushered in new technological advancement that brings about new invention and innovation in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship then includes the suppliers of money with interest and those who gain from entrepreneurial skills. The early twentieth century entrepreneurship was still viewed as quite different from management organisation until the mid-30's when Schumpeter (1943), an economist included innovation and untried technology known as creative destruction in entrepreneurship. Creative destruction is a process by which existing products, process, ideas and businesses are replaced with better ones, thus portraying the importance of innovation in entrepreneurship. The late twentieth century theorists like Peter Drucker's believes that entrepreneurship recognize and act on opportunities that comes from untapped and underdeveloped opportunities. Drucker(1985) is of the notion that not every new small business is entrepreneurial nor represents entrepreneurship. This simply means that entrepreneurship is the ability of new firms to create innovation The twenty- first century theories are also believed to be grounded on innovation. This theory known as the "institutional theory", "new growth theory," "evolutionary theory," "neo-Schumpeterian theory," or "innovation economics" help to reformulates the traditional entrepreneurial theories so that knowledge, entrepreneurship, technology and innovation will be at the center, rather than seen as

independent forces that operates on its own. Though no generally accepted theory has emerged from all these theories, study on entrepreneurship and entrepreneurs is still an ongoing process.

Empirical Review

Previous studies on entrepreneurial development among researchers and their findings are presented below.

Theodore(2020), studied the effect of entrepreneurship development on job creation in Nigeria with special reference to Ohaozara local government area of Ebonyi state. Using survey design and a random sampling technique, the author randomly selected a sample of 400 from 1000 respondent for the study. Data was analyzed using chi-square. The author discovered that there is a positive correlation between job creation and entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. Entrepreneurship development always gives birth to job creation in the country. According to the author, entrepreneurship encourages vibrant youths to engage on meaningful business activities to sustain themselves and contribute to economic growth and development in Nigeria. The author recommended that government should channel more effort towards empowering more Nigerians to embark on entrepreneurship ventures in order to create more jobs and reduce unemployment

Uhuabana and Erah (2020) studied the role of entrepreneurship in economic development of Nigeria using survey method. Sample of 1500 SME's were randomly selected from cross section of population of SME's spread around the states of Nigeria. Using chi-square method of data analysis. The researcher discovered that SME's have contributed immensely to the growth and development of Nigeria. He recommended among other things that advocates of SME's should possess managerial ability and entrepreneurial education before sourcing for capital to establish and develop their businesses.

Ezeude (2020) in his work "Nigeria's growing unemployment situation and dwindling potentials of the economy", using secondary data analysis the author showed that more than one million of Nigerian youths are not employed as recorded by the office of Bureau of statistics in 2019. The researcher concluded among other things that government should make entrepreneurship marketable to the Nigeria citizens by incorporating it into the educational curriculum at every level of the educational system and integrate it into National youth service scheme to produce vibrant entrepreneurs to will help to promote and drive entrepreneurial skills and development to excellent standard in Nigeria.

OLakunle (2020) looked at the relationship between entrepreneurship and Nigerian business enterprises. He discovered a decrease in small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria due to failures of series of government intervention policies targeted at stimulating entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. Instead of establishing import-substitution industries for sourcing of local raw materials, entrepreneurs rely on imported raw material, which make production very costly. This leads to low profit margin thereby discouraging entrepreneurship- spirit. He therefore recommends that government should enact new policy to protect infant industries in other to motivate entrepreneurship- spirit in Nigeria.

Yinusah (2019), on his study," leveraging the relationship between entrepreneurship and job creation" in Nigeria, He discovered that personal talent, knowledge, behaviours and skills together with other variables such as government loans, financial credits, information & technology; infrastructure, access to god road & markets help to drive entrepreneurial development in every economy.

Oladeho and Ikharo(2019), examined the impact of entrepreneurship on youth unemployment in Nigeria using secondary data The study discovered negative impact of entrepreneurship on youth

unemployment due to poor governmental policies, insecurity, corruption and bureaucratic bottleneck in government administrations in Nigeria. They recommended that government should pay more attention to entrepreneurship development in Nigeria and provide conducive environment for business start-ups to thrive.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher adopted survey research design. This is because the questions structured in this study-required people’s opinion and judgments.

Area of the study

The study covered the entire Enugu Urban state Constituency that includes Enugu East, Enugu North and Enugu South in Enugu state Nigeria.

Population of the study

The population of the study was 10000 registered businesspersons. These was made up of registered and unregistered entrepreneurs in the Enugu Urban constituency

Sample and sampling techniques

The researcher adopted a random sampling technique for the study. This was done by computing the sample size of all the entrepreneurs both registered and unregistered in Enugu Urban constituency out of population of 10000. The sample size for the study was computed using Yaro Yamane formula;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \tag{1}$$

Where:

N = Population for the study = 10000

e = Acceptable error term usually 0.05

n = Sample size

therefore:

$$n = \frac{10000}{1 + 10000(0.05)^2} = 385$$

Hence,

Sample size (n) = 385 at 95% confidence interval

Instrumentation

The researcher used a well structures questionnaire to elicit information from the respondent.

Validity of the instrument

The items of the instrument were subjected to face validation by one expert in the field of entrepreneurship, one expert in entrepreneurial education and one expert in Measurement and evaluation. Their corrections and comments were useful in modifying the items of the instrument. The surviving items, therefore, possess adequate face validity of the instrument for data collection

Content Validity

One expert in the field of entrepreneurship, one expert in entrepreneurial education and one expert in Measurement and evaluation using the test blue print that was developed by the researcher the instrument items to content validity. The table specification was validated by the experts to determine how effective it is in selecting questions considered the percentage allocation of the various levels of contents. Ten (10) questions survived out of eighteen (18) items after validation and these were reflected on the table of specification.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was determined using test re-test method with two hundred (200) respondents. The choice is because it is most suitable and appropriate in determining the relationship between variables in a study. The instrument was re-administered on the respondents after two weeks and data were collected. Then the two set of scores were from first and second administration of the instrument were correlated using Person Product moment correlation coefficient(r) and is 0.87. The measure of internal consistency was determined using Kuder Richardson 20 (K-20). The value of the Kuder Richardson 20 was 0.86. The choice of the Kuder Richardson’s 20 was the most appropriate because the items were dichotomously scored.

Method of data Collection

The researcher collected back the questionnaires by hand. Three hundred and eighty five (385) questionnaires were administered to the respondents. The researcher collected back (383) copies. Therefore, the sample size for the study was (383).

Method of data Analysis

The data collected was arranged on the tabular form. The researcher used four points: like- scales to assemble the data. The research question was analyzed using mean average. The researcher as a benchmark used an assumed mean of 3.0. The estimated mean is calculated using this formula;

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{n}$$

Hypothesis Testing

Decision rule

Reject null hypothesis (H0) if estimated mean value is less than 3.00, otherwise accept H0 and draw conclusion.

Results and Discussions of Results

This chapter presents and discussed the results of the study

Research Question 1

What are the categories of entrepreneurs that create new jobs the most in Nigeria?

Table 1: Categories of entrepreneurs that create new jobs in Nigeria

S/N	QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	N	Σfx	\bar{X}	Remark
	Categories of Entrepreneurs	4	3	2	1				
1.	Online Entrepreneurs	158	175	38	12	383	1,245	3.25	Accepted
		632	525	76	12				
2.	Small business entrepreneurs	45	30	173	135	383	751	1.96	Rejected
		180	90	346	135				

3.	Lifestyle entrepreneurs	48	32	173	130	383	764	2.0	Rejected
		192	96	346	130				
4.	An influencers entrepreneurs	16	30	154	183	383	645	1.68	Rejected
		64	90	308	183				
5.	Investors	177	157	30	19	383	1,258	3.28	Accepted
		708	471	60	19				
6.	Intrapreneurs or Innovators	185	145	25	28	383	1,253	3.27	Accepted
		740	435	50	28				

Source: Field survey, 2021

The result in Table 1 simply showed that investors, intrapreneurs or innovator and online entrepreneurs are categories of entrepreneurs that create new jobs in Nigeria. Their mean values are 3.28, 3.27 and 3.25 respectively, which are above the benchmark of 3.0. Small businesses, influencers and lifestyle entrepreneurs belong to the categories of entrepreneurs that do not create new jobs rather they end up creating jobs that will take care of themselves and their families. Their mean values are 1.96, 1.68 and 2.0, which are below the benchmark of 3.0 respectively.

Research Question 2

What are the ways entrepreneurs can create new jobs and drive economic development in Nigeria to the next level?

Table 2: Ways entrepreneurs can create new jobs and drive economic development in Nigeria to the next level

S/ N	QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS	SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	N	Σfx	- X	Remark
1.	Investing in products and services people need and incorporating new technology into their businesses to promote efficiency	195	133	21	19	368	1,240	3.7	Accepted
		780	399	42	19				
2.	Providing employment opportunities or job creation	179	147	30	12	383	1,229	3.34	Accepted
		716	441	60	12				
3.	Addressing environmental and social – economic challenges	162	191	10	5	383	1,246	3.38	Accepted
		648	573	20	5				
4.	Availing themselves to innovative competitions and engaging in regional and international trade to promote commerce and regional economic integration	180	140	18	30	383	1,206	3.28	Accepted
		720	420	36	30				

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 2 showed that entrepreneurs could create new jobs and drive economic development to the next level in Nigeria. These they can do by investing in products and services people need, incorporating new technology into their businesses to promote efficiency, providing employment opportunities, addressing environmental and social – economic challenges, availing themselves to innovative competitions and engaging in regional and international trade to promote commerce

and regional economic integration. The result also depicts that all these variables exceed an assumed mean of 3.0, which happen to be the benchmark chosen by the researcher. The above findings will be of immeasurable benefit to government and aspiring entrepreneurs in developing countries especially Nigeria in area of new job creation, ways to create them and achieving sustainable economic development

Evaluation of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1

H0₁: there are no categories of entrepreneurs that creates new jobs the most in Nigeria

H1₁: there are categories of entrepreneurs that create new jobs the most in Nigeria

Table 1 showed the categories of entrepreneurs that could create new jobs in Nigeria. They include the investors, intrapreneuers or innovator and online entrepreneurs. All these categories of entrepreneurs have mean averages above 3.0 that represent the benchmark for the study. Small businesses, influencers and lifestyle entrepreneurs belong to the categories of entrepreneurs that do not create new jobs rather they create jobs for themselves to satisfy their needs and that of their families. Their mean averages are below 3.0. We therefore reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative, which stated that there are categories of entrepreneurs that create new jobs the most in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

H0₂: there is no way entrepreneurs can create new job and drive economic development in Nigeria.

H1₂: there are different ways entrepreneurs can create new job and drive economic development in Nigeria

Table 2 showed different ways entrepreneurs could create new jobs in Nigeria. They can create new jobs by investing in products and services people need, incorporating new technology into their businesses to promote efficiency, providing employment opportunities , addressing environmental and social - economic challenges, availing themselves to innovative competitions and engaging in regional and international trade to promote commerce and regional economic integration. There mean values are above 3.0 benchmark, therefore we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there are different ways entrepreneurs can create new job and drive economic development in Nigeria to the next level.

Findings

Result from the field survey revealed that there are categories of entrepreneurs that could create new jobs in Nigeria. They include the investors, intrapreneuers or innovator and online entrepreneurs. Small businesses, influencers and lifestyle entrepreneurs belong to the categories of entrepreneurs that do not create new jobs rather they create jobs for themselves to satisfy their needs and that of their families. Furthermore, entrepreneurs can create new jobs by investing in products and services people need, incorporating new technology into their businesses to promote efficiency, providing employment opportunities , addressing environmental and social - economic challenges, availing themselves to innovative competitions and engaging in regional and international trade to promote commerce and regional economic integration.

Conclusions

Entrepreneurism represents a route to upward mobility and a way average person build their wealth. Entrepreneurship and innovation fuel economic growth and development of any nation because entrepreneurs create businesses, businesses create jobs and people with jobs make good

customers. Some businesses were created with the sole aims of making both ends meet while some are created to create more new jobs like the incorporated ventures by high skilled entrepreneurs. This study tried to find out the categories of entrepreneurs that create new jobs the most and ways they can create these jobs in other to drive economic development of Nigeria to the next level. The researcher discovered that the categories of entrepreneurs that create new jobs are the investors, intrapreneurs or innovator and online entrepreneurs. They do this by investing in products and services people need, incorporating new technology into their businesses to promote efficiency, providing employment opportunities, addressing environmental and social - economic challenges, availing themselves to innovative competitions and engaging in regional and international trade to promote commerce and regional economic integration.

Policy Implication of the Study

If Entrepreneurship is not the life- blood of every nation, the likes of Dangote, Innoson, Markzuckberg, Steve Jobs and Bill Gate will not be in the world history of entrepreneurship. Without entrepreneurship, the economic growth and development of Nigeria will be a mirage. There is very little job creation by most entrepreneurs in Nigeria beyond those created for themselves which have only short time prospective. Nigeria needs the mix of investors, intrapreneurs/innovator, online entrepreneurs and supports of other entrepreneurs to take the economy to the next level. The economy is faced with so many challenges including environmental, social and economic challenges that seek for the attention of Government and Nigerian entrepreneurs. Failure to address these problems will have a long lasting negative implication on the economic growth and development of Nigeria more especially in the area of job creation and poverty reduction.

Recommendations

- ❖ There is need for new job creation in Nigeria especially during this period of economic recession. Government and Nigerian entrepreneurs can create more jobs that are new by venturing into incorporated businesses instead of sole proprietorships. This is because incorporated businesses have the ability to create jobs and have both short-run and long run prospective.
- ❖ Nigeria entrepreneurs should be encourage to create new jobs by venturing into businesses like agriculture, power generation, healthcare, lowering green gas emissions, preserving biodiversity and combating climatic change.
- ❖ Educated and skilled youths should be encourage to find partners with quality skills that can complement their own by visiting conferences for entrepreneurship.

Contribution to Knowledge

The work has contributed to the body of knowledge by establishing that certain categories of entrepreneurs create new jobs in Nigeria. They include the investors, intrapreneurs or innovator and online entrepreneurs. They do this by incorporating new technology into their businesses to promote efficiency, providing employment opportunities, addressing environmental and social - economic challenges and availing themselves to innovative competitions among other things.

Limitations of the study

The following are the limitation of the study.

1. The time given for the completion of this research was very short and was combined with an academic work, which makes it more cumbersome.
2. Lack of finance to run around for materials was another challenge faced by the researcher
3. The unwillingness of the respondents to give out certain useful information is also another impediment to the study

Suggestions for Further Study

The researcher suggested that more research work should be conducted in these areas:

1. Effect of entrepreneurship development on the economic growth and development of Nigeria
2. Impact of Entrepreneurship on youth development in Nigeria
3. Entrepreneurship as a panacea to industrial revolution and wealth creation in Nigeria

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References

- Ephraim, O. (2020). Effects of unemployment on industrial productivity in Nigeria, College of education technical umunze, Anambra state, unpublished project
- Eric. U. (2019).Don't blame the entrepreneur, blame the government: Enterprises, vol. 2.NO.3, pp34-45
- Ezeude,G. (2020).“Nigeria’s unemployment situation and recessive economy” Journal of sustainable economic development, vol.2.No.5.pp103-122
- Gilbert, V.(2020).Importance of entrepreneurship in Nigeria economy. Published Thesis, Department of Economics, Abia state University Uturu.
- George. (2019).The need for entrepreneurial development in Nigeria. Journal of Economics, development and Investment, Vol.1.No.3.
- Mitchell. (2019). The 6-types of entrepreneurs: which one are you? <http://strtb.ro/35oeFfH> or startupbro.com/entrepreneurs
- Newman, F.(2019). Entrepreneurship; an integrated business approach, Enterprise, vol.3.No.2, pp 56-69
- Nwakobi,S and Okolie, N.(2018). Entrepreneurship and unemployment reduction in Nigeria, Journal of Education and General studies vol.5.No 2. pp 12-29.
- Oladeho.V & Ikharo M. (2019). Impact of entrepreneurship on youth unemployment in Nigeria, Quarterly journal of business management, vol.3.No.2.pp27-42.
- OLakunle, C. (2020). “Relationship between entrepreneurship and industrial output” A Lecture Presented at First Annual Students’ Entrepreneurship Lecture organized by the Students Union Government, Sokoto
- Olayeide,O.M.(2020).Local entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria, problems and prospects; *Journal of department of business administration University of Lagos, Nigeria, vol.3.No, 4 12-22.*
- Onyenuke, E. (2018). Challenges and prospects of Entrepreneurship development in Nigeria and way forward, Journal of Business and Financial development, vol.2 No.3. pp 24-42
- Okpalaojiego, E.(2012). Entrepreneurism as a panacea to job creation and development of Nigeria. Unpublished seminar paper, Department of Economics, University of Nigeria, Nsukka

- Orogbu, O. L., et al(2015).Entrepreneurial Development and Job Creation in Selected Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria).International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR) Volume 3, Issue 7, July 2015, PP 41-53 ISSN 2349-0330 (Print) & ISSN 2349-0349 (Online),www.arcjournals.org ©ARC Page 41
- Schumpeter, J.A., (1943). Capitalism, Socialism and democracy-6th ed. Counter Poist edition. Unwin paperbacks.
- Stephanie, T.(2020). Entrepreneurship and Economic growth in Nigeria: the way forward, Nigeria research journal of Entrepreneurship, vol.3.No.2.pp101-114
- Sylvia, A.(2020). Importance of *Entrepreneurs in job creation in Nigeria*: Business Review, Vol 64, No.14. Pp 12-29
- Sappin, E.(October 20,2016). 7ways entrepreneurs drive economic development. Sappine global strategies.
- Theodre, H. (2020). Effect of entrepreneurship development on job creation in Nigeria: Journal of business management, college of education technical Umunze, vol.3.No.2, pp53-67
- Uhuabana & Erah (2020). Role of entrepreneurship in economic development of Nigeria, Journal of Entrepreneurship and Technology, vol.2.No.1.pp13-22
- Vikash, K. (February 20, 2020).Theories of Entrepreneurship, online
- Yinusah (2019) ,leveraging the relationship between entrepreneurship and job creation” in Nigeria, *Business review* Vol. 4, NO .1.121-134.

NON-LIFE INSURANCE CLAIMS ON GROSS FIXED CAPITAL FORMATION IN NIGERIA 1981-2018

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Abstract

Research Purpose: *The study investigated the relevance of Non-Life Insurance Claims in facilitating the growth of Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria from 1981-2018.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *Ex-post facto design was used to establish the cause effect relationship of the variables. The study employed Secondary Data sourced from World Bank National Accounts Data, OECD National Account Data Files, CBN Statistical Bulletin and NAICOM market statistics 2019. The technique adopted for this study was multiple regression econometric procedure of the ordinary least square (OLS), three hypotheses were formulated and tested using 0.5 level of significance.*

Findings: *The study revealed that Fire insurance, general accident insurance and Motor vehicle insurance claims had a negative and insignificant effect on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria.*

Implication: *The findings conclude that Non-Life Insurance Claims had a negative and insignificant effect on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria.*

Originality/Value Added: *The study recommends that insurance sector should be prompt in claims settlement without unnecessary disputes in order to boost the confidence of the various investment outlets in the country in purchasing insurance coverage. Finally Government should ensure the compliance of compulsory insurance in order for the insurance industry to be effective in contributing to Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria*

Keywords: non-life insurance, gross fixed capital formation, fire insurance, general accident insurance, motor vehicle insurance, claims

Introduction

Gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) being a macroeconomic conception used in official domestic accounts has in terms of principle acknowledged as an indispensable factor to facilitate economic development and employment (Overseas Development Institute (ODI, 2016)). In Nigeria there have been incredible growths in the rate of gross fixed capital formation. At current price, the GFCF is at N25.416 billion in 2019 (World Bank National Accounts Data, and OECD National Account Data Files 2019).

Indemnification reinstates the monetary positions of individuals and businesses to their pre-loss positions through insurance; insurance sinks amassed risks, liberates or preserves funds for other industrious activities thus heightening the prevailing stock of wealth in the economy (Ehiogu, 2018).

Hence as the primary function of insurance companies in an economy is the curtailing the effects of losses by providing financial compensation that may befall various economic outlets in the event of an unwanted circumstance occurring, Non-life insurance coverages cannot be overemphasized as loss or damage to the various economic components can lead to economic breakdown without any form of protection (Nwite 2014)

Though there have been raging disapproving arguments as to the benefits of exclusively non-life insurance to the economy. Limited studies have revealed that insurance activities, as a means of risk handover and indemnification, contribute to financial development through stimulating financial solidity, allowing diverse risks to be managed more resourcefully, encouraging the buildup of fresh capital and facilitating to moderate damages as well as the undesirable concerns that indiscriminate shocks could have on investment in the economy (Haiss&Sumegi, 2006; Levine, 2004).

This argument has formed wrong public opinion in Nigeria that insurance is a gaming or wagering and such assumptions lack of comprehensive studies (in disaggregated form) of the response of Gross Fixed Capital Formation to stimuli emanating from the claims payments on key non-life insurance policies (Nwite 2014).

It is against these background that the researchers sought:

1. To investigate the influence of fire insurance claims on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria
2. To find out how general accident insurance claims has obstructed Gross Fixed Capital
3. To assess the effect of motor vehicle insurance claims on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria

The study is time-series based. The period of the study runs from 1981 to 2018. The base year of 1981 was chosen given that it was a year in which data on all the variables in the study as provided by the sources of data started at the same time. Gross fixed capital formation is the dependent variable while Non-life claim is the independent variables which is measured with fire insurance, claim, general accident insurance claim and motor vehicle insurance claim. The outcome from the study will be of massive significance to administrators, financial forecasters, stakeholders, insurance companies, investors, government and other institutions as the effects of non-life insurance claims settlement on gross fixed capital formation will be recognized.

Literature Review

Claims

Agreeing to Krishman (2010), claim is a demand on an insurance company to fulfil its quota of the undertaking committed to while writing the contract with the policyholder. Asokere and Nwankwo (2010) defined a claim by way of a request made by the policyholder to the insurer for the compensation of benefits under a policy. Brooks, Popow and Hoopes (2005) previously succumbed that an insurance claim is correspondingly a request by a person or an organization seeking to recuperate from an insurer for a damage that an insurance policy might cover. A claim, agreeing to Vaughan and Vaughan (2008), is labelled as a notification to an amount payable under the terms of a policy.

However, Francis and Butler (2010) labelled claim as a defining moment in the relationship between an insurance firm and its client. Equally, such relationship can develop to being strong if the insurers are able to address five important concerns such as: taking greater control of the claim process; understanding their policyholders; selecting the right claims model for their industry; developing a communally favourable relationship with other service providers; and gaining an information advantage. Singh (2012) discourses that underwriters can change the claims processing by leveraging modern claims system that are affiliated with healthy business intelligence, document and content management system that will develop claims processing efficiency and effectiveness.

Non-Life Insurance Claims

Ehiogu & Duruechi (2021), an insurance claim is the only way to officially apply for benefits under an insurance policy, but until the insurance company has assessed the situation it will remain only a claim, not a pay-out. The Claims under investigation in non-life insurance can be treated under the following broad categorizations: -

- Fire insurance
- Automobile insurance (Motor vehicle insurance)
- General Accident Insurance Claims

Fire Insurance Claims

The significance of fire insurance can be concluded from the point that fire hazards are one of the great scourges of our time. Fire is a superlative servant but a dreadful master. Fire insurance claims necessitate the management of expert technical knowledge.

This is due to the element that many insurers are expected to be involved and because the loss may be of great complexity.

If the claim relates to goods, it is essential to take into account depreciation or appreciation in order to observe the elementary principle of indemnity. Sensible business proof is prerequisite, but the production of invoices or other proof of cost is not needed where the insurance is centred on a professional inventory and valuation. If the fire is as a result of negligence of third party, the insurers by the exercise of subrogation rights may be able to recuperate from that third party any amount paid under the policy.

Motor Insurance Claims

Automobile or motor insurance as it is generally called is the most prevalent form of insurance in Nigeria today as exposed by this study. The claims condition in the motor policy necessitates the policy holder to give instant notice to the insurance company of an accident or the incidence of the insured peril.

The subsequent is the full wording of this condition as contained in the motor policy issued by most of the prominent insurers in Nigeria.

“Notice shall be given in writing immediately upon the occurrence of any accident or loss or damage and in the event of any claim. Every letter claim write summons and/or process on receipt by the insured.

Notice shall also be given to the company immediately the insured shall have knowledge of any impending prosecution inquest of fatal give rise to claim under this policy. This may be the subject of a claim under this policy the insured shall give immediate notice to the police and co-operate with the company insuring the conviction of the offender.

Automobile insurance claims can arise as a result of accidental damage to the insured’s vehicle, theft of the insured vehicle, fire damage to the insured’s vehicle, and third party’s property, or death of or personal injury to a third party.

General Accident Insurance Claims

Accident claims are usually dealt with by the insurers’ own staff. Adjusters are sometimes appointed for the large burglary claims and occasionally with the classes of business.

Method of Claims Settlement

When a claim has been fully documented and adjusted, there are various ways in which settlement can be made. Ayeni (2000) gave ways in which claims may be settled.

- 1. Cash:** This is the most obvious and in some ways the suitable method of settling claims. Indeed with liability claims this is the only practicable method available.
- 2. Replacement:** It is sometimes advantageous for the insurer to replace an article rather than to pay cash with a very new item or with such things as jewellery and furs. Depreciation is likely to be negligible and the insured article may well be acquired at a discount from the appropriate dealer.
- 3. Repair:** An adequate repair constitutes an indemnity. This form of settlement is particularly common in Motor Insurance, where the insurer settles the repair bill directly with the garage concerned.
- 4. Reinstatement:** This is a term usually found in fire insurance and concerns the restoration or rebuilding of premises (not necessarily on the same site) to their former condition. This can give rise to difficulties, if the insured is not happy about the standard of work, but in some circumstances the insurer may be required to pay policy moneys in respect of re-instatement as opposed to other methods.

Concept of Capital Formation

Capital formation is defined as the process of building investable assets of value, the increase in wealth or the creation of further wealth. Capital formation is not savings though savings may be a process of capital accumulation because accumulation deals with the increase in stock of real investments and not all savings are necessarily invested. The increase in investment through non-financial assets is responsible for an increase value and gross domestic product to the economy through further increase in employment (Adekunle&Aderemi 2012). The Central Bank of Nigeria (2007), defines “capital formation as the total change in the value of fixed assets in the economy in addition to fixed assets either for replacing or adding to the stocks, it refers to the increase in the fixed capital stocks of the capital formed”. In Nigeria there have

been tremendous growths in the rate of gross fixed capital formation in Nigeria. The GFCF price was N18.2 billion in 1981. From 1982 to 1987 it declined until 1988 when it assumed an increasing trend. The GFCF was N40.1bn in 1990, N141.9bn in 1995, N331.1bn in 2000, N804.4 billion in 2005 and N1546.5 billion in 2006. It came up to N2053 billion in 2008, and N4207.4 billion in 2011, (Kanun, Ozurumba and Anyanwu, 2014)

Concept of Gross fixed capital formation

(GFCF) is a macroeconomic perception used in official domestic accounts. It is called "gross" since the measure does not make any alterations to subtract the consumption of fixed capital (depreciation of fixed assets) from the investment records. GFCF is not a degree of total investment, since only the value of net additions to immovable assets is measured, and all varieties of financial assets are excluded, as well as stocks of inventories and other operating costs. In national accounts, immovable assets require a wider coverage than immovable assets in business accounts. Fixed assets are produced assets that are used repetitively or constantly in production processes for more than single year. The variety of immovable assets comprised in statistical measurement is demarcated by the purpose in using them. An automobile for instance is a fixed asset, but automobiles are incorporated in GFCF since they are essentially used in work activities, i.e. if they fall within the range of "production". A car for own use only is not normally incorporated. The boundaries are not always easy to define however, since automobiles may be used both for own use and for industrial purposes; a conventional rule is ordinarily useful in that circumstance. Non-produced properties (e.g. land) except the value of land improvements, subsoil assets, mineral reserves, natural resources such as water, primary forests) are excluded from the official measure of GFCF. Also ordinary repair work, purchases of durable household equipment (e.g. private cars and furniture) and animals reared for their meat are not part of GFCF.

Theoretical Review

The relationship concerning capital formation and insurance within the confines of this investigation is supported by three main theories viz. the Neo-classical Theory of Growth, Financial Liberalization Theory and the Finance-Growth Nexus Theory. The growth theory initiated by Solow (1957) and Swan (1956) recognises contributors to development as labour, capital, technical progress and any additional variable incorporated in the growth accounting exercise. Agreeing to this theory the thrust for economic growth had to come outside the system, mainly from technological progress which is clearly preserved as exogenous. Nevertheless the central inquiry of why labour supply (both quantity and quality) capital amassing and technical progress grow at dissimilar rates in different countries still stays with us. Further, the neoclassical growth theory headed by Solow (1957) anticipated merging of per capital income across countries. Secondly, there is the theory of Financial Liberalization which has its origins in the work of McKinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973). However, it was Patrick (1966), who published the seminal work on the relationship between financial development and economic growth. He theorized two possible relationships, a "demand following" approach, in which financial development arises as the economy develops, and a "supply leading" phenomenon, in which the widespread development of financial institutions leads to economic growth (Arestis, Nissanke and Stein, 2005). Thirdly, there is the finance-growth nexus theory by (Schumpeter, 1911). Borrowing from Schumpeter, financial services are important for economic growth as long as they increase productivity by stimulating technological innovation, investment and aiding business persons with the best chances of achievement in the improvement process. Bringing all the above together, this study is theoretically anchored on the fact that capital which is formed by insurance activities is used for production which stimulates growth.

Empirical Review

Lezaasi and Tamunonimim (2012) tried at investigating the relationship between insurance risk management denoted by claims payment and Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) in Nigeria. The study engaged the ordinary least square, Johansen co-integration, Granger causality, impulse response and variance

decomposition procedures on annual rate of change in Nigerian, using data from 1980 to 2011. The outcomes show that claims paid on Accident, Fire, Motor vehicle and Employers' Liability insurance policies impacted growth in GFCF. It was instituted that unidirectional causation flow happens from GFCF to indemnifications made on Fire and Marine insurance policies. This infers that development in the procurement of new productive capital stocks could prompt up insurance patronage particularly in fire and marine insurance. The variance decomposition analysis of GFCF to innovations originating from indemnifications on fire and motor vehicle insurance policies show positive and reliable expansionary effects over a decade projection period into the future; consequently, as insurance indemnifications rises, the trend of indemnification pressures initiates the economy to upturn its capital formation in broad terms.

Gap in literature

The study seeks to update the previous work carried out by Lezaasi and Tamunonimim in 2012 investigating insurance risk management represented by claims payment and Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) in Nigeria from 1980 to 2011 and to reveal if there exist any variations in findings using multiple regression to estimate the effect of fire, general accidents and motor vehicle insurance claims variables on Gross Fixed Capital Formation from 1981-2018.

Methodology

In the course of this work, the research design engaged is the *ex-post facto* design which seeks to establish the cause effect relationship and the variables of interest are not under the control of the researcher and therefore cannot be manipulated.

The populations used for this study are Secondary data from World Bank National Accounts Data, OECD National Account Data Files, Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and NAICOM market statistics 2019 which covers from 1981-2018.

The technique adopted for this study is multiple regression econometric procedure of the ordinary least square (OLS)

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is the measure of goodness of fit. It is used to measure the power of the explanatory variables on the dependent variable. The R^2 denotes the percentage of the variation in the dependent variable that is accounted for by the independent variables. The value of R^2 lies between 0 and 1. The closer the R^2 is to 1, the better the goodness of fit. If $R^2 = 1$, it implies that there is 100 percent explanation of the variation in the dependent variable by the independent variables. This signifies a perfect fit of the regression line. However, if $R^2 = 0$, it then indicates that the explanatory variables do not explain any changes in the dependent variable.

Model Specification

Multiple regression econometrics method will be used to analyse the Impact of Non-Life Insurance Claims on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria.

Thus, the model is expressed functionally as follows.

$$(GFCF) = F(\text{Fire claims, accident claims, motor claims}) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

$$GFCF = \text{GROSS FIXED CAPITAL FORMATION}$$

$$GFCF = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Fire_claims}_t + \beta_2 \text{accident_claims}_t + \beta_3 \text{motor_claims}_t + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Whereas,

t = time period

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = constant parameters or intercept of a regression line which capture the effect of the entire variable excluded from the equation.

μ = the error term which is the disturbance term or random variable. A random variable is variables which value depend on chances or probabilities. Therefore, at any particular point in time the mean of the μ is equal to zero (0).

Apriori Expectation

The a priori criteria are based on the principles of economic theory concerning the possible relationship between dependent and independent variables. In evaluating the result of the estimation base on the a priori expectation, the result will find out whether the sign of the estimated parameter are as expected. It is one of the criteria used in determining whether the estimates are theoretically meaningful. Whereas $\beta_0 > 0, \beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0$ and $\beta_3 > 0 \beta_4 > 0$

Test of Hypothesis

In testing the Null H_0 and Alternative Hypothesis H_1 the hypothesis will be tested at 5% level of significance. The null hypothesis is to be rejected if the probability at which the t-value is significant is less than the chosen level of significant, otherwise, the alternative hypothesis will be accepted.

4.0 Data Presentation

Graph 4.1: shows the trend analysis of the various observations under investigation from 1981-2018 in Nigeria from appendix 1.

Source: Author’s computation 2021 (Eview 9)

The trend analysis from the graphs above shows that Gross fixed capital formation has gradually reduced from 1981-2017 however there is a spike in 2018 from N14.716B in 2017 to N19.018B. Fire insurance claims, General accident claims and motor vehicle claims all had similar growth variations within the period of investigation with motor vehicle making the highest claims settlement of N25,935.58B in 2013 amongst the independent variables.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 4:1 Summary of Descriptive Results for Gross fixed capital formation, Fire insurance claims, General accident claims and motor vehicle claims in Nigeria from 1981-2018.

	GFCF	FIRE_CLAIMS	ACCIDENT_CLAIMS	MOTOR__CLAIMS
Mean	36.22045	4904.907	3390.849	6071.709
Median	35.31550	1134.340	627.5300	1814.455
Maximum	89.38600	23636.03	15239.75	25935.58
Minimum	14.16900	0.010000	3.660000	44.65000
Std. Dev.	19.57231	7212.121	4422.893	7800.579
Skewness	0.987216	1.402401	1.058677	1.025101
Kurtosis	3.620849	3.619867	2.779646	2.606751
Jarque-Bera	6.782737	13.06432	7.175257	6.900123
Probability	0.033663	0.001456	0.027664	0.031744
Sum	1376.377	186386.5	128852.3	230725.0
Sum Sq. Dev.	14173.78	1.92E+09	7.24E+08	2.25E+09
Observations	38	38	38	38

Source: Author’s computation 2021 (Eview 9)

Gross fixed capital formation has a Median of 35.31550 and mean value of 36.22045 with minimum and maximum values of 14.16900 and 89.38600. The degree of the distribution of Gross fixed capital formation is unskewed with a value of 0.987216. Gross fixed capital formation has a flat curve being Platykurtic with a Kurtosis value of 3.620849 which indicates lower values than the sample mean of 36.22045. Fire insurance claims, General accident claims and motor vehicle claims in Nigeria from 1981-2018 are positively skewed with right-tail distributions of 1.402401, 1.058677, 1.025101 respectively. The kurtosis values of the independent variables also indicate lower values than the sample mean hence being Platykurtic.

Data Analysis**Table 4.2: Estimated Regression Result**

Dependent Variable: GFCF

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/21/21 Time: 10:39

Sample: 1981 2018

Included observations: 38

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	47.17655	2.933571	16.08161	0.0000
FIRE_CLAIMS	-0.000276	0.000703	-0.392315	0.6973
ACCIDENT_CLAIMS	-0.000388	0.001822	-0.213181	0.8325
MOTOR_CLAIMS	-0.001365	0.001101	-1.238988	0.2238
R-squared	0.518526	Mean dependent var		36.22045
Adjusted R-squared	0.476043	S.D. dependent var		19.57231
S.E. of regression	14.16738	Akaike info criterion		8.239062
Sum squared resid	6824.300	Schwarz criterion		8.411440
Log likelihood	-152.5422	Hannan-Quinn criter.		8.300393
F-statistic	12.20552	Durbin-Watson stat		0.493897
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000014			

Source: Author's computation 2021 (Eview 9)

From table 4.2 above the coefficient of correlation indicates that -0.000276 decrease in fire insurance claims settlement will lead to a corresponding change in Gross fixed capital formation. -0.000388 decrease in general accident claims settlement will lead to corresponding variations in Gross fixed capital formation and -0.001365 decrease in motor vehicle claims settlement will also lead to a corresponding change in Gross fixed capital formation.

The coefficient of determination shows the influence of Fire insurance claims, General accident claims and motor vehicle claims on Gross fixed capital formation at 52% as indicated by the R-squared meaning a fair portion of changes in Gross fixed capital formation is caused by the independent variables, hence 48% is explained by the error term. The negative coefficients of fire, general accidents and motor vehicles insurance claims indicate a negative impact on Gross fixed capital formation in Nigeria from 1981-2018. The adjusted R-square of 48% does not show a favourable goodness of fit of the result as it falls below average of 50%. However the Probability (F-statistic) of 0.000014 indicates that the investigation is statistically significant.

Test of hypotheses:**Hypothesis one**

Since the probability value 0.6973 (sig) is greater than 0.05, we will accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hence, fire insurance claims had an insignificant impact on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria from 1981-2018.

Hypothesis two

Since the probability value 0.8325 (sig) is greater than 0.05, we will accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hence, General accident insurance claims also had a non-significant impact Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria from 1981-2018.

Hypothesis three

Since the probability value 0.2238 (sig) is greater than 0.05, we will accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hence, motor vehicle insurance claims has not contributed the growth of Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria from 1981-2018.

Discussion of results

From estimated regression result above the coefficient of correlation indicates that -0.000276 decrease in fire insurance claims settlement will lead to a corresponding change in Gross fixed capital formation. - 0.000388 decrease in general accident claims settlement will lead to corresponding variations in Gross fixed capital formation and -0.001365 decrease in motor vehicle claims settlement will also lead to a corresponding change in Gross fixed capital formation.

The influence of Fire insurance claims, General accident claims and motor vehicle claims on Gross fixed capital formation at 52% as indicated by the R-squared meaning a fair portion of changes in Gross fixed capital formation is caused by the independent variables, hence 48% is explained by the error term. The negative coefficients of fire, general accidents and motor vehicles insurance claims indicate a negative impact on Gross fixed capital formation in Nigeria from 1981-2018. The adjusted R-square of 48% does not show a favourable goodness of fit of the result as it falls below average of 50%. However the Probability (F-statistic) of 0.000014 indicates that the investigation is statistically significant.

Fire insurance claims had a negative (-0.000276) insignificant (0.6973) impact on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria from 1981-2018.

General accident insurance claims also had a negative (-0.000388) non-significant (0.8325) impact on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria from 1981-2018.

Motor vehicle insurance claims also revealed a negative (-0.001365) insignificant (0.2238) effect on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria from 1981-2018.

The result is however contrary to the findings of Lezaasi and Tamunonimim (2012) who tried at investigating the relationship between insurance risk management denoted by claims payment and Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) in Nigeria. The study engaged the ordinary least square, Johansen co-integration, Granger causality, impulse response and variance decomposition procedures on annual rate of change in Nigerian, using data from 1980 to 2011. The outcomes show that claims paid on Accident, Fire, Motor vehicle and Employers' Liability insurance policies impacted growth in GFCF. It was instituted that unidirectional causation flow happens from GFCF to indemnifications made on Fire and Marine insurance policies. This infers that development in the procurement of new productive capital stocks could prompt up insurance patronage particularly in fire and marine insurance. The variance decomposition analysis of GFCF to innovations originating from indemnifications on fire and motor vehicle insurance policies show positive and reliable expansionary effects over a decade projection period into the future; consequently, as insurance indemnifications rises, the trend of indemnification pressures initiates the economy to upturn its capital formation in broad terms.

Conclusion

Haven investigated explicitly the Impact of Non-Life Insurance Claims (proxy: fire, general accidents and motor vehicle insurance claims) on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria from 1981-2019, the findings from the study conclude that Non-Life Insurance Claims had a negative and insignificant effect on Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria. However the result is not in conformity with Lezaasi and Tamunonimim (2012) haven studied the relationship between insurance risk management represented by claims payment and Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) in Nigeria revealing a positive influence.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. The insurance sector should be prompt in claims settlement without unnecessary disputes in order to boost the confidence of the various investment outlets in the country in purchasing insurance coverage.
2. Government should ensure the compliance of compulsory insurance in order for the insurance industry to be effective in contributing to Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Amorose, R.C. (2011). Driving operational excellence in claims management. USA: *Deloitte Development*.
- Aon Risk Solutions (2013). (*Insurance and claims manual*. Sydney: Aon Risk Services Australia Limited.
- Asokere, A.S, &Nwankwo, S.I. (2010). Essential of insurance: A modern approach (1stedn.).Lagos: *Fevas Publishing*.
- Brennan, P. (2012). A comprehensive survey method for overcoming the class imbalance problem in fraud detection. A dissertation submitted for the Degree of M.Sc in computing of institute of Technology, Blanchard town. Dublin, Ireland.
- Capgemini (2011). Claims system migration and enhancement cuts costs by \$ 15 million and improves customer relationship. USA: *Computer Sciences Corporation*.
- Capgemini (2011). Claims transformation Enhancing brand value by delivery on customer commitments capturing efficiency gains, and optimizing indemnity expenditure.
- Capgemini (2011). Capturing operational efficiency and sustainable value through claims. Retrieved from <http://www.capgemini.com/claims>.
- Capgemini and Efma (2011). World insurance report: insurers need to transform claims to meet their brand promise to customers while driving results. Retrieved February, 23 from <http://www.capgemini.com/wir11>.
- Chartered Global Management Accountant (2012). Fraud risk management: CGMA Report New York: *Association of International Certified Professional Accountants*.
- Crocker, K. & Tennyson, S. (2002). Insurance fraud and optimal claims settlement strategies. *Journal of law and Economics*, 45 (2) ,469-507.
- Daniel Francois MEYER (2019) A causality analysis of the relationships between gross fixed capital formation, economic growth and employment in South Africa. *StudiaUniversitatisBabeş-BolyaiOeconomica* Volume 64, Issue 1, 2019, Pp. 33-44
- Ehiogu, Chizoba P. &Duruechi, H. Anthony(2021) Inflation and Nonlife Insurance business in Nigeria: (An Impact Analysis 1996 – 2018). *UNILAG Journal of Business*. Vol 7 No 1
- Esri (2012). GIS for the insurance claims process: five steps for an effective workflow. *California:Esri Whitepaper*.
- Eze O.R and Okoye V, (2013). Anaysis of insurance practices and economic growth in Nigeria: using co-integration test and error correction model: *Global Advanced Research Journal of Management and Business Studies*. 2(1), 063-070.
- Goel, C. (2013). Insurance claims management: improving staff capacity using BPM. London:

Cognizant Business Consulting.

- IBM (2011). Three ways to improve claims management with business analytics. USA: *IBM Corporation*.
- IBM (2012). Insurance claims fraud assessment: Reducing loss costs by combating insurance claims fraud. USA: *IBM Corporation*.
- Insurance Europe (2013). The impact of insurance fraud. Brussels: *Insurance Europe aisbl*.
- Kanu, S. I. & Ozurumba, B. A. (2014) Capital formation and economic growth in Nigeria. *Global Journals Inc. (USA) Online ISSN: 2249-460x & Print ISSN: 0975-587X*
- Lee, h. & padian, (2013). Examine the relationship between life insurance premiums and growth: *economic journal and research*, 2(3): 123-134
- Ojikutu, R.K., Yusuf, T.O., & Obalola, M.A. (2011). Attitude and perception about insurance fraud in Lagos State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 57 (4), 615-625.
- Owojori, A. A., Akintoye I. R., & Adidu, F. A. (2011). The challenge of risk management in Nigerian banks in the post consolidation era. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 13(2).p. 144.
- SAS (2012).Combating insurance claims fraud: How to recognize and reduce opportunistic and organized claims fraud. USA: *SAS Institute Inc*.
- Shittu A.I. (2012). Financial intermediation and economic growth in Nigeria: *British journal of art and social sciences*, 4(2): 164-179.
- Tajudeen (2014). The effect of claims cost on insurance profitability in Nigeria. *International review of management and business research* 2(3): 34-68.
- Usman OA (2009). Scale Economies and Performance Evaluation of Insurance Market in Nigeria. *Soc. Sci. Medwell Journal*, 4(1):1-11
- Yusuf, T.O. & Ajemunigbohun, S.S. (2015). Effectiveness, efficiency and promptness of claims handling process in the Nigerian Insurance industry. *European Journal of Business and Economics*,10 (2), 6-10.
- Yusuf, T.O. (2010). Brokers and the control of post contractual opportunism in the Nigerian Insurance market. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 17 (2), 223-239.
- Yusuf, T.O. & Ajemunigbohun, S.S. (2015). Effectiveness, efficiency and promptness of claims handling process in the Nigerian Insurance industry. *European Journal of Business and Economics*,10 (2), 6-10.
- Yusuf, T.O., & Abass, O.A. (2013). Investigating the roles of claims manager in claims handling process in the Nigeria Insurance Industry. *Journal of Business and Finance*,1 (2), 69-74.
- Yusuf, T.O., & Dansu, F.S. (2014). Effect of claim cost on insurers' profitability in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Commerce*, 3 (10), 1-20.

Appendix 1: Shows the Gross fixed capital formation, Fire insurance claims, General accident claims and motor vehicle claims in Nigeria from 1981-2018.

YEAR	GFCF (N'M)	Fire (N'M)	Accident (N'M)	Motor (N'M)
1981	89.386	6.27	3.66	46.95
1982	85.941	6.78	5.48	44.65
1983	75.757	6.03	5.59	55.64
1984	58.956	5.33	6.28	53.71
1985	46.395	-0.01	6.41	54.15
1986	54.948	6.88	5.88	54.22
1987	50.05	16.42	8.37	55.64
1988	43.755	16.53	11.24	67.83
1989	52.487	46.95	28.82	73.11
1990	53.122	61.51	30.80	114.49
1991	48.4	80.42	42.78	164.84
1992	43.774	114.80	66.77	267.44
1993	44.476	1,161.03	448.73	607.33
1994	42.068	267.40	193.83	605.16
1995	37.206	194.53	207.14	563.64
1996	36.582	342.70	276.88	712.33
1997	38.422	349.11	376.62	780.89
1998	40.553	388.13	396.75	832.87
1999	38.278	890.97	1,649.04	1,824.67
2000	34.049	1,107.65	806.33	1,804.24
2001	30.038	1,164.66	957.82	2,315.94
2002	26.769	1,857.87	109.29	2,818.65
2003	28.374	1,681.74	2,266.79	3,040.17

2004	26.063	2,724.43	2,852.92	3,476.24
2005	24.966	2,766.71	3,138.16	3,733.39
2006	26.166	6,662.98	15,239.75	20,734.98
2007	20.18	1,793.39	3,829.06	6,196.12
2008	18.86	6,076.60	4,467.50	9,935.50
2009	21.115	15,124.74	6,567.45	13,040.29
2010	16.815	7,794.06	6,444.45	13,219.03
2011	15.676	8,520.45	6,820.64	13,205.62
2012	14.211	13,398.70	10,387.18	16,080.83
2013	14.169	11,815.14	9,024.90	25,935.58
2014	15.084	15,347.46	10,050.14	14,512.03
2015	14.827	17,676.02	10,550.36	17,254.58
2016	14.725	22,927.54	10,397.97	18,137.15
2017	14.716	23,636.03	9,994.79	20,849.42
2018	19.018	20,348.49	11,175.70	17,455.64

Source: World Bank National Accounts Data, OECD National Account Data Files, CBN Statistical Bulletin and NAICOM market statistics 2019.

EMPLOYEES' ATTITUDE AND ORGANISATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED PUBLIC SECTOR ESTABLISHMENTS IN IBADAN, OYO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Research Purpose: *This study examined the effect of employees' attitudes on organisational performance in selected Public Sector Establishments in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The study reviewed relevant theoretical and empirical literature and is anchored on self-determination theory.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The study adopted a descriptive survey research design of the ex-post facto type. A sample size of 342 was arrived at using Taro Yamane (1967) model. It was selected from 2345 staff members of the six purposively selected state ministries in Oyo state which is the study population, using stratified random sampling. Questionnaires were administered, but only 318 questionnaires were considered usable, representing a 93.00% response rate. A descriptive and regression analysis with the aid of SPSS was used to analyse the relationship between employees' attitude and organisational performance.*

Findings: *The findings indicate that there exists a significant relationship between employees' attitude and organisational performance ($r = 0.517$; $p < 0.05$). This study concludes that fostering positive employees' attitudes would improve employees' productivity and eventually improve organisational performance.*

Originality/Value Added: *The study recommends that management should develop diverse but appropriate strategies to create a conducive work environment that can stimulate employees' ability to develop, engage, and be empowered in their jobs.*

Keywords: Civil service, Employees' attitude, Management, Organisational performance, and Public sector establishments

Introduction

Organisational performance involves analysing how a company is doing concerning its goals and objectives. It is the actual results or output of an organisation as measured against its intended outputs (Ondoro, 2015). Organisations could be classified into either the private or public sector. Public sector establishments are typically service-oriented and not competing with other institutions for profit. Their primary purpose is the efficient and effective provision of public services rather than making a profit. As such, the measure of organisational performance for public sector establishments is the extent that they have achieved set goals, aims, and objectives; how much their outputs have effectively and efficiently contributed to policy objectives.

Public sector establishments are characterized with high level of formalization, many hierarchical structures, and red-tapism. These characteristics are significant sources of work delays, unethical practices, and corruption in these establishments as people want to expedite their work by using different ways, legal or illegal (Din, Khan, Rehman & Zainab, 2011). Therefore, organisational performance can often be influenced by a multiplicity of personal, managerial, technological, environmental, and structural factors, including employee attitudes (Mukolwe, Korir, Buyeke, Wafula & Musyoki, 2015). Employees' attitudes can be described as employees' feelings toward their employer, co-workers, position, and job in the organisation, and could be either positive or negative. It is a fundamental factor for determining and attaining efficiency, effectiveness and customer satisfaction in an Organisation (Kwizera, et al 2019).

Employees have attitudes or viewpoints about several aspects of their jobs, their careers, and their organisation. Attitude describes an employee's feelings toward his employer, co-workers, job, and position within the organisation. It is a psychological action expressed through evaluation of a particular entity, with some degree of disfavour or favour. In organisational settings, attitudes are essential for the achievement of goals and objectives. Employees' behaviour at their workplaces often largely depends on their feelings about being there. Employees' attitude basically involves characteristics such as having an interest in the job, having a positive, cheerful disposition, working without supervision, and willingness to contribute (Chatterjee & Kulakli, 2015).

Employees' work-related attitudes can directly affect the atmosphere and significantly impact a workplace, including productivity levels and morale. It is essentially either negative or positive, depending on the degree of like or dislike for the matter in question. A positive attitude refers to having a positive mind-set and thinking about the greater good, irrespective of the situation on ground³⁴. Positive attitudes are excellent and contagious. Everyone feels like teammates, effort is collective, and everyone's ideas are valued and welcomed. A positive attitude gives a feeling that everything is achievable. Colleagues support each other and work in tandem. Positive employees' attitudes lead to numerous other positive outcomes, such as improved morale, willingness to be creative and attempt new things, willingness to share ideas and information, ability to overcome challenges, a greater probability of teamwork and collaboration, better customer service, low employees' turnover and increased productivity.

Negative attitudes, however, are counter-productive and would always have a profound adverse impact on an organisation's morale. These include dull performance, unwillingness to be a team player or collaborate, be creative and attempt new things, reduced energy levels, dismal outlook, depressed feelings, reduced quality of job output, low customer engagement, and difficulty overcoming obstacles. A negative attitude breeds contempt and creates a situation of low motivation to make an effort to achieve success, distrusts among teammates, and employees merely struggle to complete their work-hours rather than flourish, take the initiative, and succeed. All these will drag down the morale of co-workers and create stress for fellow workers (Ilahi & Masood, 2016).

Work-related attitudes include job satisfaction, job involvement, and employee commitment. Job satisfaction basically is the extent to which an individual is comfortable and pleased with their job. It is the pleasant emotional state arising from evaluating one's job or job experiences; It is the positive (or negative) evaluative judgment an employee makes about their jobs or its situation (Mahdi, Sakat, Zin, Nor & Naim, 2012). It is the extent to which employees gain enjoyment from their efforts at the workplace. According to Ndulue and Chinonso (2016), it has two major components - intrinsic (that is, job satisfaction on features associated with the job itself) and extrinsic job (that is, job satisfaction on various features associated with the job environment).

Job involvement, on the other hand, is the measure of how much employees are psychologically engaged in their daily work. It is the extent that a person psychologically identifies himself with his job, participates actively, and considers his performance level significant to self-worth (Singh & Gupta, 2015). Job-involved employees usually believe in work ethics; they find work meaningful and challenging; they are willing to work long hours. They complete given tasks, work at complex tasks employing various skills, and attempt to be high performers (Pardeep & Kumar, 2017).

In this competitive world, the global landscape is changing; the current dynamics of the market, economic situations, and competition make companies radically change how business is being done. Organisations are restructuring to operate better; businesses are moving to explore new markets. Every organisation strives to achieve its competitive advantage by establishing a decent workplace environment so that human resources can improve jobs and organisational performances through new innovative ideas. Organisations must continually change to remain ahead of others, remain profitable, and relevant. The extent to which an organisation has been able to deliver benefits of businesses linked to the substantial portfolio investments depends

primarily on its ability to manage the process of organisational change and carry along its employees with strategic initiatives in such a way to reflect that every employee is working together towards a common objective. The extent that an organisation can engage its employees, build an on-going and sound capacity to gain commitment of and engage employees optimally, to ensure profitable and timely delivery of service is the extent that the organisation is successful, would gain competitive advantage and be better than its competitions.

Due to the permanent nature of employees' attitudes in organisations, those that will be successful and have perform optimally will be those that constantly develop the appropriate methods of improving their employees' attitude to achieve set standards and goals.

After reviewing several past articles on employees' attitudes, it was discovered that previous studies have been carried out, mainly in the private sectors(Aqeela&Ramakrishnan, 2018). These studies generally show that positive employees' attitudes contribute to improved organisational performance and primarily recommend that organisations should effectively manage employees towards having positive attitudes so as to achieve optimal organisational performance. There should be clearly defined task allocation, which would lead to job satisfaction and commitment, in order to foster positive employees' attitude(Adewole, Ogunyemi, &Otapo, 2019). To the best knowledge of the researcher, there appear to be no previous study to have specifically linked employees' attitudes to organisation performance in the public sector establishments. It is against this backdrop, therefore, this current study examined employees' attitudes, and organisational performance in the public sector establishment. The study proposed recommendations on managing employees' attitudes which would foster optimal organisational performance in the selected public sector establishments in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Thus, this research question emerged to assist in guiding this study:To what extent do employees' work-related attitudes, such as (job satisfaction, job involvement, and employees' commitment) affect organisational performance in selected public sector establishments in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria?

Similarly, the study assessed the extent to which employees' work-related attitudes such as (job satisfaction, job involvement, and employee commitment) affect organisational performance in selected public sector establishments in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Therefore, this study tested the null hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between employees' work-related attitudes such as (job satisfaction, job involvement, and employee commitment) and organisational performance in selected public sector establishments in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Employees' Attitude

An attitude is a psychological state of mind. It refers to our opinions, beliefs, and feelings about aspects of our environment. It is the way a person thinks about situations, and it ultimately determines a person's behaviour. Attitude has three components: cognitive components, affective or emotional components, and behavioural components. The cognitive involves knowledge or information received, while the affective involves the person's emotions or feelings, which is psychological. The behavioural component describes how attitude influences the way we behave or act. These components are hugely different from one another, and they build upon each other to form our attitudes and affect the way we relate with the world.

People's attitudes are shaped by their experiences; upbringing could have been acquired from other persons and can change with circumstances and needs. Attitude has been referred to as a little element that makes a great difference(Nadeem, 2021). The choices people make are most times determined by their attitude towards people, things, places, or situations. Attitudes are

important in organisational settings for the achievement of goals and objectives. Behaviours at workplaces are often dependent on the way employees feel about being there.

Employees' attitudes are essentially either positive or negative.

Positive Attitude: Refers to having a positive mind-set and thinking about the greater good irrespective of what the situation is. People with good attitudes towards work and co-workers are active and productive; they do what they can to positively influence those around them by improving their mood. They are sure of their personal strengths and weaknesses, and they stay resilient. Individuals exhibiting positive attitudes do always focus on the good side in people, situations, or events instead of the wrong or negative side. They do not take failure or mistake as an insurmountable problem but as a chance to improve and try again. They are upward-looking in life and learn from mistakes. They often display confidence, contentment, cheerfulness, optimism, determination, happiness, reliability, flexibility, tolerance, willingness to adapt, humility, diligence, and a deep sense of responsibility.

Negative Attitude: This is the contradiction of having a positive, optimistic mind-set. Employees exhibiting this negative attitude ignore good sides in people and life; and concentrate on the wrong sides in people, events, or situations. They often handle challenging situations by avoiding them; they tend to shift blames of their failure on other people and mostly grumble about changes rather than adapt (Yashasvi, 2019). A negative attitude prevents people from looking at anything in life with hope or happiness. Employees with negative attitudes towards work would likewise adversely affect others around them by behaving in a manner that would reduce effectiveness and efficiency. People may have experienced terrible situations that make them develop negative attitudes towards life, and this may have an effect on their physical and mental well-being. Symptoms such as anger, self-doubt, frustration, pessimism, hatred, resentment, inferiority complex, and jealousy would be displayed by them.

Employees can have either a negative or positive attitude about different, particular tasks, products, services, management, co-workers, or the organisation itself. Employees with positive attitudes often outshine even when not the best, most talented, and most skilled due to their perspectives, dedication, and commitment leading to their putting in high levels of determination. In contrast, the person that is the most talented and most skilled employee with a negative attitude would underperform severely. A saying goes that "positive attitude gives people power over circumstances instead of circumstances having power over people" (Meyer, 2021). Positive attitudes in employees ensure workdays are increasingly satisfying. Tasks are more competently performed without grudges or complaints. Negative attitudes may however, result in work apathy, a high tendency to agitate over minor problems, low performances, and low productivity. It should be eliminated and well-handled at all costs.

Work-Related Attitudes

Work-related attitudes are broken down into job satisfaction, job involvement, and employee commitment. Job Satisfaction is the pleasurable emotional state of employees, resulting from their job appraisals or job experiences. It could better still be described as the evaluative judgment one makes about one's job and/or job situations, which could be positive or negative (Mahdi, Nor, Zin, Sakat, & Naim, 2012). It is the extent to which employees gain enjoyment from their efforts at workplaces (Ndulue & Chinonso, 2016). In short, job satisfaction describes the feelings and attitudes people have regarding their job. It can also be described as the degree to which an employee has positive emotions towards his/her job role. It will be adjudged to be low if the job does not fulfill the employee's psychological or physiological needs. Employees who have low expectations are more readily satisfied at their jobs than those with high expectations. When expectations are just or exceedingly met by a job, the employee would be satisfied and happy. There is a deep feeling of joy and contentment derived from that positive appraisal of a job and

the clear understanding that the job is playing its part in the continuous achievement of life goals. Job dissatisfaction, meanwhile, refers to the unpleasant feeling which an employee gets when the job reports a negative appraisal and shows as a barrier in achieving set goals. Job satisfaction plays a vital role in both personal growth and performance in an organisation. It, therefore, can be referred to as probably the most researched variable of employees' attitudes in the literature of industrial and organisational psychology, social psychology, and organisational behaviour (Redmond, 2016).

A considerable literature on organisational behaviour has highlighted that a high percentage of job satisfaction shall help organisations to keep their experienced, trained, and competent employees enhance levels of motivation among employees, create loyalty, commitment, and confidence to the organisation, increase employee productivity, and decrease turnover and absenteeism (Ismail & Razak, 2016). Thus, this situation would result in enhanced organisational effectiveness and efficiency. A review of current literature relating to job satisfaction reveals that it has two major dimensions, namely intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction. Intrinsic job satisfaction refers to employees' satisfaction with internal job factors, which include recognition, opportunity to use and develop human capacities, achievements, responsibility, and career advancement. If employees are satisfied with these intrinsic job factors, they would be motivated to execute their jobs efficiently and effectively. If, however, employees are not satisfied with these intrinsic job factors, it may cause a decrease in job performances.

Extrinsic job satisfaction refers to employees' satisfaction with external job factors and work conditions such as compensation, interpersonal relations, supervision, company policy, safe and healthy, career growth and security, social integration, and status. If an employee is satisfied and happy with these job elements, it will lead to increased enthusiasm. If, however, the employee is not satisfied, it may result in lower motivation and work performance.

Factors that influence employee's job satisfaction include pay, benefits, the perceived fairness of the promotion system within a company, the quality of the working conditions, leadership and social relationships, organisational culture, job security, low stress, and the job itself.

Job Involvement refers to how committed, engaged, and involved employees are at their specific job. It has been defined as the extent to which an individual psychologically identifies himself with his job. This implies the extent that one's job is central to the person's identity, the extent to which an individual actively contributes and believes that his performance level is essential to his self-worth (Gupta, 2015). Job involvement is an employee's job-related significant behaviour. Employees with high levels of job involvement would sincerely care about, strongly align or identify with their jobs. Employees with a low level of job involvement may feel alienated, perceiving that their job does not have a purpose; and that they are of less importance to the organisation. They simply would not recognize the connection between their work and their aspirations in life. This implies that employee that is fully job-involved would perceive the job as an essential part of their self-concept (Dehal & Kumar, 2017).

Although its construct seems somewhat similar to organisational commitment as both are related to employee's identification with work experience, job involvement, however, differs from organisational commitment. Job involvement is particularly related to identifying with employees' assigned work activities, while organisational commitment is related to employees' sense of loyalty to the organisation itself. As such, there could be situations where an employee is highly job-involved but not entirely committed to the organisation and vice versa. The degree of job engagement or involvement is determined firstly, by personal characteristics like employee's age, education, sex, tenure, needs, values, and work ethics; Secondly, by the environment, that is, the organisational setting; and thirdly, characteristics of the job such as task autonomy, task significance, task identity, skill variety, and feedback and supervisory behaviours.

Employees become more job-involved as they feel the potentials for the satisfaction of important psychological needs, such as growth, recognition, achievement, and security. Job involvement

promotes employees' work performances by motivating employees to put in more outstanding efforts and use critical thinking and creativity to work intelligently and solve problems. Job-involved employees would most likely believe in work ethic; they will find work more meaningful, enjoyable, and challenging, be willing to carry out complex tasks using various skills, be able to complete tasks, be willing to work for long hours, and attempt to be high performers (Dehal & Kumar, 2017).

Job-involved employees are willing and ready to carry out any other tasks in general and are committed to career advancement and achievement. They are typically highly satisfied in their jobs, mostly intrinsically. This job satisfaction dominates and influences behaviours even when problems and conflicts arise, for example, where the supervisor is inconsiderate, uncommunicative, or autocratic. Job-involved employees have quite strong affective ties to the organisation and, as such, they are seldom tardy or absent; they are less likely to resign and leave their jobs. Job involvement constitutes an essential key to motivation, individual effort, satisfaction, performance, and organisational performance.

Employee commitment is a crucial work attitude that has been described as a psychological state that binds the individual employee to the organisation. It is the strength of employees' identification and involvement in their workplace. Employee commitment is an attitude reflecting an employee's loyalty to the organisation. It was described using three distinct components, as a condition where an employee has a strong belief in and acceptance of an organisation's goals; high motivation and willingness to exert considerable effort on behalf of the organisation; and, strong desire to maintain membership in the organisation (Wainwright, 2019). *It is the connection employees have with their organisation. Notably, committed employees would generally have an affectionate connection with the organisation; they will believe that they fit in and know the organisation inside out, its purpose, challenges, and goals.*

Employee commitment must be regarded as a business necessity. Committed employees give the organisation crucial competitive advantages, lower employee turnover, and higher productivity. Employee commitment depends on several factors, including the level of autonomy involved in the execution of jobs, the variety or types of work, the responsibility level linked to the job, and the social relationship quality at work. Other essential factors are the remuneration and reward, the available promotion opportunities, and the general career advancement opportunities in the organisation. At an individual level, those who are more committed to the organisation *tend to be more focused and determined in their work. They are more proactive in offering their services or support and more relatively highly productive. They have higher job satisfaction, higher levels of motivation, and lower stress levels. They also perform better and manifest less job-searching tendencies.*

In summary, an organisation can only function at an optimum level with committed employees. Organisational commitment is nowadays seen as a crucial part of investigating the health of organisations. Organisations cannot, in the present-day competitive environment, perform at optimal levels except their employees are committed to the organisational goals, and they work together as effective teams. Highly motivated, committed employees put in their time and energy to the achievement of organisational goals. A committed employee is the one who stays with the organisation even during turbulent times, regularly does his assigned works, protects organisational properties, and aligns with the organisational objectives.

Organisational Performance

Organisational performance is described as an organisation's ability to utilize its acquired scarce resources and valuables in the pursuit of its operational objectives and goals (Robbins, 2009). It is the single most vital determinant of the accomplishment of a business; the capability of an organisation to achieve organisational goals effectively and efficiently. Public sector establishments have their peculiarity; they are process or service-oriented and not result-oriented.

As such, the measure of their organisational performance is the extent that they have achieved set goals, aims, and objectives; how much their outputs have effectively and efficiently contributed to policy objectives (Jones & George, 2006).

The Balanced Scorecard, developed by Kaplan and Norton, has been identified as the appropriate performance measurement method (Sheeran & Webb, 2016). The balanced scorecard (BSC) converts the organisation's mission and strategy into a comprehensive set of performance tools and creates a strategic measurement system. It has four core perspectives:

- a. Financial objectives: How will we look like to our employees?
- b. Perspective of users: How do we look to our customers?
- c. Internal processes: Which internal processes must be improved?
- d. Learning and growth: How can the organisation learn and improve? (StevTon, 2016)

The balanced scorecard method unites the perspectives of these four perspectives, and other different groups of data of performance results so that the performance can be more comprehensively analysed and measured.

Theoretical Framework

Self-Determination Theory (SDT)

Self-determination theory is developed from the works of psychologists, Edward Deci and Richard Ryan (1985). They developed the Self-determination theory (SDT), which posited that two main types of motivation exist: intrinsic and extrinsic, and both are powerful in determining who we are and how we behave. That, people, are driven by a need to grow and gain fulfilment; they are motivated to grow and change by three innate and universal psychological needs: Autonomy (the extent to which an action carried out by an individual comes from their own interests), competence (the sense of ability and of executing a task to a certain level), and relatedness with others (the desire to feel connected or experience a feeling of belonging and attachment to other people)²¹⁸. This indicates that people can become self-determined and achieve psychological growth when these three psychological needs are fulfilled.

Two key assumptions of the SDT theory according to Cherry (n,d) are:

- a. **Need for Growth Drives Behaviour:** This is the belief that people are actively geared towards development and growth. That, gaining expertise over challenges and having new experiences are crucial for creating a consistent sense of self.
- b. **Autonomous Intrinsic Motivation is Crucial:** Usually, people are motivated by external rewards, like prizes, money, and commendations, which are extrinsic motivations. SDT, however, focuses mainly on internal, intrinsic sources of motivation, which for example, include a need to gain independence or knowledge.

The notion of intrinsic motivation plays an essential role in SDT. Intrinsic motivation comes from within. It refers to behaviour that is driven by internal rewards. It is the pleasurable feelings of enjoyment or interest which at the same time accompany and are inextricably tied to doing an activity. When intrinsically motivated, individuals will engage in an activity solely because it is enjoyable and get personal satisfaction from it (Nadeem, 2021). For example, a person high in self-determination, who fails to complete an important project at work will admit their fault, feel bad, and strive to fix the problem, take action to correct the mistake.

In contrast, a person low in self-determination might blame others, make excuses, and move on to work on something else. They, most importantly, will not feel motivated to try more, fix the mistake, and attempt the activity again. Instead, they might feel helpless about the situation and accept quickly that nothing they can do will have any real effect. Self-determined people who feel that they positively affect work tend to feel more engaged and motivated. They exhibit positive attitudes. Satisfaction of the salient needs is linked to positive employees' attitudes. The gap

between employees' needs and what employees get from their job is negatively correlated with positive employees' attitudes.

Self-determination theory (SDT) remains invaluable in understanding employees' attitudes, job satisfaction, and optimizing work performance. The theory can help employers better understand how best to develop and engage their employees and help individuals understand how they can adopt the best attitude to be professionally successful. It offers a roadmap for building work-lives and organisational cultures that enable both individuals and organisations to flourish (Mahdi, Nor, Zin, Sakat, & Naim, 2012). In conclusion, Self-Determination Theory evaluates the three basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness as distinctive and essential for ongoing human internalization, psychological growth, and well-being (Ndulue & Chinonso, 2016). It addresses the central questions of why people do what they do and the costs and benefits of various ways of socially regulating or promoting good behaviour.

Empirical Review

Lebowitz (2015) studied "The effect of Employee Work-Related Attitudes on Employee Job Performance: A Study of Tertiary and Vocational Education Sector in Sri Lanka". The study was hypothetically tested, the type was a correlational study, and conducted in a non-contrived setting. It was a cross-sectional study, and the unit of analysis was individual. Data was collected from the employees working in the Tertiary and Vocational Education Sector in Sri Lanka. A questionnaire was designed and used for data collection. Findings revealed that 26.7% of the job performance variance was significantly analysed by the three independent variables. It was then concluded that there is a significant effect of employee-related work attitudes on employees' job performance of the vocational and tertiary education of government sector in Sri Lanka.

Ahmed and Osunsan (2020) also studied "Employee attitude and customer satisfaction in selected hotels," used a cross sectional survey design to examine the effect of employees' attitudes on customers satisfaction in selected hotels in Kampala, Uganda. With simple random sampling, 179 hotel employees were selected for the study. The findings showed that employees' attitude was generally poor ((mean = 1.09), while customer satisfaction was at moderate (mean = 1.89) levels. The study also showed a significant positive relationship between employees' attitudes and customer satisfaction among the selected hotel employees ($R^2=0.558$, $P<0.05$). It was concluded that employees' attitude was a suitable predictor of customer satisfaction in the selected hotels. The recommendation was given then was that hotel owners and management should prioritize employees' engagement, development, and empowerment to enable them to develop more positive attitudes towards their job.

Scuderi (2021) did a conceptual study titled "Role on Employees' Attitude in Workplace". The study was conducted to assess the behavioural attitude of individuals in the workplace, especially focused on job involvement, job satisfaction, and organisational commitment. It was also conducted to predict the employees' workplace behaviour for its importance today. The researcher found a significant relationship between job satisfaction, job involvement, and organisational commitment. He posited that these are the prime determinants of employees' workplace behaviours.

Reddy (2021) studied "Perception and Attitude of Employees of Telecommunication Sector towards the Organisation". The sample size of 150 was taken through a stratified random sampling method from three prominent telecommunication companies (STC, Zain, and Mobily) of Jazan, KSA. The analysis was carried out with averages, percentages, weighted scores, and ranking methods. The results indicated that individual attitudes do matter, and they may be related to job satisfaction and their performance which can indirectly affect the organisation. It was concluded that employees can enhance skills for better future prospects if their work-related problems are solved timely and get enough respect and recognition in the organisation.

Heathfield (2021) researched on the organisational performance concerning employee attitude and behaviour in the IT industry. The sample in the study was 310 IT employees from different IT companies in Bangalore comprising both males and females. The judgment sampling method was used. In conclusion, a hypothesis that proposed a positive relationship between employees' attitudes/behaviour and organisational performance was partially supported. The organisational performance measure is positively and significantly related to employees' attitudes and behaviour. A possible explanation for the positive associations found in this study in the relationship between employees' attitudes and profitability is 0.298, sales-related with employee attitude and behaviour is 0.160, and reputation with employees' attitudes and behaviours is 0.254. Secondly, a significant relationship was found between employees' attitudes and behaviours with outcome measures. Employees' attitudes and behaviour is positively related to discretion effort and loyalty 0.141. The overall outcome measure to employees' attitudes and behaviours is 0.148. Thirdly, there is a significant difference between Gender and the Employees' attitudes and behaviours. This context evidenced that organisational performance may influence employees' attitudes, and employees' attitudes may determine how employees behave. The results proposed that the employees' attitudes survey is a handy tool that organisations should use for their performance.

Methodology

The study adopted *ex-postfacto* research design. This study was conducted in Six (6) ministries of the Oyo State Civil Service establishments, namely Ministries, namely: Education and Technology; Finance; Health; Lands, Housing and Survey; Budget and Economic Planning; Local Governments; and Chieftaincy Matters. These ministries were purposively selected for being the core establishments in the civil service and having a larger number of workers. The workers also showed interest in participating in this study. The study population is the entire staff of these ministries, males, and females, across senior and junior cadres who had been in the organisation's employment for more than five years, numbering two thousand, three hundred and forty-five (2345). The sample size calculated using *Taro Yamane (1967) sampling method*.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n = sample size required,
 e = level of significance,

N = population size
 1 = is a constant.

The population size of this research is 2876 people, and we shall use 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, substituting in the formula stated above, the sample size is calculated below:
 $n = N / 1 + N(e)^2$

$$n = \frac{2345}{1 + 2345(0.05)^2} = \frac{2345}{1 + 5.86} = \frac{2345}{6.86} = 342$$

The sample size as calculated above is 342.

The individual sample size is determined using Bourley's (1964) population allocation formula, which is normally stated as: $N_h = \frac{nN_h}{N}$

Where: n_h = sample size per each group;

n = the total sample size; N_h = Number of people in each group; N = total study population

Senior Cadre staff sample size determination: $n_h = 342(814)/2345 = 119$

Junior Cadre sample size determination: $n_h = 342(1531)/2345 = 223$

The stratified random sampling technique was then employed to select 119 respondents from the Senior cadre and 223 respondents from the Junior cadre of the Six (6) Ministries of the Oyo state Civil service establishments, making up the 342 respondents in the study from the population. These respondents for the study were carefully selected to ensure an adequate representation of views and generalizations. The primary criteria for inclusion in the sample were job rank and organisational tenure of not below five (5) years.

Description of Instrument(s)

The study was based on primary and secondary data. The primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire, interviews, discussions, and personal observation.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics of Responses on Employees' Attitudes

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Established trust and confidence	2.77	2.39	High
Healthy and safe work environment	2.75	2.36	High
Communication is effective	2.28	1.91	Moderate
Work-life balance	2.94	2.55	High
Feedbacks & Rewards	2.69	2.31	High
Average Mean score = 2.69	Average SD = 2.30		
Job Satisfaction:			
Like, enjoy & enthusiastic about job	3.03	2.59	Very high
Mutual trust, respect & confidence	3.15	2.76	Very high
Satisfaction with total salary package	1.47	1.07	Moderate
Effective communication	2.28	1.91	Moderate
Training & Development	2.49	2.13	High
Average Mean score = 2.48	Average SD = 2.09		
Job Involvement:			
Discuss organisation outside	2.28	1.90	Moderate
Emotionally involved in job	2.48	2.14	High
Recognition of skills and abilities	2.83	2.43	High
Feeling of personal accomplishment	2.10	1.69	Moderate
Open & comfortable environment	2.65	2.32	High
Average Mean score = 2.47	Average SD = 2.10		
Employee Commitment:			
Work related to goals & priorities	2.25	1.92	Moderate
Job gives personal meaning	2.69	2.31	High
Leaving organisation	2.40	2.05	High
Sense of belongingness	2.85	2.45	High
Identification with Organisation	3.30	2.85	Very high

Average Mean score = 2.70

Average SD = 2.32

Overall Average mean score = 2.58

Overall Average SD = 2.20

Source: *Field Survey (2021)*

Table 1 reveals that job satisfaction and job involvement ranked the lowest with an average mean of 2.48 and 2.47 respectively but are still relatively high on measuring employees’ work attitude. Employees’ commitment ranked highest with a mean of 2.70. This implies that employees like their chosen careers and have some level of a strong bond with the organisation. They are not likely to willingly leave their jobs. Other constructs that measure the generally positive effects of employees’ work attitude, which would affect organisational performance, have an average mean of 2.69. The practice of the policies that these constructs define by organisations would, in the long run, lead to high organisational performance. It can hence be inferred that organisational performance is significantly affected by employees’ attitudes.

The overall average mean of 2.58 confirms that employees’ work attitude is generally high in the selected ministries being observed. This will definitely reflect in the energy, zealotness, and willingness displayed by employees in carrying out their functions and will ultimately lead to better organisational performance.

Test of Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant relationship between employees’ work-related attitudes such as (job satisfaction, job involvement, and employee commitment) and organisational performance in selected public sector establishments in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Using Stepwise Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Squared	Adjusted R Squared	Std Error of the Estimates	R Square Change	F change	df1	Df2	Sig F Change
1	.437	.191	.189	.26385	.194	75.842	1	321	.000
2	.502	.252	.247	.25419	.060	25.850	1	320	.000
3	.517	.267	.260	.25197	.015	6.662	1	319	.000

Source: *Researchers’ output, 2021*

According to the stepwise multiple regression analysis in Table 2, the R-value of the model as per the table above was 0.517. R-squared value of the stepwise regression model was 0.267, indicating that employees’ work-related attitudes accounted for 26.7% of the variance in organisational performance. The F value was 6.662, which was significant at 5% (P=0.010), which suggests that work-related attitudes have significantly explained 26.7% of the variance of organisational performance. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted, as there was a 26.7% impact of employees work-related attitudes on organisational performance, which was significant at 0.010. (0.010).

Going by this multiple regression analysis, employees’ work-related attitudes such as (job satisfaction, job involvement, and employee commitment) jointly positively contributed significantly to organisational performance of selected state ministries in Oyo state.

According to the frequency distribution analysis, employees’ work attitude in the selected state ministries is generally positively high and rarely negative. The average mean score arrived at for the five (5) constructs used to measure its effect on organisational performance is 2.69. Work-related attitudes are the feelings employees have toward different aspects of the work environment. The employees’ work attitude variables in this study, job satisfaction, job involvement, and organisational commitment, are the three critical attitudes that are the most

relevant to important positive outcomes in any organisation (Malini & Atchyuthan, 2016). Employees' work-related attitudes are one of the essential yardsticks for better functioning and maximizing organisational performance (Hettiarachchi & Jayarathna, 2014). Furthermore, the frequency distribution analysis was made individually for the variables of job satisfaction, organisational commitment, and job involvement. The mean value of the distribution for job satisfaction was 2.48, and it depicted that the respondents (employees of state ministries in Oyo state) were "moderately satisfied" with their job.

According to the frequency distribution analysis of the variable of organisational commitment, the mean value of the distribution is 2.70. It shows respondents were also "moderately committed" to their organisation. When considering the frequency distribution analysis for job involvement, the mean value of the distribution is 2.47. Thus, it can be identified that the respondents were "moderately involved" in their jobs. Hence it can be inferred that performance would be highly enhanced as the satisfaction and involvement in their jobs and their commitment to the organisations will culminate into positive employees' work attitudes. This will definitely reflect in the energy, zealotness, and willingness displayed by employees in carrying out their functions and will ultimately positively affect organisational performance.

What emanated within the context of this present study, however, deviated from the general belief and the findings of another study that employees in public enterprises are poorly motivated, and as such, never satisfied and involved in their jobs nor committed to their organisations. The low level of their output is usually attributed to their negative work attitudes caused by unfavourable top management (Ezeanyim, Ufoaroh, & Ajakpo, 2019). The study found out that employees in public enterprises face the problem of working in an inconducive environment, and the government does not involve them in decision-making. Thus, the employees do not give their best at work, and performance is negatively affected. The study also discovered that affective work relations boost employees' work attitude, which is in tandem with the findings of this present study too. It is therefore imperative for the public sector organisations to consider the needs and feelings of their employees and not just overlook them, so as to safeguard industrial harmony. A happy worker, they say, is a productive worker. This study showed that workers place great value on having a conflict-free environment and motivation to improve their performances.

The hypothesis of this study, H_0 was to examine the relationship between the combination of the employees' work-related attitudes such as (job satisfaction, job involvement and employee commitment) and organisational performance in selected public sector establishments in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria. In precise terms, the hypothesis says, "There is no significant relationship between employees' work-related attitudes such as (job satisfaction, job involvement and employee commitment) and organisational performance in selected public sector establishments in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria.

With a multiple regression approach in statistically evaluating the testing of this hypothesis, the result revealed that the R value of the model is 0.517. R-squared value of the stepwise regression model was 0.267, indicating that employee' work-related attitudes accounted for 26.7% of the variance in organisational performance. The F value was 6.662, which was significant at 5% ($P=0.010$), which suggests that work-related attitudes have significantly explained 26.7% of the variance of organisational performance. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted, as there was a 26.7% impact of employees work-related attitudes on organisational performance, which was significant at 0.010. (0.010.).

Hence, employees' work-related attitudes such as (job satisfaction, job involvement, and employee commitment) jointly positively contributed significantly to organisational performance of selected state ministries in Oyo state. Also, the three (3) employees' work-related attitudes (job satisfaction, job involvement, and employee commitment) are positively individually significant to organisational performance of selected state ministries in Oyo state.

The findings of the study show that there is a significant relationship between employees' work-related attitudes and organisational performance of the employees of the state ministries in Oyo state. Also, there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance. Previous studies suggested that job satisfaction always has an impact on several work-related outcomes like job performance, absenteeism, and voluntary turnover. It has been typically assumed by most people associated with the human relations movement that job satisfaction is consistently positively associated with job performance (Hettiararchchi&Jayarathna, 2014). Human relations might be described as an attempt to increase productivity by satisfying the needs of employees and subsequently increase job performance (Kuranchie-Mensah&Amponsah-Tawiah, 2016).

As indicated in the empirical data, that there is a positive relationship between organisational commitment and performance. Previous studies have demonstrated that organisational commitment is positively related to employee job performance. The main thrust of the notion of commitment is that it can influence individual actions independently of other factors. Indeed, as a stabilizing psychological configuration giving direction to behaviour, commitment can lead to persistence in a specific course of action, even in the face of conflicting motives or attitudes, and may make individuals behave in ways that, from the perspective of neutral observers, might seem contrary to their own self-interest (Bornman &Wessels, 2018).

Also, it was found that there is a positive relationship between job involvement and job performance. Employees with a high level of job involvement strongly identified with and really cared about the kind of work they do. High levels of job involvement have been found to be related to fewer absences and lower labour turn over (Chi, Yeh, &Nguyen, 2018).

The finding of this study aligned with a past research, done to identify the impact of employee attitudes on job performance (Hettiararchchi&Jayarathna, 2014). The dependent variable was employee job performance, and the independent variable was employee work-related attitudes measured with three sub-variables named; job satisfaction, organisational commitment, and job involvement. These employee work-related attitudes, job satisfaction, organisational commitment, and job involvement were found to be significantly related to organisational behaviour.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined the interaction of Employees' Attitude, and Organisational Performance in Selected Public Sector Establishments in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Employees' attitude is a vital locus point for influencing, determining, and attaining effectiveness, efficiency, and organisational performance. Hence, employers must strive to create a conducive work environment that can stimulate employees' ability to develop, engage, and be empowered in their jobs. Employees' attitude is mainly influenced by the owners and top management in any organisation. As such, they must strive to ensure employees' happiness and good well-being, which would, in turn, lead to positive employees' attitudes, lower conflict situations, and thus, high organisational performance. The mission of most organisations is focused on client/customer satisfaction through effective service delivery.

Based on the findings and conclusions derived from the study, the following recommendations are to be considered and implemented by relevant colleagues:

- i. Managements should endeavour to create a conducive work environment that can stimulate employees' ability to develop, engage, and be empowered in their jobs. Information should be disseminated, or orders should be given clearly, by formally instructing employees on the use of written guidelines such as memos, circulars, and procedures to prevent communication gaps so that employees will have a clear understanding and correct interpretation of all information and instructions.

- ii. Employees should be informed and given adequate orientation on the shared beliefs, practices, norms, values as well as policies within the organisation, as this would get them more committed to the organisation.
- iii. Value should be given for employees' suggestions as most employees are aware of the best way of handling tasks through experience, and there should be an opportunity to take feedback from the customer face-to-face (negative or positive). This is because employees' attitudes are most positive when based on open communication and understanding of management goals and other employees.

Reference

- 3 Components of Attitudes (2021). Retrieved from: <https://www.iedunote.com/components-of-attitudes#:~:text=Behavioral%20Component.,Cognitive%20Component,general%20knowledge%20of%20a%20person.>
- Adeyinka, J. A. Ogunyemi, K. & Otapo, T. W. (2011). Implications of effective conflict management in organisational performance: Case Study of Nigerian bottling company plc. *Marketing & Management of Innovations*, 1, 257-280.
- Ahmad, F. M., Ahamad, A. S. Mohamad, Z. M. Z. MohdRoslan, M. N. & Abang, S. A. N. (2012). "The relationship between job satisfaction & turnover intention". *America Journal of Applied Science*. 9(9), 1518-1526
- Ahmed, W. & Osunsan. O. (2020). Employee attitude & customer satisfaction in selected hotels. *International Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Studies (IJHTS)*, 1(2) 144-150
- Ajay, S. & Bindu, G. (2015). Job involvement, organisational commitment, professional commitment, & team commitment: study of generational diversity" *benchmarking: An International Journal*, 1192-1211
- Ajay, S. & Bindu, G. (2015). Job involvement, organisational commitment, professional commitment, & team commitment: A study of generational diversity, *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 6, 1192-1211
- Aqeela, M. & Ramakrishnan, Vivek. (2018). "The relationship between high-performance work practices & employee attitudes; study on small business private sector in Colombo district" *World Journal of Innovative Research*.
- Brian, F. Redmond (2016). "Job satisfaction". Retrieved from: <https://wikispaces.psu.edu/display/psych484/11.+job+satisfaction>.
- Broeck., A. V. Lance, F. D. Chang, C. Christopher C. R. (2016). A review of self-determination theory's basic psychological needs at work". *Journal of Management*. 42(5), 1195-1229.
- Bronwyn, W. (2019). What is employee commitment? Retrieved from: <https://www.effactory.com/knowledge/what-is-employee-commitment/>
- Bronwyn, W. (2021). What is employees' commitment? Retrieved from: <https://www.effactory.com/knowledge/what-is-employee-commitment/>
- Business Dictionary. (2020). Organisational Performance. Retrieved from: <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/organisational-performance.html>
- Charles, O. O. (2015) Measuring organisation performance from balanced scorecard to balanced ESG framework". *International Journal of Economics, Commerce, and Management UK* 3(2)
- Chatterjee, A. & Kulakli, A. (2015). A study on the impact of communication system on interpersonal conflict, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 4th International Conference on Leadership, Technology, Innovation and Business Management. 210. 320 – 329

- Cheap, J. (2021). An abstract definition of attitude: Retrieved from: <https://cheapjewelryus.com/abstract-definition-of-an-attitude-is-a-psychological-tendency-that-is-expressed-by-evaluating-a-particular-entity-with-some-degree-of-favour-or-disfavour>
- Courtney, E. A. (2021) "Self-determination theory of motivation: Why intrinsic motivation matters, Retrieved from: <https://positivepsychology.com/self-determination-theory/>
- Din, S., & Rashid Rehman, B. K. & Zainab, B. (2011). An investigation of conflict management in public & private sector universities. *African Journal of Business Management*. doi:10.5897/AJBM11.363
- Domenico, S. I. D. & Ryan, R. M. (2017). The emerging neuroscience of intrinsic motivation: A new frontier in self-determination research, *Front. Hum. Neurosci.* 11:145.
- Employee Attitude Definition, Formula, and Examples. (2017). Retrieved from: <https://www.employeepedia.com/info/general/735-employee-attitude-definition-formula-and-examples>.
- Employee Commitment to an Organisation. (2018). Retrieved from: <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/mgt/employee-commitment-to-an-organisation.php>
- Employee Commitment to an Organisation. (2018). Retrieved from: <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/management/employee-commitment-to-an-organisation.php?vref=1>
- Ezeanyim, E. E., Ufoaroh, E. T. & Ajakpo, I.K. (2019). Impact of job satisfaction in employees' performances in selected public enterprise in Awka, Anambra state. *Global Journal of Management & Business Research, Administration and Management*, 1-11
- Gopinath, R. (2020). Role on employees' attitude in workplace. *Gedrag & Organisatie review* 33. ISSN 0921-5077
- Harada, Y., Sivanadan, S. & Ndanusa, Mohammed, M. N. (2018). Effect of productivity & perceived quality on organisational performance from lean management practice perspective. *Research Journal of Business Management*, 12, 1-9.
- Henry, O. (2009). Organisational conflict & its effects on organisational performance". *Research Journal of Business Management*, 2(1), 16 – 24.
- Ho-Won, J. (2020). Understanding conflict and conflict analysis. Retrieved from: <https://is.muni.cz/el/1423/podzim2015/MVZ208/um/59326109/Ho->
- Job Involvement** (2021). Retrieved from: <http://psychology.iresearchnet.com/industrial-organisational-psychology/work-motivation/job-involvement/>
- Job satisfaction and employee turnover. (n,d). All answers ltd. Retrieved from: <https://ukdiss.com/litreview/employee-turnover-2.php?vref=>
- Joyce, M. (2021). A positive attitude gives you power over your circumstances. Retrieved from: <https://www.quotespedia.org/authors/j/joyce-meyer/a-positive-attitude-gives-you-power-over-your-circumstances-instead-of-your-circumstances-having-power-over-you-joyce-meyer/#>
- Kendra Cherry. (n,d). Self-Determination: Theory and Motivation. Retrieved from: <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-self-determination-theory>
- Kendra, J. (2021). Self-determination theory and motivation. Retrieved from: <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-self-determination-theory>
- Market Business News (2020). Organisational Performance: Definition & meaning. Retrieved from: <https://marketbusinessnews.com/financial-glossary/organisational-performance-definition-meaning/>
- Mostahfezian, M. (2017). Predictions of conflict management strategy with personality traits in youth & sports department managers in Isfahan Province. *International Journal of Scientific Management & Development*, 5(11), 539-543.
- Mukolwe, E. Jacqueline, K. Eliza, B. Milka, W. & Joseph, M. (2020). "Effects of interpersonal conflict on organisational performance in selected hotels in Kisii town, Kenya". *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*. 4(1), 1-15

- Mukolwe, E., Jacqueline, K. Eliza, B. Milka, W. & Musyoki, J. (2015). Effects of interpersonal conflict on organisational performance in selected hotels in Kisii town, Kenya. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*. 4(1), 1-15.
- Pardeep, S. D. & Rakesh, K. (2017). Job involvement among college teachers, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research & Development*. 502-505.
- Pierre, R., Timothy, D. George, Y. & Gerry, J. (2009). "Measuring organisational performance: towards methodological best practice". *Journal of Management*. 35.
- Pierre, R., Timothy, D. George, Y. & Gerry, J. (2009). Measuring organisational performance: towards methodological best practice. *Journal of Management*. 35.
- Ryan, R M & Deci, E L. (2017). *Self-determination theory: basic psychological needs, in motivation, development, and wellness*. New York: The Guilford press.
- Saud, I. & Ahmed, M. (2016). Perception and attitude of employees of telecommunication sector towards the organisation. *Asian Journal of Management Applications & Research*, 7(1), 2230-8679.
- Saud, I. & Masood, A. (2016). Perception & attitude of employees of telecommunication sector towards the organisation, *Asian Journal of Management Applications and Research*, 7(1)
- Self-Determination Theory (2021). Retrieved from: <https://selfdeterminationtheory.org/theory/>
- Singh, D. P & Rakesh, K. (2017). Job involvement among college teachers". *International Journal of Multi-disciplinary Research & Development*. 502-505
- Sirajud, D., & Bakhtiar, K. Rashid, R. & Bibi, Z. (2011). An investigation of conflict management in public & private sector universities. *African Journal of Business Management*.
- Sirajud, D., Bakhtiar, K. Rashid, R. & Bibi, Z. (2011). An investigation of conflict management in public & private sector universities. *African Journal of Business Management*. 5.
- Types of Attitudes (2021). Retrieved from: <https://psychologenie.com/types-of-attitudes>
- Types of Attitudes at the Workplace. (2020). Retrieved from: <https://harappa.education/harappa-diaries/types-of-attitude>
- Vimala, R. B. (2013). Organisational performance with employees' attitude & behaviour respect to IT industry, Bangalore: An empirical study Retrieved from: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2210737>
- Wampande, A. & Olutayo, O. (2020). Employee attitude & customer satisfaction in selected hotels. *International Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Studies (IJHTS)*, 1(2), 144-150
- What is Organisational Performance? (2020). Retrieved from: <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/dynamic-specifications-norm-governed-systems/21528>
- Won, J. (n.d). Understanding conflict and conflict analysis.pdf.
- Work Attitudes (2021). Module 2: Personality, attitudes and work behaviour. Retrieved from: <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/principlesmanagement/chapter/2-4-work-attitudes>.
- World Bank (2020). Public Sector Performance. Retrieved from: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/governance/brief/public-sector-performance>
- Yashasvi. (2019). 4 different types of attitudes of people as per psychology. Retrieved from: <https://stylesatlife.com/articles/types-of-attitudes/>
- Zafar, B.N. (2021). **Types of attitudes**. Retrieved from: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/types-attitudes-zafar-bilal-nadeem>

ELECTRONIC WORKPLACE MANAGEMENT AND EMPLOYEE TURNOVER INTENTIONS IN ZENITH BANK BRANCHES ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Research Purpose: *The study explored the relationship between electronic workplace management and employee turnover intentions in the Zenith bank branches, Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the relationship between electronic workplace camera management and turnover intentions; and ascertained the relationship between electronic workplace computer management and turnover intentions.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The study adopted a survey design method. Statistics provided by the personnel department, Zenith bank branches Anambra State shown that the population consisted of 356 non-managerial staff. The researchers adopted a personal delivery and recovery during the administration of the instrument. Of the 356 copies of questionnaire that were issued out, 225 copies were completed and returned, thus showing a response rate of 71.62 percent which was considered adequate for the study. The hypotheses were tested using Regression Analysis with the aid of SPSS (version 20.0).*

Findings: *The findings revealed that electronic camera management has positive and significant influence on turnover intentions; and that electronic computer management has shown insignificant empirical link with turnover intentions.*

Originality/Value Added: *The study recommended that management of organisations especially banks should reconfigure their current resources and develop a wide range of policies and procedures involving camera and computers monitoring as well as communicating them effectively for successfully management of electronic monitoring system.*

Keywords: Management, Workplace, Camera Monitoring, Computer Monitoring, Turnover Intentions

Introduction

In large organizations, Shareholders elected boards of directors who with the help of employees as their agents run the day-to-day activities of the organisations. Immediately hired, the questions of how trustworthy are the employees and do they put themselves or their organizations first caused monitoring management (Wheelen and Hunger in Ifeanyi, 2015). An employee's intention to continue or quit an organisation has been a topic of considerable interest in the literature about organisational behaviour (Biswas, in Onukwuli, 2018). A variable strongly related to voluntary job mobility is "turnover intention". In this study "turnover intention" rather than turnover was used as the dependent variable. The importance of analysing turnover intention draws upon its role in forecasting and understanding the actual quit (Arshadi and Shahbazi, 2020).

Voluntary employee turnovers incur significant cost for an organization, therefore, employee's intention to quit is a situation that all managers try to eliminate as actual quitting not only leads to higher costs, such as referring to recruiting new employees (Sellgren, Ekvail and Tomson in Trivellan, Gerogiannis and Svarna, 2020). Thus, it is important to identify turnover intents as early as possible to enable managers to implement a course of action.

Electronic management is increasing throughout the world because of intense competition in a global economy (Schleifer in Onukwuli, 2018). For organisations to maintain a competitive advantage, they must reform their internal and external process through computerisation of workplace (Gupta, 2014). The rapidly changing attributes of information technology can be seen as affecting the employer's needs and expectation as well as employees' behaviour and role responsibilities (Coultrup and Fountain, 2012). These changes have mandated new roles

of technology monitoring and surveillance efforts by any organizations in an attempt to increase performance, decrease abuse, waste and control of undesirable employee behaviour. Traditional approaches to workplace monitoring include direct observation of work behaviour, examination of work samples, and review of progress reports and analysis of performance measures (Schleifer, 2020). Historically, employers have already attempted to improve these methods for monitoring workers' performance through electronic workplace management. Electronic workplace management (EWM) is not a new development; what is new is the use of EWM devices, particularly in the office and service workplace to capture employee performance on a second by the second basis. In effect the human supervision replaced by electronic supervision (Smith in Scheilfer, 2020).

Using an electronic workplace monitoring technology to gather information about employees is more problematic than the traditional forms of monitoring, as employees no longer have cover or secret from his/her employer who has the ability and capacity to conduct the monitoring of each of the operational activities of his/her employee without notice (Watt as cited in Osarenoma, 2014). Although it has been suggested that some turnover attributed to electronic workplace management is good for an organisation (Shaw, Gupta and Delary, 2015), the common view is that turnover disrupts productivity (Mueller and Price as cited in Haley, Flint and Menally, 2012). For this reason, it is critical that organisation gain a better understanding of human resources practices and procedures which affect voluntary employees' turnover. Some of the electronic workplace management methods used in the banking industry include; electronic video camera surveillance and electronic computer (email monitoring and blocking of social websites).

Thus, the gap in the relationship between electronic workplace management and turnover intentions needs to be filled in absolute terms including more proxies like, electronic camera management, and electronic computer management. Specifically, the study examined the relationship between electronic workplace camera management and turnover intentions; and ascertained the relationship between electronic workplace computer management and turnover intentions in the Zenith bank branches, Anambra State, Nigeria. The hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance and stated in a null form as follows;

H0₁: Workplace electronic camera as a management effort does not have significant positive relationship with employees' turnover intentions in the Zenith bank in Anambra State, Nigeria.

H0₂: There is no significant positive relationship between electronic workplace computers as a management tool and employees' turnover intention in the Zenith bank under study In Anambra State, Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Electronic Monitoring Management

It is important to define the meaning of electronic workplace-monitoring management in this study. There is a distinct difference between "conventional" monitoring management and electronic monitoring management. For the conventional one, it is a walk around or "over the shoulder" observation performed by the supervisor of the employees being monitored, where the monitored employees are aware of the monitoring activity. In contrast, electronic workplace-monitoring management is the use of electronic hardware and software to collect, analyse and report individual or group actions or performance (Alder and Ambrose, 2015). Electronic monitoring is defined as 'a system of home confinement aimed at monitoring and controlling and modifying the behaviour of defendants and or offenders' (Prison Reform Trust, 1997). Sentence involving Electronic Monitoring (EM) originated from the United States of America (USA) but programmes for offenders now operate in several countries

around the world (Ardley, 2015). Prison is a expensive form of punishment with high running costs and forms a big part of a country's criminal system budget. Prison overcrowding was seen as a problem that be tackled by EM.

Samaranayake and Gamage (2012) state that electronic monitoring is the use of computerized systems to automatically collect, store, analyse and report information on employee activities at work. They further stress that it is a device or system that allows an employer to observe what employees do on the job and review employee communications, including email and Internet activity, capturing and reviewing communications that employees consider private. Electronic monitoring makes it possible to monitor many employees simultaneously and to obtain much more detailed information at the same time.

Computer Monitoring

Technological advances have made computer part of every workplace (Friend and Media, 2016). They indicated that many companies store valuable data on computer systems, database and networks, and most workplace communication is done using computers. Computer monitoring measures employees' keystroke speed and accuracy. There are several types of computer monitoring system. For instance, computers can be programmed with software to monitor clerical workers thereby recording the number of keystrokes speed per minute, the precise time and location of any error (Ikonne and Ikonne, 2014). Data entry monitoring also give information on the number of times it takes to process or complete each task. With the use of electronic computer monitoring, financial control is achieved (Yerby, 2013). Financial Control (FICON) monitors the performance of the marketing staff using different Key Performance Indices (KPI) such as the number of accounts opened, a number of account reactivated, risk assets booked, deposit realized and income generated for the bank (Herbert in Ikonne and Ikonne, 2014).

Camera Monitoring

Camera surveillance detects employee theft, horseplay and safety (Mischra and Crampton, 2014). Employers use video surveillance to monitor their employees' behaviour. The use of Close Circuit Television (CCTV) as a surveillance camera mounted in strategic places in the bank such as the teller area, vault area, marketing hall, and customers' service area to detect fraud and monitor all the environments. The camera is mounted while the televisions are placed in the manager's office and head of operations desk. Some cameras are placed in open and noticeable area, while others be installed secretly so that the employees do not know they are present. The tiny fish eye cameras can go unnoticed for weeks. To provide critical surveillance information, Mishra and Crampton (2014) indicate that the reason why employers install such devices is to keep track of employee pilferage, horseplay, or safety hazards.

Turnover Intentions

Employee turnover refers to the termination of the relationship that individual members gain from organisation (Cao, Chen and Song, 2013). Price in Cao, Chen, and Song (2013) consider that there are two types of employee turnover behaviour, namely; voluntary and involuntary. The employees initiated voluntary turnover, while the organization initiated involuntary turnover resolving to terminate the employees' relationship (Cao, Chen and Song, 2013). Employees' turnover intention is defined as the ratio of organizational members who wish to leave the organization during a stated period (one year) considered by the average number of people in that organisation during that period (Mueller and Price in Haley, Flint and Menally, 2012). In the simpler term, an employee turnover intention is the series of actions that it takes from the employee wanting to leave his organization (Mba and Ikemefuna, 2012). It is utilised as an indicator of company performance and can easily be observed negatively towards the organizations efficiency and effectiveness (Glebbeekand in Onukwuli, 2018). The process of job turnover can be described as job dissatisfaction in the first step, followed by the intension to leave, which finally, in some cases, can result in actual turnover (Mobley et. al in Alam, Rahman and Talukder, 2014).

Theoretical Framework

Lot of models have been identified in literature on determining human behaviour and turnover intentions, this study is anchored on signalling theory.

Signalling Theory (Spence, 1973)

Recent accounting scandals have renewed attention to signalling theory. According to signalling theory, under information asymmetry, management/corporations with superior information transparency (electronic monitoring devices) signals better performance (Ifeanyi, 2015). Spence in Ifeanyi (2015) states that if information asymmetry exists between a company manager and the employees, the company manager can provide better information (to the investors) with the use of electronic monitoring devices to eliminate that asymmetry. The condition and assumptions underlying Signalling theory are as follow;

- i. Members of a social group/organization vary in some underlying attributes (physical condition, resources endowment, need motivation) that is difficult or impossible to observe but in principle be reliably signalled.
- ii. Observers/organization monitoring of employees stands to gain from accurate information about this variation in attribute quality.
- iii. Signals cost or benefit is quality dependent (the marginal cost of the signal is negatively correlated with the signal quality or the marginal benefit is positively correlated with the same). When these conditions are met, we can expect one or more design forces to favour a system of communication conforming to the signalling framework.

The importance of signalling theory to the study of electronic workplace management and turnover intentions in the banking sector is that it provides a coherent framework that ties a host of disparate social phenomena and unifies some seemingly unrelated wasteful behaviour by noting how a given action;
particular hidden attributes.

- i. Signal
- ii. Demonstrate how signals of attributes quality remain credible and provides Benefits to the management or observers.

Empirical Literature on the Subject Matter

In academia, it is hard to say that empirical researches have not existed in relation to the problem under investigation, unless the problem is a new discovery which no research has attempted (Ifeanyi, 2015). Ikonne and Ikonne (2014) examined how employers indirectly gather information on their employees in workplace. Some forms and method of e-monitoring and surveillance applications were identified. Rationales in favour of and against e-monitoring and surveillance of employees were also reviewed. Employers argue that e-monitoring and surveillance are indispensable for employees' effective performance and security of the organisation. On the other hand employees contended that workplace e-monitoring and surveillance is a system that infringe on their privacy and results to turnover intentions. It was discovered that one of the ways by which this conflict in monitoring be resolved is establishing a clear and balanced written policy regarding the implementation of e-monitoring and surveillance in workplace. The written policy is a part of employee's work contact and lead to the balancing of their rights of both the employers and employees to workplace.

Holland and Cooper (2015) examined the relationship between electronic monitoring and surveillance in the workplace on employees' trust in management in Australia. Data were randomly from responses of the 2012 Australian Electronic Workplace Survey (AEWS) of 500 employees from residential telephone directories. Analyses conducted using ordinary

least square (OLS) regression. Result of regression analyses identified that electronic monitoring and surveillance have on average, a negative relationship with trust in management. However, the magnitude of this relationship was relatively small across the entire sample ($\beta = 0.13$ for overall scale score). Nevertheless, in case of manual workers, the negative effects of electronic monitoring and surveillance on trust in management were much for manual employees ($\beta = 0.35$) for the overall scale score compared with non-manual employees ($\beta = 0.05$). The study recommended a balance right in an increasingly electronically monitored and surveilled workplace policy by human resource management.

Coultrup and Fountain (2012) studied on the effect of electronic monitoring and surveillance on psychological contact of employees using 92 copies of structured questionnaire administered to participants of full-time faculty and administrative staff from Southern Liberal Arts University. A two-tailed test and Pearson product-moment correlation analysis was used and significance considered when the p -value < 0.05 . Result shows that the only component that correlated with prior knowledge was a negative relationship. Employees felt that even if they had prior knowledge of electronic monitoring effects, still that it should not be done.

In a similar study by Gupta (2014) on the impact of workplace monitoring in India using survey responses from 147 professionals who are involved in IT related works in their respective organizations, hypotheses were tested using ANOVA method, where the independent variable was the level of monitoring in the organization and the dependent variable was responses obtained from trust, efficiency behavior and turnover. Result shows that the computer monitoring significantly and positively affects turnover intension. The study concluded that while workplace monitoring takes a hit at employee trust, commitment and turnover intentions for the organisation on the individual level. Employees find it harsh to leave the organisation for breach of privacy at the workplace due to monitoring.

Haley, Fruit and McNally (2012) investigated the effects of employee perceptions of monitoring procedures on turnover intentions. Random sampling of employees from an +inbound ($n=80$) and outbound ($n=90$) call centre was analyse using regression analysis. It was concluded that there is a significant relationship between camera monitoring and turnover intentions ($\beta = - . 23$, $p < 0.05$), time spent between calls has a significant effect on turnover intentions ($\beta = - . 32$, $p < .01$).

Methodology

The survey design method was used in the study. Survey design method is found suitable for this study because it is a valuable tool for assessing opinions, belief, attitudes, behaviour and trend. The design is therefore suitable for this study because it focuses on the views and opinions of non-managerial staff of Zenith bank branches operating in Anambra State. The primary data collected were extracted from the review of related literature on variables under study (electronic monitoring facets and turnover intentions) and modified into Electronic Workplace Management and Turnover Intentions Questionnaire (EWMTI-Q) by the researchers.

Statistics provided by the offices of the Zenith bank branches in Anambra State show that the population consists of 356 non-managerial staff. The population serves as the sample; hence there are no sampling techniques. The researchers adopted a personal delivery and recovery during the administration of the instrument. Of the 356 copies of questionnaire that were issued out, 225 copies were completed and returned, thus showing a response rate of 71.62 percent which was considered adequate for the study. The research hypotheses were tested using Regression Analysis to determine the strength of relationships between workplace

electronic management facets and turnover intentions with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.0 version.

Model Specification

The study established a model of electronic workplace management and turnover intentions through research objectives. Thus, the model used in this study was expressed in standalone variables (functional form). The model is specified as the following

Model 1: Stand-alone variables in functional form

$$\text{Turnover intentions} = F(\text{Camera Management}) \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Turnover intentions} = F(\text{Computer Management}) \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (2)$$

Stand-alone variables in testable form

$$TI = \beta_0 + \beta_1CAM + U_0 \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (3)$$

$$TI = \beta_0 + \beta_2COM + U_0 \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (4)$$

Where:

TI = The estimated value of Turnover Intentions (the dependent variable)

CAM = Camera Management

COM = Computer Management

CAM and COM = Independent Variables

β_0 = Regression Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ Are partial regression coefficient

Results and Discussion

The two hypotheses were tested to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the dependent and independent variables. The hypotheses are stated as follows:

- H₀:** Electronic security cameras as a workplace management effort do not significantly and positively relate to the turnover intentions of employees Zenith bank branches in Anambra State.
- H₁:** Electronic security camera as a management effort significantly and positively relates to the turnover intentions of employees Zenith bank branches in Anambra State.
- H₀:** There is no significant relationship between computer management (emails and social websites) and turnover intentions in the Zenith bank branches under study in Anambra State.
- H₁:** There is a significant relationship between computer management (emails and social website) and turnover intentions in the Zenith bank branches being studied in Anambra State.

Interpretation of Regression Results

Here, an attempt was made through the application of regression coefficients table, to test the “Stand-alone variables” in hypotheses H₀₁, and H₀₂. The hypotheses were conducted using Unstandardized coefficients in the regression analysis. Unstandardised coefficients indicate how

much the dependent variable varies with an independent variable when all other independent variables are held constant. The results of the hypotheses were obtained from the **Coefficient** table as shown in Table 1;

Table 1: Summary of Coefficients of Camera Monitoring, Computer Monitoring

Coefficients^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.132	.111		1.196	.233
1 SECURITY CAMERA MANAGEMENT	.274	.065	.538	4.247	.000
COMPUTER MANAGEMENT	.079	.049	.144	1.604	.110

a. Dependent Variable: TURNOVER INTENTIONS

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between security camera management and turnover intentions holding other regressor variables constant; the unstandardised coefficient for electronic workplace camera as a management effort was represented by $\beta_1 = .274$, it implies that a unit increase in electronic workplace security camera management will lead to 27.4 percent increase in employees turnover intentions if other variables are held constant.

Statistical Significance of Independent Variable (Security Camera Management)

We test for statistical significance of independent variable (security camera management), and show whether the unstandardised (standardized) coefficients are equal to 0 (zero) in the population. If $p < .05$, we can conclude that the coefficient is statistically different from 0 (zero). The t-value and corresponding p-value are located in the “**t**” and “**Big**” columns, respectively. We can see from the “Big” column that the independent variable coefficient (security camera management) is statistically different from (zero). Hence, the t-value is 4.247 which are significant at .000 because it is less than the chosen level of significance ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which suggests significant relationship between electronic workplace security camera management and turnover intention was accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between computer management and turnover intentions holding other regressor variables constant; the unstandardised coefficient for electronic workplace computer management was represented by $\beta_2 = .079$ in Table 4.3 above, it implies that a unit increase in electronic workplace computer management will lead to 7.9 percent increase in employees turnover intentions if other regressor variables are held constant.

Statistical Significance of Independent Variable (Computer Management)

We test for statistical significance of independent variable (computer management), and show whether the unstandardized (standardized) coefficients are equal to 0 (zero) in the population. If $p < .05$, we can conclude that the coefficient is statistically different from 0 (zero). The t-value and corresponding p-value are located in the “**t**” and “**Big**” columns respectively. We can see from the “Big” column that the independent variable coefficient (computer management) is not statistically different from (zero). Hence, the t-value is 1.604, which is insignificant at .110 because it is greater than the chosen level of significance ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, there is no significant relationship between electronic workplace computer management and turnover intentions.

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis, which states that an electronic camera monitoring as a management effort does not significantly relate to turnover intentions in the Zenith Bank branches in Anambra State was rejected. This hypothesis shows that electronic camera management and employees turnover intentions in the Zenith Bank branches in Anambra State are significantly correlated. The finding has collaborated with works of Haley, Fruit and McNally (2012) that employees' privacy is in the hands of their employers that use camera surveillance installed secretly so that employees do not know that they are present, thereby affecting their turnover.

The second hypothesis states, 'there are no significant relationships between electronic computers as a management tool in Zenith Bank branches in Anambra State and turnover intention was accepted. The finding of this study agrees with the work of Coultrup and Fountain (2012) that there is no significant relationship between electronic mail monitoring (computer) and turnover intentions. The result also contradicts the works of Degree and Jude (2016) that 76% of organizations are engaged in tracking internet usage.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the relationship between electronic workplace management facets and employees turnover intentions in the Zenith Bank branches in Anambra State, Nigeria. Voluntary employee turnovers incur significant cost for the organization; therefore, the employee's intention to quit is a situation that all managers try to eliminate as actual quitting leads to higher cost, such as referring to recruiting new employees (Sellgren, Ekvail and Tomson in Trivellan, Gerogiannis and Svarna, 2020). The findings of the study revealed that electronic camera management has a positive and significant influence on turnover intentions; and that electronic computer management in the Zenith Bank Branches in Anambra State has shown insignificant empirical link with turnover intentions.

Recommendation

From the above findings, the study recommends that management of organisations especially banks should:

- i. Educate employees about the reasons behind monitoring them through electronic camera and computers.
- ii. Reconfigure the current resources of their organisations and developing various policies and procedures involving cameras and computers monitoring and communicating them effectively will be vital to successfully implement monitoring system.

References

- Alam, J., Rahman, M. & Talukder, H. (2014). Identifying the reason for which people quit their jobs: An empirical study in the organizations of Bagladesh. Retrieved from www.academia.edu/8403929/on15/9/2021
- Alder, G.S. & Ambrose, M.L. (2015). Towards understanding fairness judgments associated with computer task specific monitoring: An integration of the feedback, justice, and monitoring research. *Human Resources Managerial Review*, 15:46–67
- Ardley, J. (2015). The theory, development and application of electronic monitoring in Britain. Retrieved from www.internetjournalofcriminology.com on 20/9/2021
- Arshadi, N. & Shahbazi, F. (2020). Work characteristics and turnover intention: mediating role of emotional exhaustion. *Procedia – Social and Behavioural Sciences*, (84): 640 – 645. Retrived from www.sciencedirect.com on 2/9/2021

- Cao, Z., Chen, J & Song, Y. (2013). Do total rewards reduce the core employees' turnover intentions? *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(20), 62-75
- Coultrup, S. & Fountain, P.D. (2012). Effects of electronic monitoring and surveillance on the psychological contact of employees. An exploratory contract study. *Proceedings of ABBS Annual Conference Las Vegas*, 19(1):219-235
- Friend, L. & Media, D. (2016). Benefits of computer monitoring in the workplace. Retrieved from <http://smallbusiness.chron/benefits-computer-monitoring> on 3/9/2021
- Gupta, C.P. (2014). Workplace Monitoring in Indian. *Academy of Management Journal*, 48:195-203
- Haley, M.L., Flint, D. & McNally, J.J. (2012). The effects of employee perceptions on monitoring procedures on turnover. *Problem and Perspectives in Management*, 10(3), 75-82
- Holland, P.J. & Cooper, B. (2015). Electronic monitoring and surveillance in the workplace: the effect on trust in management, and the moderating role of occupational type. *Personnel Review*, 44 (1): 161-175
- Ifeanyi, T.T. (2015). Effect of Board characteristics on corporate profitability in Nigeria. *Thesis presented to the faculty of management sciences, Chukwuemeka Odimegwu University, Anambra State, Nigeria*
- Ikonne, C.N. & Ikonne, C.N. (2014). Workplace e-monitoring and surveillance of employees: indirect tool of information gathering. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 3(10), 2349-2352
- Mba, E.S. & Ikemefuna, C.O. (2012). Job satisfaction and employed turnover in Total Nigeria PLC. Lagos State. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(14): 276-287
- Mishra, J.M. & Crampton, S.M. (2014). Employee monitoring in the workplace. *Advanced Managerial Journal*, 63(3): 4-11
- Onukwuli, A.G. (2018). Electronic workplace monitoring and employees turnover intensions in South-East Nigerian banking sector: *A Research Thesis Presented to the Faculty of Management Sciences, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Anambra State*
- Osarenoma, N.U. (2014). Electronic workplace monitoring and employees performance in Nigerian banking sector: A study of selected banks in Edo State. *A Research Proposal Presented to the Faculty of Management Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria*
- Prison Reform Trust (1997). Electronic tagging: viable option or expensive diversion? Prison Reform Trust, London. Retrieved from www.internetjournalofcriminology.com on 12/9/2021
- Samaranayake, V. & Gamage, C. (2014). A managerial incentive for workplace electronic surveillance. *IADIS International Journal on Computer Science and Information System*, 7(2):87 – 100
- Schleifer, M. (2020). Electronic monitoring. Retrieved from [Electronic Work Monitoring6.tm](http://ElectronicWorkMonitoring6.tm) on 5/2/2015
- Trivellas, P., Gerogiannis, V. & Svarna, S. (2013). Exploring workplace implications of emotional intelligence in hospitals: Job satisfaction and turnover intentions. *Procedia of the 2nd International Conference on Integrated Information, Social and Behavioural Sciences*, (73): 701 – 709, retrived from www.sciencedirect.com on 2/8/2021
- Yerby, C.U. (2013). Indigenous banks in colonial Nigeria. *International Journal of African Historical Studies*, 43(3): 7-11.

APPENDIX: Reliability

Reliability FOR SECURITY CAMERA MANAGEMENT, COMPUTER SYSTEM MANAGEMENT, TURNOVER INTENTIONS correlation and regression results

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	8.9
	Excluded ^a	204	91.1
	Total	224	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.975	4

COMPUTER SYSTEM MONITORING

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	8.9
	Excluded ^a	204	91.1
	Total	224	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.966	4

TURNOVER INTENTION

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	8.9
	Excluded ^a	204	91.1
	Total	224	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.975	2

Summary of Coefficients of Camera Monitoring, Computer Monitoring

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.132	.111	1.196	.233
	SECURITY CAMERA MANAGEMENT	.274	.065	.538	.000
	COMPUTER MANAGEMENT	.079	.049	.144	.110

b. Dependent Variable: TURNOVER INTENTIONS

EFFECT OF CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT ON PRODUCT QUALITY OF BREWING FIRMS IN SOUTH-EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Research Purpose: *The study focused on effect of Continuous improvement on Product Quality of Brewing Firms of South-East, Nigeria. The study sought to determine the effect of continuous improvement on Product Quality of Brewing Firms in South-East, Nigeria.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The study had a population size of 1528, out of which a sample size of 431 was obtained using Cochran's formula at 5% error tolerance and 95% level of confidence. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaire and observation and secondary data were obtained through textbook, and journal materials. Out of 431 copies of the questionnaire that were distributed, 401 copies were returned while 30 copies were not returned. The hypothesis were tested using correlation coefficient and simple linear regression.*

Findings: *Findings revealed Continuous improvements have a significant effects on product quality of the Brewing Firms in South East, Nigeria. ($r = 0.801; t = 26.965 p < 0.05$). The study concluded that continuous improvement to a large extent affect product quality in the Brewing Firms of South East, Nigeria, indicating that Continuous improvement ensure that set standard is put at the top of the mind of every employee and departments by producing quality product that will meet or exceed customers expectation in their daily activity and also their long term plan..*

Originality/Value Added: *The study recommended that Brewing Firms in South East, Nigeria should embrace continuous improvement which will help to maintain the realms of quality on a consistent and continuous basis, also enable firms to conduct market research and study on a regular basis having a drive in offering the products that stand as a testimony to the quality and its principles*

Keywords: Continuous Improvement, Product Quality, Brewing Firms and South-East, Nigeria

Introduction

The contemporary global marketplace has been putting enormous pressures on the manufacturing organizations to continuously adapt proactive, innovative strategies for enhancing their manufacturing capabilities (Ahuja and Khamba, 2008). To meet the challenges posed by the contemporary competitive environment, the manufacturing organizations must infuse quality and performance improvement initiatives in all aspects of their processes to improve their competitiveness. In contemporary highly challenging environment, a reliable production system has been considered as a crucial factor for competitiveness (Pintelon et al., 2006)

Today, continuous improvement plays a vital role in day-to-day strict schedules as it emphasizes on the customer, flexibility and quality in order to survive competition. It also helps the organization to anticipate what will delight their customers in the future (Zangwell & Kantor, 1998). The skills provided by continuous improvement include waste elimination, identification of process problem areas and improvement through the focus on what and how attention to detail and customer focus (Ndlovu, 2008). Continuous improvement being a quality philosophy system has been anchored with Resource based view (RBV) theory and system theory. The shared aims between continuous improvement and RBV has been surrounded in the belief that surviving organization will use resources and capability in a cost effective way, as they are limited (Attaran & Attaran, 2004). The relevance of the theory with continuous improvement is that for positive effects organizations have to constantly conform and align itself to the changing environment

The continuous improvement cycle consists of establishing customer requirements, meeting the requirements, measuring success, and continuing to check customers' requirements to find areas

in which improvements can be made. Customers may be internal or external, depending on whether they are located within or outside the organization. Internal customers are working towards external customer satisfaction (Chang, 2002; Cole, 2002)

Meanwhile, Bateman and David (2002) have noted that companies can have initial short-term success with available process improvement tools; however these are not sustainable. Process improvement programmes are useful projects for improving competitiveness, but the concern about maintaining them is well founded. Ljungstrom (2005) found that many companies struggle with their competitiveness in the market place. The global market has reduced the number of mergers and produced many large companies working at an international level. These companies strive to produce the best product at the lowest cost. The following obstacles are often encountered: the company is totally production-focused and does not support continuous improvement or cross-functional thinking; the ability to learn and create a learning organization is missing; no response is given to suggestions or improvement ideas; no management commitment; lack of resources; negative opinions on business improvement; culture of people not wanting to implement change; political issues in terms of managers trying to influence purely for their own gains and not necessarily in the best interests of the business.

Statement of the Problem

The continuous implementation of improvement program is expected to yield increased benefits; Continuous improvement is the everyday activities executed by a company in order to enhance its ability to meet customers' demands. Continual improvement can be achieved by carrying out internal audits, performing management reviews, analyzing data, and implementing corrective and preventive action, but when firms fail to improve on their quality they are bound to experience low customer patronage, low profitability index, inadequate satisfaction and collapse of the system.

Objective of the Study

Determine the effect of continuous improvement on Product Quality of Brewing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

Research Questions

With the above objective in focus, the study seeks to find answers to the following question. To what extent does Continuous improvement affect Product Quality of the Brewing Firms in South-East, Nigeria?

Research hypotheses

The study has the following hypotheses

Continuous improvement does not have significant effect on Product Quality of Brewing Firms of South-East, Nigeria

Review of Related Literature

Continuous improvement

Continuous improvement is defined as the planned, organized and systematic process of ongoing, incremental and company-wide change of existing practices aimed at improving company performance (Paneru, 2011). It focuses on elimination of non-value added activities in the process. Identification and elimination of non-value added activities in the process results to increased production, reduction of cost, time and improving quality. The organization's ability to learn, share information and make decisions facilitates the integration of an individual in a new continuous improvement practice. The continuous improvement practice desired by organizations are: waste elimination, flow, production scheduling, problem solving, standardized processes,

visual control and management, continuous improvement, respect for people, team work, leadership, long term focus and reflection (Womack and Jones, 2009) Continuous improvement means 'a commitment to constant examination of the technical and administrative process in search of better methods' (Fuentes-Fuentes et al, 2004).

Quality product

Quality is the performance of the product in relation to the commitment made by the producer to the consumer. Such commitment may be explicit or implicit in terms of written contract or in terms to the Quality Management expectation of the average consumer of the product. The performance of the product is concerned with the ultimate function and service which the product must provide to the final consumer. A product is known as a quality product only when it satisfies various criteria in its functioning for the consumer. In addition to the physical criteria, there is also a service and time factor to quality. The same quality of physical performance should be available over a reasonable length of time. Hence time is also a necessary aspect of quality

Continuous Improvement and Product Quality

Continuous improvement is a philosophy which focuses on the work process and people, with the major concern for satisfying customers and improving the organizational performance. It involves the proper coordination of work processes which allows for continuous improvement in all business units with the aim of meeting or surpassing customer's expectations. It emphasizes on quality in all facets of an organization with the aim of reducing waste and rework reduce cost and increase efficiency in production, continuous improvement is a firm-wide management philosophy of continuously improving the quality of the products/services/processes by focusing on the customers' needs and expectations to enhance customer satisfaction and firm performance. There are mixed results about the relationship between continuous improvement and performance. Mohammed (2006), asserted that Continuous improvement is an effective system for integrating the quality development, quality maintenance and quality improvement efforts of various aspects of a system so as to enable services at most economical level and derive full satisfaction. CI is aimed at the satisfaction of customers needs in an efficient, reliable and profitable way. It involves a radical direction through which an organisation perform her day to day operations in other to ensure that quality is put at the top of mind of every employee and departments in which they operate. The effective implementation of CI will increase customer satisfaction with the service offerings (Omachonu and Ross, 1994). Quality enhances customer loyalty through satisfaction; this in turn can generate repeat business and lead to the attraction of new customers through positive word of mouth. The word of mouth communication will help in cost reduction. This Omachonu and Ross (1994), noted will provide competitive edge to the company. The improvement in quality will result in increased market share, profitability and customer loyalty. Implementation of CI further ensures that organizations change how they perform activities so as to eliminate inefficiency, improve customer satisfaction and achieve the best practice (Porter, 1996). Porter noted that constant improvement in the effectiveness of operation is essential but not a sufficient factor for organization to be profitable. Sila (2007), CI helps in improving the quality of products and also reduces the scrap, rework and the need for buffer stock by establishing a stable production process. He argued that CI will reduce the cost of production and time of production. Continuous improvement is said to reduce the product cycle time thus improving productivity (Huang and Lin, 2002). Many other CI practices such as training, information system management, relationship with suppliers etc have a positive impact on operational performance. The efficient management handling of these practices will improve efficiency and no doubt affect the profitability of the firm and the product quality of the firms

Theoretical Review

Lean Manufacturing Theory

Lean manufacturing theory states that the maximization of process velocity through the reduction of waste is fundamental. It provides tools for analysing process flow and delay times at each activity in a process. The focal point is the separation of "value-added" from "non-value-added" work. The Lean Manufacturing method originates from Taiichi Ohno's Toyota Production System (TPS) which is closely related to the Just-In-Time (JIT) principles (Shah and Ward, 2007). Lean is essentially aimed at the reduction of waste and inefficiencies within processes across the entire supply chain, and is focused on those activities that increase the quality and value of the product for the customer. The method stimulates continuous improvement cycles within all layers of the firm and its entire supply chain to reach increased process performance rates (De Treville and Antonakis, 2006). In the Lean process of continuously identifying and eliminating waste (Chen, Li & Shady, 2010), redesign programs are initiated to maximize the customer perceived value of a product or service (Gautam and Singh, 2008). In this process it is essential to know what aspects of the product or service the customer values to prioritize improvement initiatives throughout the supply chain. The adaption of Lean Manufacturing by U.S. managers and the explanation and analysis of the method by academics has proven to be a challenge, because of this the literature contains somewhat contradicting definitions (Shah & Ward, 2007), which can cause hazardous situations for firms wanting to implement the methodology (Pettersen, 2009). A study regarding these contradicting definitions of Lean by Shah and Ward has provided the following explanation: "Lean production is an integrated socio-technical system whose main objective is to eliminate waste by concurrently reducing or minimizing supplier, customer, and internal variability." (Shah and Ward, 2007: 791). This definition indicates the wide coverage of Lean within a firm or even its supply chain. The emphasis is on the reduction of waste within processes which leads to standardization, reduced cycle times, and an efficient process flow (De Treville and Antonakis, 2006), simply put, Lean is about doing more with less (Christopher, 2000). Lean is a way to continuously improve quality and performance of products and processes, as well as reducing costs and streamline the development of innovations (Gautam and Singh, 2008). On a supply chain level, long-term relationships with suppliers and customers regarding integration of information and physical flows are also incorporated into the Lean philosophy (Cagliano, Caniato and Spina, 2004)

Empirical Review

Rula (2017) did a study on the impact of total quality management on organizational performance Case of Jordan Oil Petroleum Company. This study aimed to examine the impact of CI implementation on organizational performance. The study was conducted in Jordan Petroleum Refinery Company (JPRC), the study sample size was (103) managers from different levels. The researcher depended on primary and secondary data. The results show that CI has positive impact on organizational performance.

Marcel and Ayankeng (2015) investigated the impact of Continuous improvement (CI) on organizational performance. Data are collected from manufacturing firms in the republic of Cameroon. Variables used to capture Continuous improvement (CI) are management commitment through leadership, Quality control, inspection, employee training, customer focus, benchmarking as the basis for enhancing product quality. Organizational performance was measured by Customer Satisfaction, Corporate Social responsibility, Cost Reduction, and Employee Satisfaction. We run a series of multiple regressions of organizational performance variables on explanatory variables defining CI. Results show that only employment training and empowerment has a significant impact on financial performance and corporate social responsibility; leadership commitment, quality control and inspection have a significant impact on cost reduction. However, none of the CI practices appear to have a significant effect on customer satisfaction

Muhammad, Flevy and Khalid (2017) did a study on the effect of CI on organizational performance: empirical evidence from the textile sector of a developing country using SEM . The effect of national culture on CI implementation is gaining importance; thus, several studies argue that the effect of CI practices on organizational performance needs to be evaluated in different social, cultural, and economic settings. Furthermore, this study also contributes in the important debate in the operations management literature related to convergence versus divergence argument in CI implementation. Therefore, this study provided empirical evidence from a developing country in South Asia. Data were collected from the member companies of All Pakistan Textile Mills Association by using a questionnaire. The questionnaires were sent to 210 textile companies and the respondents were quality or production managers. Structural equation modelling was used to investigate the effect of continuous improvement on organizational performance. The findings of this study indicate that IC has a highly positive effect on organizational performance. These findings support the divergence argument, which indicates that the positive effect of IC on organizational performance is not limited only to companies located in developed nations, but can also be equally achieved in other parts of the world.

Shehzad, Hashim & Rashid (2014) did a study on impact of total quality management on the Performance of Service Organizations in Pakistan. The objective of this paper was to evaluate the role of total quality management in service sector of Pakistan. First of all total quality management was implemented in manufacturing organizations and the results were outstanding in manufacturing organizations. Now a days, in service sector there are many service providers that provide the same type of services. But customers prefer the service provider that provides the best service. For data collection, interviews were conducted from the top-level management of hospitals, banks, telecommunication companies, educational organizations and airlines. Findings of the research showed a positive relationship between CI and performance of service organizations in Pakistan. This research paper was useful for improving quality of output in service organizations and it served as a basis for future research

Manjunath; and Arun,(2013) carried out a study on impact Of CI Implementation On Productivity And Quality --A Study at General in Motors KARNATAKA, INDIA .The objective of the study was to determine whether the implementation of CI leads to higher productivity and quality. The study was carried out at General Motors by collecting the primary data from the managers through structured questionnaire. The data was analyzed by descriptive analysis and Anova technique the result revealed that there is a significant relationship between CI implementation and high productivity and quality.

Hamidah (2015) carried out a study on the effect of Continuous Improvement (CI) on Productive Behavior of Small Industries of Cibaduyut Shoes. The main objective of this study was to explore the potentials and constraints that occur; thus would be able to become a model for advancing small industries performance of Cibaduyut shoes.The research was be conducted in the center of Cibaduyut shoes because that area became one of tourist destinations of domestic and foreign. The study is designed by using descriptive and verification method. Respondents are owners or managers small industries of Cibaduyut shoes, with a total sample of 30 enterprises. The data used were primary and secondary data. Data retrieval technique is to study literature, interview using questionnaires, and observe. The data were analyzed by using descriptive analysis and path analysis using IBM SPSS Statistics version 22. The research result indicates that Continuous improvement (CI) affects 71.7% on productive behavior the Cibaduyut shoes industries at the level of 95%, positively and significantly

Horsfall, Ukoha and Alagah (2018) carried out a study on total quality Management and organizational success of manufacturing Firms in Rivers State Nigeria. This study has evaluated the connection between total quality management and organizational success of manufacturing firms in Nigeria using primary sourced data as culled via structured questionnaire, using a sample size of 238 respondents out of a population size of 588. This study proceeded to use dimensions such as Product improvement, Process improvement and Customer cocus and measures such as

Employee and Customer Satisfaction with an encompassing moderating variable which is Technology towards integrating the unit of measures of employed variables. The study evaluated the activities of the Manufacturing sector in Rivers state. The study discovered that despite the inherent importance of Continuous Improvement, it has rarely been adopted by the managers, usually as a result of their gender as all sample managers were largely male, and majority of the managers had a strong knack for Process improvement and were mostly weak towards Product improvement which could also be attributed to their marital status as most of the respondent were married and might have maintained a stringent workplace behaviour due to their level of responsibility in and out of their respective workplace. A positive and significant relationship was found amongst employed variables showing that a rise in any of the Continuous improvement is very likely to give birth to a corresponding rise in their Organizational success status. It was thus recommended that managers are to invest in the time and resources to implement CI programs. This study also signals the importance of ensuring a supportive organizational environment through its technology for the effective implementation of CI.

Victor and Rosemarie (2017) did a study on total quality management strategies and organizational performance In Kenya: A case of Blue Triangle Cement Ltd. The general objective of this study was to find out the Total Quality Management strategies and Organizational Performance in Kenya. The specific objectives of this study was to: examine the effect of Leadership commitment on performance of Blue triangle in Kenya; to establish the extent to which customer focus affects CI strategy and performance of Blue Triangle in Kenya; to assess the effect of employee empowerment and performance of Blue Triangle cement. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize data while inferential statistics, specifically Multiple Linear Regression, was used to test the hypothesis. The analysis used Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 to help in data analysis. Leadership commitment was found to have a significant effect of performance of Blue Triangle Cement. The study recommended that the management should be committed to quality by providing strategic direction with respect to quality management strategies, which should be aligned to the firms' objectives. Finally, the study recommended that similar research be done in other sectors like manufacturing industries

Methodology

The study adopted survey research design. The study was carried out primarily through the survey research design and structured oral interview. Secondary data were sourced from books, Journals and internet. The population (**1528**) of the study consist of Nigeria Breweries Nigeria (Enugu Plant), International Breweries (Onitsha), Nigeria Breweries Nigeria (Aba Plant), Nigeria Breweries Nigeria (Awo nmama Plant) and Golden Guinea Umuahia. A sample size of 431 was realized using Cochransformula at 5% error to tolerance and 95% level of confidence. The total number of 431 copies of the questionnaire were distributed while 401 copies were returned and 30 copies were not returned. Instruments used for data collection were primary questionnaires and observation. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire structured in 5-point Likert scale and validated with the content validity of face to face approach. The reliability test was done using test-retest method. The result gave a reliability coefficient of 0.78, indicating a high degree of consistency. The hypothesis formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance and the hypothesis was tested using simple linear regression and correlation coefficient.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics of continuous improvement on product quality of the Brewing Firms in South East, Nigeria?

s/no	Questionnaire items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Remarks
	Continuous Improvement							
1	In my organization set standard is put at the top of the mind of every employee in their day to day activities	300 (74.81%)	82 (20.45%)	10 (2.49%)	7 (1.75%)	2 (0.50%)	4.67	Agreed
2	We aim at satisfying our customers' needs in the most efficient way	202 (50.37%)	170 (42.39%)	21 (5.24%)	5 (1.25%)	3 (0.75%)	4.40	Agreed
3	We have a company culture that aims at zero defects in all our operation	60 (14.96%)	330 (82.29%)	3 (0.75%)	5 (1.25%)	3 (0.75%)	4.09	Agreed
4	We depend on our customers to get our definition of quality	230 (57.36%)	160 (39.90%)	4 (1.00%)	5 (1.25%)	2 (0.50%)	4.52	Agreed
	Mean	3.55						
	Cronbach Alpha	0.915						
	Valid N (listwise)	401						
	Product Quality							
5	The products we make are targeted to meet the expectations of our customers	60 (14.96%)	330 (82.29%)	6 (1.50%)	4 (1.00%)	1 (0.25%)	4.11	Agreed
6	The determination of what we produce and how starts with our funding our what our customers want	212 (52.87%)	180 (44.89%)	3 (0.75%)	4 (1.00%)	2 (0.50%)	4.49	Agreed
7	We make every attempt to ensure that our products perform well over a reasonable length of time	240 (59.85%)	146 (36.41%)	3 (0.75%)	9 (2.24%)	3 (0.75%)	4.52	Agreed

	We are always committed to making sure our products function (perform) in accordance to what our customers want	292 (72.82%)	101 (25.19%)	2 (0.50%)	4 (1.00%)	2 (0.50%)	4.69	Agreed
8	We have a research and development team always working to make sure our product is as good as other similar products in the market	180 (44.88%)	207 (51.62%)	4 (1.00%)	8 (2.00%)	2 (0.50%)	4.38	Agreed
	Mean	4.44						
	Cronbach Alpha	0.934						
	Valid N (Listwise)	401						
	Overall Mean	4.43						

Source: Fieldwork 2021

Decision Rule:

If mean < (less than) 3.5 the respondents Disagree

If mean > (greater than) 3.5 the respondents Agree

Table above shows the responses to the likert scale statement and this sample mean (x) respect of the continuous improvement on product quality in the Brewing Firms of SouthEast, Nigeria. For the statement on in there organization set standard is put at the top of the mind of every employee in their day to day activities, the responses show that 300 (74.81%) of the respondents strongly agree that in their organization set standard is put at the top of the mind of every employee in their day to day activities, 82 (20.45%) and 10 (2.49%) were undecided while 7 (1.75%) and 2 (0.50%) disagree and strongly disagree respectively that in their organization set standard is put at the top of the mind of every employee in their day to day activities. The associated simple mean of the responses is 4.67. This shows that the respondents agreed that in their organization set standard is put at the top of the mind of every employee in their day to day activities; since the mean is > 3.5.

For the statement on whether they aim at satisfying their customers’ needs in the most efficient way, 202 (50.37%) of the respondents strongly agree that they aim at satisfying their customers’ needs in the most efficient way, 70 (42.39%) of the respondents agreed , 21 (5.24%) were undecided while 5 (1.25%) and 3 (0.75%) disagree and strongly disagree respectively that they aim at satisfying their customers’ needs in the most efficient way, giving a sample mean of 4.40 . This shows that they aim at satisfying their customers’ needs in the most efficient way, since the mean is > 3.5.

For the statement on whether there is a company culture that aims at zero defects in all their operation, 60(14.96%) of the respondents strongly agree that they have a company culture that aims at zero defects in all their operation, 330 (82.29%) of the respondents agreed, 3 (0.75%) were undecided while 5 (1.25%) and 3 (0.75%) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively they have a company culture that aims at zero defects in all their operation, giving a sample mean

of 4.09. This shows that they have a company culture that aims at zero defects in all their operation, since the mean is > 3.5 .

For the statement on whether they depend on their customers to get their definition of quality, 230(57.36%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they depend on their customers to get their definition of quality, 160(39.90%) of the respondents agreed, 4 (1.00%) of the respondents were undecided while 5 (1.25%) and 2 (0.50%) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that they depend on their customers to get their definition of quality, giving a sample mean of 4.52. This shows that most of the respondents depend on their customers to get their definition of quality, since the mean > 3.5

For the statement on whether the products they make are target to meet the expectations of their customers, 60(14.96%) of the respondents strongly agreed that the products they make are targeted to meet the expectations of their customers, 330 (82.29%) of the respondents agreed, 6 (1.50%) of the respondents were undecided while 4 (1.00%) and 1(0.25%) disagreed and strongly disagree that the products they make are targeted to meet the expectations of their customers, giving a sample mean of 4.11. This shows that the products they make are target to meet the expectations of their customers, since the mean > 3.5

For the statement on whether the determination of what they produce and how it starts with their funding out what their customers want, 212 (52.87%) of the respondents strongly agreed that the determination of what they produce and how it starts with their funding out what their customers want, 180(44.89%) of the respondents agreed, 3(0.75%) of the respondents were undecided while 4 (1.00%) and 2 (0.50%) disagree and strongly disagree that the determination of what they produce and how it starts with their funding out what their customers want, giving a sample mean of 4.49 . This shows that the determination of what they produce and how it starts with their funding out what their customers want, since the mean > 3.5

For the statement on whether they make every attempt to ensure that their products perform well over a reasonable length of time, 240 (59.85%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they make every attempt to ensure that their products perform well over a reasonable length of time, 207 (51.62%) of the respondents agreed, 3(0.75%) of the respondents were undecided while 9 (2.24%) and 3 (0.75%) disagreed and strongly disagree respectively that they make every attempt to ensure that their products perform well over a reasonable length of time , giving a sample mean of 4.52, This shows that they make every attempt to ensure that their products perform well over a reasonable length of time ,since the mean > 3.5

For the statement on whether they are always committed to making sure their products function(perform) in accordance to what their customers want, 292 (72.82%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they are always committed to making sure their products function(perform) in accordance to what their customers want, 101(25.19%) of the respondents agreed, 2 (0.50%) of the respondents were undecided while 4(1.00%) and 2(0.50%) disagreed and strongly disagreed that they are always committed to making sure their products function(perform) in accordance to what their customers want, giving a sample mean of 4.69. This shows that they are always committed to making sure their products function(perform) in accordance to what their customers want, since the mean > 3.5 .

For the statement on whether they have a research and development team always working to make sure their product is as good as other similar products in the market, 180 (44.88%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they have a research and development team always working to make sure their product is as good as other similar products in the market, 207 (51.62%) of the respondents agreed, 4 (1.00%) of the respondents were undecided while 8(2.00%) and 2(0.50%) disagreed and strongly disagreed that they have a research and development team always working

to make sure their product is as good as other similar products in the market, giving a sample mean of 4.38. This shows that they have a research and development team always working to make sure their product is as good as other similar products in the market, with the mean > 3.5 .

On the average, the respondents agreed that continuous improvement to a large extent affect product quality in the Brewing Firms of South East, Nigeria; with an overall mean of 4.43 which is greater than 3.5, (4.43) is > 3.5)

Test of Hypothesis

Ho: Continuous Improvement does not have significant affect on product quality of the Brewing Firms in South East, Nigeria

Hi: Continuous Improvement does not have significant affect on product quality of the Brewing Firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.1aa Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.801 ^a	.641	.640	.44641	.091

a. Predictors: (Constant), Continuous Improvement

b. Dependent Variable: Product Quality

Table 4.1b ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	142.017	1	142.017	712.631	.000 ^b
	Residual	79.515	399	.199		
	Total	221.531	400			

a. Dependent Variable: Product Quality

b. Predictors: (Constant), Continuous Improvement

Table 4.1c Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.411	.050		8.195	.000
	Continuous Improvement	.903	.034	.801	26.695	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Product Quality

$r = .801$

$r^2 = .641$

$F = 712.631$

$T = 26.695$

$DW = .091$

The regression sum of squares (142.017) is greater than the residual sum of squares (79.515) and this indicates that more of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the model. The significance value of the F statistics (0.000) is less than 0.05, which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance. The significance of the F value indicates that the model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable.

The correlation coefficient r has a value of 0.801 and this indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between continuous improvement and product quality. r square, the coefficient of determination, shows that 64.1% of the variation in product quality is explained by the model.

In the linear regression model, a low error of estimate with a value of 0.44641 is indicated. A value of 0.091 for the Durbin Watson statistics which is less than 2 indicates that there is no correlation.

The continuous improvement coefficient of 0.801 indicates a positive significance continuous improvement and product quality, which is statistically significant ($t = 26.695$). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted thus continuous improvement to a large extent significantly affect on product quality of the Brewing Firms in South East, Nigeria.

Summary of Finding, Conclusion and Recommendation

Summary of Finding

The finding at the end of this study focuses on:

Continuous improvements have a significant effects on product quality of the Brewing Firms in South East, Nigeria. ($r = 0.801$; $t = 26.965$; $p < 0.05$)

Conclusion

We can conclude that Continuous improvement to a large extent affect product quality in the Brewing Firms of South East, Nigeria, indicating that Continuous improvement ensure that set standard is put at the top of the mind of every employee and departments by producing quality product that will meet or exceed customers expectation in their daily activity and also their long term plan.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study and the study recommends that

Brewing Firms in South East, Nigeria should embrace continuous improvement which will help to maintain the realms of quality on a consistent and continuous basis, also enable firms to conduct [market research](#) and study on a regular basis having a drive in offering the [products](#) that stand as a testimony to the quality and its principles

References

- Ahuja, I.P.S. and Khamba, J.S. (2008), "An evaluation of TPM initiatives in Indian industry for enhanced manufacturing performance", *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, Vol. 25 No. 2, pp. 147-172.
- Attaran, M., & Attaran, S. (2004) The rebirth of re-engineering. X engineering. *Business Process Management*, 10(4), 415-429.
- Bateman N, David A (2002). Process improvement Programs: a model for assessing sustainability. *Int. J. Oper. Prod. Manage.*, 22(5): 515- 52
- Cagliano, R., Caniato, F., and Spina, G. (2004). Lean, agile and traditional supply: How do they impact manufacturing performance? *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 10(6).151-164.
- Chang, H. H. (2002) A model of computerization on manufacturing systems: an international study, *Information & Management*, 39(7), pp. 605–624.
- Chen, L, Li & Shady. B. (2010).How to make 5S as a culture in Chinese Enterprises. *International Conference on Information Management, Innovation Management and Industrial Engineering*. 3(9) 221-224
- Cole, R. E. (2002) From continuous improvement to continuous innovation, *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 13(8), p. 1051.
- De Treville, S., and Antonakis, J. (2006). Could lean production job design be Intrinsically Motivating? Contextual, Configurational and Levels-of Analysis Issue. *Journal of Operations Management*, 24(2), 99–123.
- Fuentes-Fuentes K, Fullerton, R. , and McWatters, C. S. (2004).The role of performance measures and incentive systems in relation to the degree of JIT implementation. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 27 (8) 711–735
- Gautam, N., and Singh, N. (2008). Lean product development: maximizing the customer perceived value through design change (redesign). *International Journal of Production Economics*, 114(1). 313-332
- Hamidah, R (2015) carried out a study on the effect of total quality management (TQM) on productive behavior of Small Industries of Cibaduyut Shoes, *First International Conference on Economics and Banking (ICEB-15)*
- Horsfall , D Ukoha, M and Alagah, K (2018), A quantitative exploration of communication's role in determining the governance of manufacturer-retailer relationships. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 33, 539-48
- Ljungstrom , M (2005) "Playing Catch-up with China: Challenges and Strategies for Smaller Developing Countries", *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management*, Vol. 21 No 5. pp 617- 637
- Marcel, T and Ayankeng, G (2015) investigated the impact of total quality management (TQM) on organizational Performance, *American Journal of Management Vol. 15(4) 69Marketing*, Vol. 20 No.6, pp.276-84
- Mohammad H, Flevy W and Khalid,L (2017) Impact of implementing total productive maintenance system on organisational excellence based on EFQM model, *Int. J. Business Excellence*, Vol. 8, No. 2, 197
- Mohammad, Z. (2006), *Nigerian aviation sector. Why not a TQM approach?* The voice www.nanka.org 30 Sep 2006 last accessed 30/10/2008
- Omachonu, V., and Ross, J., (1994), *Principles of total quality*, St Lucie Press, Delray Beach, Fla

- Petersson, P., Johansson, O., Broman, M., Blucher, D. and Alsterman, H. (2010). *Lean-Turn deviations into success!* Bromma, Sweden: Part Media, Gronviksvagen Deloitte MCS Limited. (2010). Lean and fit. Deloitte LLP
- Pintelon, L., Pinjala, S.K. and Vereecke, A. (2006), "Evaluating the effectiveness of maintenance strategies", *Journal of Quality in Maintenance Engineering*, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 7-20
- Porter, K., (1996). The gradual leaning of health systems. *Industrial Engineer*, 42(4), 50-55.
- Rula, A (2017) The impact of total quality management on organizational performance Case of Jordan Oil Petroleum Company, *International Journal of Business and Social Science Vol. 8, No. 1*
- Shah, R., Ward, P.T., 2007. Defining and developing measures of lean production. *Journal of Operations Management* 25, 785–805
- Shehzad , A Hashim, Z and Rashid, S (2014) Impact of total quality management on the performance of service organizations in Pakistan, *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences, Vol. 3, No. 6*
- Sila, I., (2007) Examining the effects of the contextual factors on TQM and performance through lens of organisational theories: An empirical study', *Journal of Operations management*, 25(1) pp83-109
- Victor, N and Rosemarie, W (2017) Total quality management strategies and organizational performance in Kenya: A Case Of Blue Triangle Cement Ltd. : *J.C.M.P., Vol.6(5):7-12*
- Womack, J., Jones, D. T. and Roos, D. (2009). *The machine that changed the World*. Rawson Associates, New York, N.Y
- Zikmund, W. G. (2003). *Business Research Methods*. Oklahoma: South-Western

CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT AND ORGANISATIONAL IMAGE OF TELECOMMUNICATION SERVICE PROVIDERS IN OGUN STATE

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Abstract

Research Purpose: *Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a strategy for attracting, developing, and retaining consumers by effectively managing their information and providing efficient services that improve the organisation's image. The study examined the impact of service delivery and knowledge management on the organisational image of telecommunication service providers among staff of Private Universities in Ogun State. Ado-Odo, Ota Local Government area was selected for this research because it has the greatest number of private universities in Ogun State.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The study adopted probability random sampling Technique to choose 343 academic and non-academic staff from a total population of 2,039 at Bells University of Technology, Covenant University, and Crawford University in Ado-Odo Ota, Ogun State. Data was gathered using a structured questionnaire, and the hypotheses were tested using Multiple Regression analysis and bi-variate analysis in SPSS 23 statistical software.*

Findings: *The results showed that there is a significant positive relationship between service delivery and knowledge management on telecommunication service providers' organisational image.*

Implication: *According to the findings of the research, customer relationship management is critical for maintaining a positive organisational image.*

Originality/Value Added: *As a result, the research recommends that telecommunications service providers' management invest in developing strong customer relationship management methods and programmes that will improve the organization's image with its consumers*

Keyword: Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Customer satisfaction, Knowledge Management, Service, Delivery and Organisational Image

Introduction

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) was launched in the commercial sector in the 1990s, sparking research community and worldwide corporate interest (Soltani & Navimipour, 2019). The necessity for the development of a new business environment served as the foundation for this strategy which provides the possibility for customer relationship management. Since the corporate world's focus has shifted from product orientation to customer orientation, it is believed that improving customer interactions leads to profitable and sustainable revenue development (Zareie & Navimipour, 2019). Evidence from literature revealed that connections formed between service providers and consumers have a beneficial impact on customer-to-firm interactions (Sivaraks, Krairit & Tang, 2018). CRM focuses on improving, sustaining, and establishing long-term relationships with customers (Moreno & Melendez, 2019), and is based on data gathering prior to decision making (Khosravifar, Bentahar, Gomrokchi & Alam, 2018).

CRM, according to Arantola (2014), is a comprehensive strategy and process for attracting, retaining, and collaborating with targeted customers in order to increase value for both the company and the customer. The significance of customer data as a significant organisational asset has been emphasised even more in current CRM system development (Peltier, Zahay & Lehmann, 2017). Furthermore, CRM operation, which enables the execution and development of more effective and efficient customer-focused initiatives, contributes to the firm's performance (Chang, Park & Chaiy, 2019). Technology may help an organisation enhance its operational processes and, as a consequence, its image.

Many businesses rely on their public image to stay competitive and steady in the face of rising demand for their products in the short, medium, and long term. The public and audience evaluate an organization's efficiency based on its public image (Druteikiene, 2011).

The public's or an organization's personnel's evaluation of its differentiating and comparative characteristics forms the foundation of the organization's image (Bromley, 2014). Individuals' interpretations of the organization's information or disinformation are reflected in the organization's image (Buttle 2012).

Organizational image, according to Perez and Torres (2017), is a subjective knowledge, attitude, and combination of the qualities of a business's product or service. The organisational image, on the other hand, is part of a collection of individual views on an organisation, its features, procedures, and products, according to these authors (goods or services) (goods or services). Individual perceptions, interests, and roles that each person plays in regard to a specific organisation are therefore determined by the ideas communicated by a society that has asymmetries and is sensitive to individual perceptions, interests, and roles that each person performs in relation to a particular organisation (Blázquez & Peretti, 2012).

Telecommunication service providers in Nigeria have made many attempts to improve customer relationship management (CRM). These include, to name a few, knowing your clients and database management. Despite these efforts, society's opinion of Nigeria's telecommunications service provider's organisational image remains unfavourable.

Evidence from the literature also showed that few research on CRM and organisational image have been performed in developing nations' communications sectors, particularly among the staff of private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria. As a result, the research was prompted to investigate the impact of service delivery and knowledge management on the organisational image of a telecommunication service provider among staff at private tertiary institutions in Ogun State.

The goal of this research was to look at how customer relationship management affects the organisational image of telecommunications service providers. More specifically, this study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. To what extent is the effect of service delivery on organisational image?
- ii. What is the effect of knowledge management on organisational image?

Literature Review

Customer Relationship Management

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a well-established concept. It began as database management, when data was collected in spreadsheets and retrieved only for the purpose of selling. In the twentieth century, it developed into relationship marketing, when critical tasks such as data mining were done. Finally, it assumed the form of today's CRM, the pinnacle of customer centricism. It has evolved into a need for a successful company and a competitive advantage. CRM is currently utilised by large corporations, despite the fact that it is relevant to virtually all types of businesses (Das, Minsha & Mohanty, 2018).

Relational interactions are the basis of CRM. It refers to all marketing efforts aimed at building, cultivating, and sustaining successful connections. Its goal is to recruit, maintain, and improve customer relationships with both current and prospective consumers. CRM developed from database marketing to relationship marketing and ultimately to its current form. Customer relationship management (CRM) is used in many aspects of business, including customer service, customer participation in the company, customisation, communication, incentives, and so on. At the corporate level, it is used to steer all of the firm's efforts toward the consumer. CRM installation at the departmental level was less effective, whereas deployment at the corporate level

was more successful. CRM has become one of the key components of a business as a consequence of competitiveness and globalisation. Firms may survive and thrive by acquiring and retaining valued consumers. It is feasible if the company provides value at every client contact, and it is simple if the company knows and understands its consumers well. CRM enables businesses to better understand their customers and make more informed decisions. As a result, it is a need for the existence of a company. Customer life cycle management, which encompasses acquisition, satisfaction, retention, and development, is also aided by CRM. The main aim of CRM is to discover and apply the best CRM practises in order to manage the customer life cycle (Das, Minsha & Mohanty, 2018).

For the first time, Gartner (2016) defined the top four practises that contribute to CRM success, as well as four areas where those practises should be implemented. Vision, strategy, valued customer experience, and organisational cooperation are the four approaches, while process, information, technology, and metrics are the four areas where they should be utilised. It is often referred to as the "eight CRM building pieces." This research is based on Gartner's first four building blocks, which are the best CRM practises and their impact on brand image.

Vision: It encompasses all procedures required to create the image of a customer-centric business. It comprises of top-down leadership development, dedication to the CRM concept, clarity on CRM goals, CRM benefits, and its distinctiveness.

Strategy: Customers must be converted into assets through strategies. It is feasible to do this through providing consumer value propositions. Long-term road maps must be developed by organisations in order to fit choices and define objectives into action. CRM must be seen as a synthesis of technology, people, and processes.

Valued customer experience: It shows how customers develop ideas about a business based on their experiences with it. Customers should be involved in the CRM process to offer ongoing value. All channels should be linked, and the basics should be prioritised. Change and communication must be effectively managed.

Organisational Collaboration: CRM needs a cultural change away from product-centric thinking and toward customer-centric thinking. It also needs structural and behavioural changes, cross-functional team formation, change management and training, and the appointment of an overall CRM manager or leader. For such initiatives to be effective, significant cooperation across the company is required. CRM best practises like as vision, strategy, customer experience, and organisational cooperation may be applied to CRM processes such as customer life cycle management and knowledge management to improve customer happiness, loyalty, and brand image (Bromley, 2014).

CRM, according to Nasution and Rafiki (2018), is linked to the use of information technology (IT). IT abilities refer to skills, capabilities to resources and plans, and capacities to a company's capacity to interact, process, and display data. The size of the company and its industry sector both have a role in IT adoption in medium-sized companies, particularly when it comes to CRM technology adoption. This is because the volume, breadth, and complexity of adoption increase with the size of the business, and different industries have different requirements. CRM's primary purpose is usually defined in terms of the size of the organisation, its geographic location, and the industry in which it operates. When managers are able to recognise, observe, and meet the needs of their clients, it means they have built a strong bond with them and have a comprehensive understanding of their needs (Moreno & Melendez, 2019).

CRM is a system that generates, stores, represents, reproduces, and translates data. It is used to manage customer interactions or relationships and to better understand custom consumers (Gupte, 2011). Furthermore, Chawla and Joshi (2015) said that CRM potentials reflect skills and knowledge that may be used to improve, establish, maintain, and upgrade positive connections with consumers. They discovered a strong link between CRM and company performance. As a result, organisations should utilise their resources to build a solid CRM system that will help them

achieve their goals.

According to Salem (2018), CRM practises offer possibilities for providing services to consumers by partnering with a reputable mobile service provider. Furthermore, Chakravorti (2016) said that the use of sophisticated software as a CRM method has altered the company perspective. This emphasises its importance in terms of customer satisfaction and organisational success.

CRM is defined as a "concept based on the idea of utilising a mix of customers and marketing to create relationships." It is believed that building a connection with consumers is the most effective method to acquire their loyalty, which is defined as the amount of money spent on a certain brand and, as a consequence, contributes to a positive organisational image (Bin-Nashwan & Hassan, 2017).

According to Ibrahim, Hamid, Babiker, and Ali (2015), a tight connection with consumers necessitates strong management between IT and marketing departments in order to retain clients for an extended period of time. As a result, in order to achieve CRM, many organisations use tools, technologies, and processes to preserve the customer connection in order to boost sales and the organization's image.

The importance of customer happiness cannot be overstated, since satisfied consumers serve as free advertisement for the business (Kotler, 2013). It is claimed that retaining current consumers is less difficult than acquiring new ones. As a consequence, companies are developing methods to ensure client retention, as well as educating their employees to be more customer- and service-oriented (Josiassen Assaf, & Cvelbar, 2014). Client satisfaction is often cited as a major factor in customer retention. Nowadays, the goal of the company is not only to delight customers, but also to compete in the marketplace in order to accomplish its goals (Josiassen, et al., 2014). Customer satisfaction is defined as the degree to which a customer's needs, wants, and expectations are met throughout the course of a product or service's life cycle, resulting in repurchase, customer loyalty, and a positive brand image. The most important objective of a company is to emphasise a customer-centric strategy in their corporate and marketing initiatives (Bin-Nashwan & Hassan, 2017).

Service Delivery

How an organisation provides value to its consumers is a critical condition that allows it to concentrate on its customers. Service delivery is a method through which organisations strive to offer services and manage their affairs in a manner that is efficient, predictable, dependable, and customer-friendly (Opele, Afolabi, & Onifade, 2018).

Knowledge Management

Moreno and Melendez (2019) defined knowledge management as the discovery and analysis of existing and needed information in order to accomplish organisational goals. The goal of knowledge management is to utilise an organization's information to improve productivity, create new value, and increase competitiveness. Because there is no one definition of knowledge management, there are many classifications of knowledge management techniques.

1. Knowledge creation: Knowledge creation may be defined as the production of new or the replacement of old information. According to Gourlay (2015), knowledge production is the ongoing interaction between implicit and explicit aspects of information, as well as a rising spiral flow as knowledge travels via individual, group, and organisational levels. This has resulted in the identification of four processes of knowledge creation: socialisation, externalisation, internalisation, and combination.

2. Knowledge storage/retrieval: Organizational knowledge storage includes written documentation, structured information kept in online databases, encoded human knowledge saved in neural nets, documented organisational procedures and processes, and tacit knowledge gained by people and networks of persons.

3. Knowledge transfer: Given the dispersed character of organisational cognition, knowledge transfer is an essential technique of knowledge management in organisational contexts.

4. Knowledge application: Making learning more active and relevant for the business in generating value is what knowledge application entails. Organizations must apply knowledge to their goods and services in a variety of ways, including repackaging existing information, educating and encouraging their employees to think creatively, and leveraging people's expertise of the company's processes, products, and services (Mills & Smith, 2019).

Organisation Image

Many academics and scholars have provided definitions and points of view on organisational image. In this research, we will look at some of the views and try to come to a conclusion on the idea of organisational image. The common consensus is that an organization's image relates to its total reputation in the perspective of its external surroundings. The overall opinion a person develops about an organisation or its goods, according to Kotler (2013), is the organisation image. He went on to say that the firm's activities and behaviours toward the public shape its image. Bernstein (2004) suggested that an image may assist anticipate a person's behaviour toward an organisation. The definitions and images provided above demonstrate that an organization's image helps to define the connection that will exist between an organisation and the public. A positive image develops connections and enhances public patronage and acceptance of the organisation, while a negative image erodes ties. Other definitions and points of view include Lievens and Highhouse (2013), who defined an image as an individual's perception of a company based on past interactions with the company. It may also be defined as the cumulative impression an organisation produced on an individual throughout the business's communication function (Gregory & Wiechman, 2019). According to Bromley (2013), image is the sum total of the public's perceptions of a company. (Robert and Dowling, 2015) stated in their contribution that a positive image acts as a good incentive to an organization's shareholders to raise their investment in the organisation, recruit quality employees, retain consumers, and improve the organization's profitability ratio. Affirming this position, Adeniji, Osibanjo and Abiodun (2013) identified some reasons for an organisation to manage its image:

- i. To get a business edge that will lead to higher profitability.
- ii. To foster a healthy connection with the community in which the organisation works in order to prevent difficulties in recruiting, selection, and employee morale.
- iii. In order to persuade investors and financial institutions.
- iv. Increasing the organization's corporate goodwill.
- v. To provide workers a positive identity that will lead to their happiness.
- vi. Increasing sales and customer satisfaction.
- vii. Maintaining positive and amicable ties with the government, opinion leaders, and different interest groups.

Murray (2013) added his perspective on the issue, stating that a strong corporate image provides a company an advantage over rivals. He claims that they achieved this through promoting new goods, hiring the finest job prospects, and demonstrating profitability.

Hsieh and Li (2018) said in their submission that a company's image may be used to sell its goods, create lucrative relationships with consumers, and refute negative rumours or tales. They also identified three key elements that may assist a company in developing long-term connections with its consumers. These are the following factors: conversational reciprocity, reciprocal empathy, and mutual vulnerability. These allow for the constant flow and exchange of information, which aids in the development of consumer trust. Bromley (2014) proposed four kinds of images: product image, trade image, customer image, and firm image. Later, he subdivided the last category (firm image) into product image, customer interactions, employer role, and ethical image. Finally, Robert and Dowling (2015) stated that a positive company image may assist to decrease production costs per unit of output.

We may conclude from the above that the views and opinions of various stakeholders have a major impact on the organization's success. This illustrates the possibility of an organisation having numerous images. We have also shown that in order for a company to have a positive overall image, the organisation must address the perceptions, needs, and expectations of the different interest groups. We also believe that corporate image has an impact on the behaviour of different stakeholders toward the organisation. We shall conclude that a good image elevates an organisation to a new level of relationship management and customer engagement, which is the cure for guaranteeing a steady stream of turnover and revenues. As a result, every company should aim to make the development of organisational image a top priority since the benefits to an organisation are limitless.

Components of Organizational Image

Customer Interaction

A one-on-one discussion with a consumer is referred to as customer interaction. Chakravorti (2016) explained that before any interaction could take place, the company would need to split prospective consumers into various categories since each division may need a different approach. Customer segmentation into groups is critical for successful customer engagement. Today's degree of technology has made consumer contact both necessary and easy for companies. Businesses may now build relationships with consumers at any time and from any location thanks to advances in new media technology. Businesses may use the internet to rapidly react to client requests and inquiries at the customers' convenience (Chakravorti, 2016).

Lifetime Value

This is the business environment; companies must try to develop valuable goods for their consumers in order to ensure a steady flow of money that will keep them in business with their clients. According to Cetu and Brodie (2015), organisations may improve customer value by concentrating on consumers who will provide greater profit to the organisation. Long-term connections, according to Davies (2017), are important assets for companies.

Employee Attitude

According to Lindgreen and Antioco (2015), employees must have excellent knowledge, skills, and be motivated to grasp the best practises of customer interactions, which will promote trust and dependability, which are the foundations of long-term partnerships.

Managerial Practice

Any customer interaction plan relies heavily on the commitment of the organization's management. The management team is crucial to the customer engagement effort's success. The organisation requires a well-structured programme supported by suitable technological applications, with the top management officer taking the lead (Rigby & Ledingham, 2014).

Service Attribute

These are the qualities and permanent characteristics that are exhibited throughout the service delivery procedure. This, if not managed correctly, has an impact on customer relations (Opele, et al., 2018).

Organisational image, competitive advantage and profitability

According to Anderson and Sullivan (2013), a strong brand image improves a company's sales turnover by making it simple for consumers to make a choice. The level of service received by a client demonstrates the link between the firm's reputation and the consumer's happiness. It raises the number of consumers and decreases the number of unsatisfied customers, giving the organisation a competitive advantage over competitors. According to Weigelt and Camerer (2018), customer satisfaction contributes to the development of a good identity for the business as well as the generation of encouraging responses from consumers. Andreassen and Lindstad

(2018) also found a link between levels of satisfaction and the firm's identity. They said that a company's reputation generates an identity for the firm.

Meanwhile, Oliver (2006) describes customer loyalty as a consumer's conscious choice to continue patronising a company in the future, independent of rivals' effects. Loyalty in the context of the preceding merely refers to a customer's intentional commitment to establishing a long-term connection with an organisation. In support of this description, Bruning and Ledingham (2016) defined customer loyalty as a scenario in which a consumer purchases a product from a single company and subsequently becomes a self-appointed advocate for that company. In this research, they also support this point of view on consumer loyalty.

Andreassen and Lindestad (2017), on the other hand, established a link between a firm's reputation and customer loyalty in his study but found no link between customer satisfaction and retention. He conducted a study on the leaders of a specific organisation to evaluate their own business on six criteria: excellent service delivery, competence, innovation, long-term views, responsiveness to customer demands, and reputation. We think that consumers will continue to do business with a company if they are pleased with the services they get. Cetu and Brodie (2015) stated in their contribution that devoted and committed consumers would be ready to pay any price for a product, purchase it again and again, and become a booster of the business. It is also important to note that, despite the various perspectives that satisfaction links a firm's reputation to profitability, the link between corporate image, satisfaction, and financial performance has not been scientifically proven because the relationship between consumer retention and a firm's reputation has not been adequately researched.

Theoretical Framework

The research was based on stakeholder theory and the IDIC Model. Stakeholder Theory is a capitalism theory that emphasises a company's intertwined relationships with its customers, suppliers, employees, investors, communities, and other stakeholders. A business, according to the concept, should create value for all stakeholders.

R. Edward Freeman proposed the Stakeholder Theory of organisational management and corporate ethics in 1984. The Theory covers morality and values in organisational management. It identifies and models the groupings of a corporation's stakeholders.

IDIC Model

Peppers and Rogers Group proposed the Identify, Differentiate, Interact, and Customize Relations (IDIC) Model in 1995. The model aids in determining consumer expectations and their worth to the company. According to the concept, businesses should take four steps to create stronger relationships with their customers: identify, differentiate, interact, and customise. Figure 1 depicts the connection between the aforementioned activities.

Figure 1: IDIC Model of Customer Relationship Management

Methodology

The study focused on subscribers of telecommunication service providers among the staff of private universities in Ado-Odo Ota Local Government Area of Ogun State. Ado- Odo Ota LGA was chosen for this study because it has the highest number of Private Universities in Ogun State. The survey research design was used in the study.

The study's population was limited to three (3) private universities in Ado-Odo Ota Local Government Area of Ogun State and the Universities we're; Bells University of Technology, Covenant University, and Craford University. To make the research area truly representative of Ogun State. Using a simple random sampling technique, 343 questionnaires were distributed to academic and non-academic members of staff at the universities in the study area.

The study's sample size was calculated using Taro Yamane's method. The intended sample size is a function of the target population and the greatest allowable margin of error (also known as the sampling error) and is mathematically defined as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N \alpha^2}$$

Where n= sample size; N= population size; α= acceptable margin of error =0.05

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N \alpha^2}$$

n=? N=343, α= 5%=0.05

$$= \frac{2039}{1 + 2039(0.05)^2}$$

$$= \frac{2039}{1 + 2039(0.0025)}$$

$$= \frac{2039}{6.0975} = 343$$

n= 343 respondents

As a result of the computation above utilising Taro Yamane's method, the sample size utilised is about 343 respondents. However, 343 questionnaires were administered for the study.

Sample Frame

The sampling frame for this research is the subscribers of the Mobile Telecommunication service providers from three private Universities in Ogun State. The sample was generated using Bowley’s Proportional allocation formula: $n_1 = nN_1/N$

Table 1: Sample Frame

S/N	Name of Institution	Population	Sample Size (Allocation)
1	Bells University	479	81
2	Covenant University	1,130	190
3	Crawford University	430	72
	Total	2,039	343

Source: Human Resource Department of the three Universities (2021)

Method of Data Collection and Analysis

The data for this research was gathered using a structured questionnaire as a main source, and the data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The inferential statistics of simple regression at 0.05 alpha level of significance and bi-variate analysis (Correlation Analysis) were employed to evaluate all specified hypotheses, whereas frequency count and simple percentage were utilised to characterise demographic data.

4.0 Results and Discussion

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant effect of service delivery on organisational image of telecommunication service providers among staff of private universities in Ogun State

Table 2: Regression Analysis of Service Delivery on Organisational Image

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	129.067	1	129.067	175.739	.000 ^b
1 Residual	251.907	343	.734		
Total	380.974	344			

a. Dependent Variable: Organisation Image

b. Predictors: (Constant), Service Delivery

Source: Field Survey, (2020)

Table 3**Coefficients^a**

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.858	.153		12.145	.000
1 Service Delivery	.563	.042	.582	13.257	.000

Source: Field Survey, (2020)

Interpretation

Testing for the significant relationship that exist between customer relationship management and organisational image, Table 2 presents that service delivery is significantly related to organisational image since the p-value (0.0001) is less than 0.05 level of significant. Table 3 presents the value of the co-efficient of the regression model that exist between variables. The model is written as:

$$Y_{oi} = 1.858 + 0.563x_{sd}$$

Where Y_{oi} = Organisational Image; 1.858 = the constant or the intercept of service delivery and organisational image the two variable; 0.563 = the co-efficient of the independent variable and; X_{sd} = Service Delivery

Table 4: Correlation Analysis for Service Delivery and Organisational Image

Correlations			Organisation Image	Service Delivery
Organisation Image	Pearson Correlation		1	.582**
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000
	N		343	343
Service Delivery	Pearson Correlation		.582**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N		343	343

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, (2020)

Interpretation

Table 4 presents the extent of relationship that exist between Service Delivery and Organisational Image. From the table, it was discovered that there exist a positive relationship between the two variables with bi-variate analysis value 0.582 and testing for significance, the result is in agreement with that of the regression analysis with p-value =0.000

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant effect of knowledge management on organisational image of telecommunication service providers among staff of private universities in Ogun State

Table 5: Regression Analysis of Knowledge Management on Organisational Image.

ANOVA ^a						
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	183.771	1	183.771	319.636	.000 ^b
	Residual	197.203	343	.575		
	Total	380.974	344			
a. Dependent Variable: Organisation Image						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Knowledge Management						
<i>Source: Field Survey, (2020)</i>						

Table 6: Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.581	.130		12.139	.000
	Knowledge Management	.665	.037	.695	17.878	.000

Source: Field Survey, (2020)

Interpretation

Testing for the significant relationship that exist between knowledge management and organisational image, Table 5 presents that knowledge management is significantly related to organisational image since the p-value (0.0001) is less than 0.05 level of significant. Table 6 presents the value of the co-efficient of the regression model that exist between variables. The model is written as:

$$Y_{oi} = 1.581 + 0.665X_{km}$$

Where y_{oi} = organisational image; 1.581 = the constant or the intercept of the two variable; 0.665 = the co-efficient of the independent variable; X_{km} = Knowledge Management

Table 7: Correlation Analysis for Knowledge Management and Organisational Image

Correlations			Organisation Image	Knowledge Management
Organisation Image	Pearson Correlation		1	.695**
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000
	N		343	345
Knowledge Management	Pearson Correlation		.695**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N		343	343
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
Source: Field Survey, (2020)				

Interpretation

Table 7 presents the extent of relationship that exist between Knowledge Management and Organisational Image. From the table, it was discovered that there exists a positive relationship between the two variables with bi-variate analysis value 0.695 and testing for significance, the result is in agreement with that of the regression analysis with p-value =0.000

Table 8: Multiple Regression Analysis of Service Delivery and Knowledge Management on Organisational Image

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	199.712	2	66.571	125.237	.000 ^b
Residual	181.262	341	.532		
Total	380.974	344			
a. Dependent Variable: Organisation Image					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Knowledge Management and Service Delivery					

Source: Field Survey, (2020)

Table 9: Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.032	.179		5.772	.000

Service Delivery	.198	.050	.204	3.963	.000
Knowledge Management	.511	.046	.534	11.127	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Organisation Image					

Source: Field Survey, (2020)

Interpretation

Multiple Regression analysis of Service Delivery and Knowledge Management on Organisational Image is presented in Table 8. From the table, it was discovered that each of the independent variable has significant relationship with Organisational Image since the p-values are less than 0.05 level of significance. With the model presented below:

$$Y_{oi} = 1.032 = 0.198X_{sd} + 0.511X_{km}$$

Where y_{oi} = Organisational Image; 1.032 = the constant or the intercept of the three variables under consideration (One dependent and two independent); 0.198 = the co-efficient of the Service Delivery and; 0.511 = the co-efficient of the Knowledge Management

Discussion of the Findings

The study has so far examined the significant of CRM and its impact on the organisational image of telecommunication service providers. Based on the hypotheses tested the result of the objective one revealed that there is a significant positive effect of service delivery on organisation image which agrees with the work of Mmutle & Shonhe (2017), "Customers' perception of Service Quality and its impact on reputation in the Hospitality Industry". The study examined the customers' perception of service quality and its impact on a selected hotel's reputation. Findings from the analysis shows that the image an organisation represents do have a great influence on its customers, when these customers are not satisfied with the impression created; they tend to decline from patronising the organisation.

The result of objective two showed that knowledge management is a predictor of organisational image. The success prediction was 90.7% and this suggest that knowledge management is positively and significantly affect the image of an organisation at ($p = .000$) prediction success. This implies that the telecommunication service providers provide services as promised, dependable and accurate in term of keeping information that meets the need of their customers. The result of objective two was corroborated by Lindgreen and Antioco, (2015).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Two hypotheses were tested, the result of hypothesis one revealed that service delivery is predictor of organisational image. This implies that service delivery contributed significantly to the image of an organisation to the prediction success ($p = .000$). It is therefore concluded that service delivery positively and significantly affects the image of an organisation. This implies that telecommunication service providers give adequate attention and extra care to their customers.

Findings from hypothesis two showed that knowledge management is a predictor of organisational image. The success prediction was 90.7% and this suggest that knowledge management is positively and significantly affect the image of an organisation at ($p = .000$) prediction success. This implies that the telecommunication service providers provide services as promised, dependable and accurate in term of keeping information that meets the need of their customers.

It is concluded that the telecommunication service providers do not appear to be too busy in responding to consumer's request. Based on these findings, it was generally concluded that two null hypotheses were rejected and this indicated that Service Delivery and Knowledge Management positively affect the image of telecommunication service providers in Ogun, State. The study therefore recommends that telecommunication service providers should ensure prompt and quality service delivery to their customers as this will engender a good image of the organisation also monitor information on customers and use the available information to provide the services needed by the customers which in return improve on the organisational image.

References

- Adeniji, A. A., Osibanjo, A. O. & Abiodun, A. J., (2013) "Organizational change and human resource management interventions: An investigation of the Nigerian banking industry" *Serbian Journal of Management* 8(2), 139-154 .
- Anderson, E.W. & Sullivan, M.W. (2013). "The Antecedents and Consequences of Customer Satisfaction for Firms," *Marketing Science*, 12(2), 125–143.
- Andreassen, T. W., & Lindestad, B., (2017). Customer Loyalty and Complex Services: The Impact of Corporate Image on Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty for Customers with Varying Degrees of Service Expertise. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*. 9(1), 7-23.
- Andreassen, T.W. and Lindestad, B. (2018), "The effect of corporate image in the formation of customer loyalty", *Journal of Service Research*, 1(1), 82-92.
- Arantola, H., (2014)," Consumer Bonding- A Conceptual Exploration" *Journal of Relationship Marketing*, 1(2) 7.29
- Bernstein, D., (2004)," Company Image and Reality: A Critique of Corporate Communications" *Communication in management*, 261 (14), 254 – 266.
- Bin-Nashwan S. & Hassan H., (2017): "Impact of customer relationship management (CRM) on customer satisfaction and loyalty": A systematic review: *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies* 6 (1), 86-107.
- Blázquez, M., & Peretti, M., (2017) "Model o para gestionar la sustentabilidad de las organizaciones a través de la rentabilidad, adaptabilidad e imagen" *Estudios Gerenciales*, 28 (14), 40-50,
- Bromley, D.B, (2013)," Psychological Aspects of Corporate Identity, Image and Reputation" *Corporate Reputation Review* 3(3), 240-252 .
- Bruning, S.D. & Ledingham, J. A. (2016). "Perceptions of Relationships and Evaluations of Satisfaction: An Exploration of Interaction," *Public Relations Review*. 26(1), 85-95.
- Buttle, F. A., (2012). "The CRM Value Chain" *Journal of Business Marketing* 52-55.
- Cetu, A. E. & Brodie, R.J. (2015). "The Influence of Brand Image and Company Reputation Where Manufacturers Market to Small Firms: A Customer Value Perspective," *Industrial Marketing Management*, 36, 230-240.
- Chakravorti, S. (2016), "CRM a content analysis of issues and best practices", *Journal of Consumer*, 72(2) 201 – 215.
- Chang, W., Park, J.E., & Chaib, S., (2019)" How does CRM technology transform into organisational performance? A mediating role of marketing capability". *Journal of Business Research* 63(8), 849-855.

- Chawla, D., & Joshi, H. (2015). "Knowledge management practices in Indian industries: A comparative study". *Journal of knowledge management*, 14(5), 708-725.
- Das, P., Minsha, O. L. & Mohanty, Y. R. (2018) "The Impact of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Practices on Customer Retention and the Mediating Effect of Customer Satisfaction" *Marketing Intelligence and Planning Journal*, 10(16), 312 – 330.
- Davies, J., (2017), "Knowledge Management" *Technology Journal* 18(1), 211 -227.
- Druteikiene G., (2018), "University image: Essence, meaning, theoretical and empirical investigation" *Global Conference on Business and Finance Proceedings*, 6, 167-174.
- Gartner, Inc. (2016), Gartner Research on Customer Relationship Management, Available at www.gartner.com (Accessed 25April 2020).
- Gourlay, S., (2015) "Tacit Knowledge': The Variety of Meanings in Empirical Research" *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 22(5), 612 -629.
- Grazdane, I. (2013), "Customer Resources Management approach for Optional Retail Business: Helsinki Metropolia University of applied Sciences
- Gregory, J. R. & Wiechmann, J. W. (2019) "Communication and Reputation" *Business& Economics Corporate Communications*, 6(4), 173–82
- Gupte, M. (2011). "Mapping of information ow in customer relationship management too". Master Thesis, Binghamton University State University of New York.
- Hsieh, A.-T. & Li, C.-K. (2018). "The Moderating Effect of Brand Image on Public Relations Perception and Customer Loyalty," *Marketing Intelligence and Planning Journal*, 26(1), 26-42.
- Ibrahim, S. B., Hamid, A.A., Babiker, B., & Ali, Y., (2015)"Customer Relationship Management Quality and Customer Loyalty: Evidence from Sudanese Bank Customers." *Academic Research International*, 6(1), 252-269.
- Josiassen A., Assaf, A.G., & Cvelbar L.K., (2014)" CRM and the bottom line: Do all CRM dimensions affect firm performance" *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 36, 130–136.
- Khosravifar, B., Bentahar, J., Gomrokchi, M., & Alam, R, (2018)" CRM: An efficient trust and reputation model for agent computing" *Knowledge-Based System*, 13(8), 125-137.
- Kotler, P., (2013), "Marketing Management" Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Lievens, F., Highhouse, S. 2013. "The Relation of Instrumental and Symbolic Attributes to a Company's Attractiveness as an Employer." *Personnel Psychology* 56,123-151.
- Lindgreen, A., Antiocho, M., (2015). "Customer Relationship Management: The Case of European bank", *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 23, (2), 136 – 154
- Mills, A. M., & Smith, T. A. (2019). "Knowledge management and organisational performance: a decomposed view." *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 15(1), 156–171.
- Mmutle & Shonhe (2017)," Customers' perception of Service Quality and its impact on reputation in the Hospitality Industry", *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 6 (3), 132 – 148.
- Moreno, A.G., & Melendez, A.P., (2019), "Analyzing the impact of knowledge management on CRM success: The mediating effects of organization" *International Journal of Information Management: The Journal for Information Professionals*, 31(5), 255-269.
- Murray, K. (2013). "Managing the Single Greatest Risk Facing Business Today," *Communication Management*, 8, 142.

- Nasution, F., & Rafiki, A. (2018).” The Effect of CRM on Organisation Performance: A Study of Medium Enterprises in Indonesia” *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 21(6), 304 - 322.
- Oliver, S. (2006). 'Corporate Communication,' Kogan Page, London
- Opele, A.M., Afolabi O.J., & Onifade, T.A., (2018) “Consumers’ Preference and Satisfaction of GSM Service Providers among Students of Tertiary Institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria” *Nigerian Journal of Technology (NIJOTECH)* 37(4), 1099 – 1109.
- Peltier, J.W., Zahay, D., & Lehmann, D., (2017) “Organizational Learning and CRM Success: A Model for Linking A Organizational Practices, Customer Data Quality, and Performance” *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 27(12), 453 – 467.
- Perez, J.P., Torres, E.M., (2017)” Evaluation of the organizational image of a university in a higher education institution” *Contaduría y Administración* 62(23),123–140
- Rigby, D.K., Ledingham, D., (2014)” CRM done right” *Harvard business review* 82(11), 118 - 129
- Robert, P.W. & Dowling, G.R. (2015).” The Value of a Firm’s Corporate Reputation: How Reputation Helps and Sustain Superior Profitability” *Corporate Reputation Review*,1(2), 72–76.
- Salem Al-Said, S. (2018). “The effects of customer relationship management (CRM) practices in the Egyptian mobile telecommunications market on customer satisfaction, loyalty and corporate image”. *Arabic Journal of Management*, 30(1), 1-10.
- Sivaraks, P., Krairit, D., & Tang, C. S., (2018) “Effects of e-CRM on customer–bank relationship quality and outcomes: The case of Thailand” *The Journal of High Technology Management Research* 22(2), 141-157.
- Soltani, Z., Navimipour, N.J., (2019) “Customer relationship management mechanisms: A systematic review of the state of the art literature and recommendations for future research” *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 9 (11), 667-688.
- Weigelt, K., Camerer, C. (2018). “Reputation and Corporate Strategy: A Review of Recent Theory and Applications,” *Strategic Management Journal*, 9, 443 – 454.
- Zareie, B., Navimipour, N.J., (2019)” The impact of electronic environmental knowledge on the environmental behaviours of people” *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 11(13), 1-8.